

D4.3 Computational analysis report

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Executive Summary

This document reports the results of the different computational analyses performed on the data collected in the project.

After a brief introduction, the document includes several sections devoted to different kinds of analysis. In each section, we have first an introduction on the objectives of the analysis presented in the context of the Diamond project, then it offers a description of the methodology, and the presentation of the results obtained, organized by use case. Finally, a last section is devoted to discussion and general conclusions.

The computational methods employed for the data analysis include:

- Analysis of structured open data to define indicators that characterize the area surrounding each urban railway station (use case I) or docking station (Use case III) along socio-demographic, territory and mobility aspects, and to select relevant stations for the subsequent steps of the analysis (Section 2).
- Analysis of observations, to characterize the selected urban railways infrastructures (Use case I) and docking stations (Use case III) (Section 3).
- Analysis of experimental sessions in a simulator laboratory setting, to validate the impact of autonomous vehicles driving experience and passengers' emotional appraisal, considering gender and other relevant intersectional variables (Use case II), combined with the analysis of user satisfaction surveys for Use case II (Section 4).
- Analysis of social media data collected from Twitter, to get insights on the concerns of men and women regarding topics related to Use case I, II and III (Section 5)
- Analysis of user satisfaction surveys on service provisions (Use cases I and III) and employment conditions (Use case IV), exploring and assessing differences in user satisfaction according to their socio-demographic characteristics, by means of statistical tests, regression analysis, factor analysis (Section 6).
- Analysis of users and employees' priorities from Dynamic Augmentative Delphi surveys, employing Analytic Hierarchy Processes to assess the ranking between priorities for different groups of respondents (Section 7).
- Bayesian network analysis to obtain a weighted hierarchy of fairness characteristics, based on open and proprietary structured data, observations and UESI questionnaires, and a statistical assessment of significant differences between users along socio-demographic variables (Section 8).

While the document is structured along the different kinds of analysis performed, the final conclusions present a summary of the main results, organized per use case (Section 9).

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Terminology and Acronyms

ADAS	Advanced Driving Assistance System
ADS	Automated Driving System
AITEC	Aitec Asesores Internacionales srl
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
API	Application Programming Interface
AV	Automated Vehicles
BN	Bayesian Network
CBI-R	Career Barriers Inventory-Revised
CCTV	Closed-circuit Television
CF	Concept of Fairness
CFCs	Cluster of Fairness Characteristics
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DAD	Dynamic Argumentative Delphi
DDT	Dynamic Driving Tasks
ENU	Edinburgh Napier University
EU	European Union
EURECAT	Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Cataluña
FCs	Fairness Characteristics
FGC	Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya
FTTE	University of Belgrade
G&V	Genre et Ville
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAV	Highly Automated Vehicles
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HR	Human Resources
IBV	Instituto de Biomecánica
ID	Inclusion Diamond
IPs	Influencing Parameters
M	Month
OAPs	Old Age Pensioners
OSM	Open Street Map

<i>PI</i>	<i>Polyhedral Individual</i>
<i>PPE</i>	<i>Personal Protective Equipment</i>
<i>RINA</i>	<i>Rina Services spa</i>
<i>SD</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>
<i>STIR</i>	<i>University of Stirling</i>
<i>SYS</i>	<i>Systematica srl</i>
<i>TU Dublin</i>	<i>Technological University Dublin</i>
<i>UESI</i>	<i>Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires</i>
<i>UC1</i>	<i>Use Case I</i>
<i>UC2</i>	<i>Use Case II</i>
<i>UC3</i>	<i>Use Case III</i>
<i>UC4</i>	<i>Use Case IV</i>
<i>VELIB</i>	<i>Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib Métropole</i>
<i>WAVE</i>	<i>Wave Women and Vehicles in Europe</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>ZTM</i>	<i>Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa</i>

I. Introduction

The overall DIAMOND methodology (see Figure 1) introduced in D2.2 indicates how data collection tools and analysis fit in the project.

Figure 1. DIAMOND's overall methodology.

So as to be more concise, Figure 2 presents the methodological flowchart for the data analysis.

Figure 2. DIAMOND's data analysis methodological flowchart.

According to Figure 2, the responses gathered in the **DAD surveys**, that indicate participants' preferences, were analysed with the Analytic Hierarchy Process (**AHP**) (Saaty, 1987; Vaidya and Kumar, 2006; Saaty, 2016). This analysis provides the hierarchy of the Fairness Characteristics (FCs) Level 1 and Level 2 to those that were previously identified and clustered into levels with the Chi-square test in the thematic analysis (D3.1. Methodology and requirements for data collection). Meanwhile, the hierarchy of the level 3 FCs (also defined in the thematic analysis) due to the high number of variables, number that makes their analysis not possible using also the AHP, were assessed with the Bayesian Network (**BN**) analysis by using the data gathered through **structured data, observations and UESI questionnaires data collection tools**. The global weights of the level 3 FCs were calculated by multiplying the local weights of the level 3 FCs obtained through the analysis with BN, with the level 2 FCs global weight (which is a multiplication of level 1 and level 2 local weights) obtained in the AHP analysis.

The **UESI questionnaires** were not only analysed, jointly with the observations and structured data, through the BN analysis, they were also studied separately with:

- a **regression analysis** to determine the correlation between the variables collected by this particular tool and to determine which are the most influent socio-demographic characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual (PI). After obtaining the relevant PI characteristics, **ANOVA analysis** was carried out for all the FCs level 3 to determine the FCs level 3 with significant differences so as to consider the results in the Focus Groups (FGs) and semi-structured interviews,
- a **factor analysis** that grouped the FCs into groups with similar response patterns. A statistical analysis determined the influence of demographic characteristics of the users on the responses for each of those factors,

- Further **ANOVA** analysis on all the PI characteristics for the Top 10 FCs obtained from the BN and AHP analysis to determine, by another way, the significant PI characteristics on the preferred FCs.

The information coming from the FGs and semi-structured interviews was useful to determine important qualitative factors and fairness measures (FM) to be included in the Maturity Model table.

User generated content from social media was studied as a complementary data source, to obtain insights on the main concerns of men and women with respect to the different use cases from a larger base of users than the surveys' respondents.

Structured data and observations were analysed to characterize railways stations (Use Case I) and docking stations (Use Case III) along different dimensions, and to develop indexes embedding mobility, socio-demographic and territorial aspects.

For Use Case II, experimental analysis with a simulator was performed to assess the emotional reaction of different demographic groups of people to autonomous vehicles' driving experience.

However, this explanation of the data analysis is only a brief summary, each data analysis and its results are deeply explained along the different sections of this deliverable.

2. Analysis of Structured Open Data for the Selection of Urban Railway Infrastructures (Use Case I) and Bike-sharing Docking Stations (Use Case III)

Objective of the analysis and alignment with the general DIAMOND's methodology

According to the objectives of the DIAMOND project, Deliverable 4.3 proposes a data-driven approach for investigating the level of accessibility of urban railway infrastructures (Use Case I) and bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III) considering the women's needs. This is based on the use of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for the analysis of several geolocated open datasets related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain), the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland) and the Paris Region Petite Couronne (France).

The considered datasets¹ were focused on: (i) land characteristics (urban fabric of land use; points of interest); (ii) sociodemographic characteristics of the inhabitants (population density; gender, age and nationality of the population); (iii) mobility characteristics (transport services; road infrastructures; parking facilities). Data analysis was aimed at identifying a short list of suitable urban railway stations managed by FGC (Province of Barcelona), and ZTM (Metropolitan Area of Warsaw), as well as a short list of suitable bike-sharing docking stations managed by VELIB (Paris Region Petite Couronne), as characterized by high and low levels of accessibility for women.

The shortlisted urban railway stations and bike-sharing docking stations have been further investigated through on-site observations and questionnaires, to characterize them according to universal design indicators and women's needs and expectations. The disaggregated data have been used to understand and trace the mobility patterns of women, to investigate their opinion and to identify the factors that are important to them, in order to plan and design a fair, gender equitable and integrated urban public transport network.

Data and methods

The proposed methodological approach is based on a series of structured open datasets (see

¹ See: 'Deliverable 4.1 Dataset description'.

Table 1,

Table 2 and

Table 3), which were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open-data repositories, national geoportals and census databases.

Table 1. The list of open data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant urban railway infrastructures managed by FGC.

Data typology	Indicator	Data source	Year
Preliminary Data	Province of Barcelona	Cartographic Institute Catalunya	2019
	Census sections	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	FGC stations	Barcelona's City Hall Data Service	2019
Territorial data	Urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
	Points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
Socio-demographic data	Total population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Gender of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Age of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Nationality of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
Mobility data	Public transport	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Road infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019

Table 2. The list of open data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant urban railway infrastructures managed by ZTM.

Data typology	Indicator	Data source	Year
Preliminary Data	Warsaw Metropolitan Area	Website Warsaw Metropolis	2018
	Census sections	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	ZTM stations	GTFS Data Exchange	2019
Territorial data	Urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
	Points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019

Socio-demographic data	Total population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Gender of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Age of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
Mobility data	Public transport	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Road infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019

Table 3. The list of open data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant bike-sharing docking stations managed by VELIB.

Data typology	Indicator	Data source	Year
Preliminary Data	Paris Region	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	2012
	Census sections	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	VELIB docking stations	Open platform for French public data	2019
Territorial data	Urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
	Points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
Socio-demographic data	Total population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Gender of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Age of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
	Nationality of population	National Institute of Statistics	2011
Mobility data	Public transport	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Cycleway network	OpenStreetMap	2019

Regarding Use Case I, the analysis was aimed at assessing the level of accessibility for women commuting by the urban railway infrastructures managed by FGC (82 stations in total) and by ZTM (96 stations in total), in order to identify and characterize a short list of suitable stations (ten stations characterized by high levels of accessibility and ten stations characterized by low levels of accessibility).

Regarding Use Case III, the analysis was aimed at assessing the level of accessibility for women using the bike-sharing service managed by VELIB (1297 docking stations in total), in order to identify and characterize a short list of suitable bike-sharing docking stations (ten stations characterized by high levels of accessibility and ten stations characterized by low levels of accessibility).

The indicators were analysed to design a multi-layer map of the considered territories² and to estimate the spatial distribution of each dataset considering the localization of the urban railway infrastructures and docking stations (see Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5).

Figure 3 Localization of the railway infrastructures managed by FGC within the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

² See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

Figure 4 Localization of the railway infrastructures managed by ZTM within the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 5 Localization of the bike-sharing docking stations managed by VELIB within the Paris Region (France).

Regarding Use Case I, the analysis was based on various attributes and characteristics of the urban area surrounding each railway infrastructure. To do so, raw data related to the urban scale were extracted for the surrounding areas of each station within a catchment area of 400 m (circular buffer areas of 0.5 km²), commonly known as comfortable walkable distance. Regarding Use Case III, raw data related to the urban scale were extracted on census section, due to the higher density distribution of docking stations.

The filtered data were post-processed through: (i) density-based calculation on catchment areas/census section; (ii) normalization of values (z values in a range between 0 and 1); and (iii) weighted formulas of normalized values to calculate the Territorial Data Index (TDI), Socio-demographic Data Index (SDDI) and Mobility Data Index (MDI). Quintile frequency distribution of results made possible the identification of the railway infrastructures and docking stations characterized by high levels of accessibility for the women (belonging to the highest quintile, $\geq 80^{\text{th}}$ percentile) and the stations characterized by low levels of accessibility for the women (belonging to the lowest quintile, $\leq 20^{\text{th}}$ percentile).

Territorial Data Index

The calculation of the Territorial Data Index (TDI) was based on the density distribution of the urban fabric (UF ca/cs) and Points of Interest (POI ca/cs) on catchment areas and census sections.

Land-use datasets include the localization of continuous urban fabric, discontinuous dense urban fabric and isolated structures. Data analysis was aimed at estimating the level of urbanization of the catchment areas/census sections since the level of accessibility of transport services for women greatly differs based on the urban or rural characteristics of the surroundings.

Points-of-interest datasets include a series of heterogenous services and facilities (e.g., commercial activities, bars, supermarkets, playgrounds, sport facilities, nightclubs, university facilities, public services, tourist attractions, etc.). Data analysis was aimed at assessing the level of attractiveness of the railway infrastructures/docking stations, considering the needs of different users' profile (e.g., commuters, students, tourists).

$$TDI = (KUF \cdot UF \text{ ca/cs}) + (KPOI \cdot POI \text{ ca/cs})$$

TDI was calculated through the weighted summation of normalized density-distribution values of urban fabric and points of interest on catchment areas/census sections. The constant parameters KUF and KPOI were equally balanced (Σ constant parameters = 1).

Socio-demographic Data Index

The calculation of the Sociodemographic Data Index (SDDI) was based on the density distribution of the Total Population (TP ca/cs), Female Population (FeP ca/cs), Elderly Population³ (EP ca/cs) and Foreigner Population (FoP ca/cs) on census sections.

Data analysis was aimed at estimating the density distribution of the population and age, gender and nationality characteristics of the inhabitants living in the catchment areas surrounding the urban railway infrastructures and docking stations, as potential users of the transport service. The calculation of the SDDI relies on the density distribution of the population on the urban fabrics, to balance the population density between urban and rural areas.

$$SDDI = (KTP \cdot TP \text{ ca/cs}) + (KFeP \cdot FeP \text{ ca/cs}) + (KEP \cdot EP \text{ ca/cs}) + (KFoP \cdot FoP \text{ ca/cs})$$

³ Elderly population dataset includes the spatial distribution of the inhabitants being over 64 years old.

SDDI was calculated through the weighted summation of normalized density distribution values of total population, female population, elderly population and foreigner population on urban fabric of catchment areas/census sections. The constant parameters KTP (corresponding to 0.3), KFeP (corresponding to 0.3), KEP (corresponding to 0.2) and KFoP (corresponding to 0.2) were weighted to accentuate the impact of the density distribution of the total and female populations on SDDI (\sum constant parameters = 1).

Mobility Data Index

The calculation of the Mobility Data Index (MDI) was based on the density distribution of Public Transports (PT ca/cs), Road/Cycleway Infrastructure (RCI ca/cs) and Parking Facilities (PF ca/cs) on the catchment areas/census sections.

Public-transport datasets include the spatial distribution of the total number of metro and commuter railway stations, bus stops, tram stops and taxi stations. Data analysis was aimed at estimating the level of connectivity of the railway infrastructures and docking stations with other transport services, especially for the first- and last-mile connections.

Data analysis of road/cycleway infrastructures and parking facilities datasets was aimed at analysing the level of accessibility of the railway infrastructures/docking stations by car, enabling multimodal mobility schemes.

$$MDI = (KPT \cdot PT \text{ ca/cs}) + (KRCI \cdot RCI \text{ ca/cs}) + (KPF \cdot PF \text{ ca/cs})$$

MDI was calculated through the weighted summation of normalized density distribution values of public transports, road/cycleway infrastructure and parking facilities on catchment areas/census sections. The constant parameters KPT (corresponding to 0.4), KRI (corresponding to 0.3) and KPF (corresponding to 0.3) were weighted to accentuate the impact of public transport on MDI (\sum constant parameters = 1).

Results

The proposed methodology helped to identify a group of suitable urban railway stations (Use Case I) and bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III) belonging at least two highest or lowest quintiles among the Territorial Data Index, Sociodemographic Data Index and Mobility Data Index. For Use Case I, the list was further shortened through the analysis of several open data related to each railway infrastructure: (i) metro and urban railway lines; (ii) transport service tariff zone; (iii) underground or above-ground infrastructure.

Within the objectives of DIAMOND, the results of the proposed analysis allowed to identify an appropriate sample of urban railway infrastructures and bike-sharing docking stations to be further investigated through on-site observations focused on universal design indicators and social media data collection and survey questionnaires focused on women passengers' needs and expectations.

Use Case I – FGC

Data analysis allowed the identification of a short list of ten heterogeneous and non-adjacent railway infrastructures (Use Case I - FGC), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility⁴ (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 TDI, SDDI and MDI results for the ten selected urban railway infrastructures managed by FGC.

Use Case I – ZTM

Data analysis allowed for identification of a short list of ten heterogeneous and non-adjacent railway infrastructures (Use Case I - ZTM), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility (see Figure 7).

Figure 7 TDI, SDDI and MDI results for the ten selected urban railway infrastructures managed by ZTM.

⁴ See: Gorrini, A., Choubassi, R., Rezaallah, A., Presicce, D., Boratto, L., Laniado, D., Aragón, P. (2021). Assessing the Level of Accessibility of Railway Public Transport for Women Passengers Using Location-based Data: The Case of H2020 DIAMOND Project. In: *Smart and Sustainable Planning for Cities and Regions - Results of SSPCR 2019*, Springer (in press)

Use Case III – VELIB

Data analysis allowed for identification of a short list of twenty heterogeneous and non-adjacent bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III - VELIB), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility (see Figure 8).

Figure 8 TDI, SDDI and MDI results for the twenty selected bike-sharing docking stations managed by VELIB.

3. Analysis of Observations Data for Characterising the Selected Urban Railway Infrastructures (Use Case I) and Bike-sharing Docking Stations (Use Case III)

Objective of the analysis and alignment with DIAMOND's general methodology

According to the objectives of the DIAMOND project, onsite observations were aimed at further characterizing the urban railway infrastructures (Use Case I) and bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III) previously selected through the analysis of structured open data.

Observations were based on *ad hoc* developed checklists for the evaluation of infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics related to women's needs as users of public transport infrastructure and bike-sharing services.

Data collection campaigns were carried out over different time periods throughout the day, in order to capture any variations across commuting times. Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public and recording their findings on paper. Results were organized in a tabular structure based on a collaborative Excel worksheet. In addition, still-photo surveys of the urban railway infrastructures and docking stations were carried out.

Data and methods

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis⁵, the assessment checklists⁶ were based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for Use Case I and Use Case III. Regarding Use Case I, the checklist was composed of four main parts: (i) area surrounding the station; (ii) concourse level of the station; (iii) platform level of the station; (iv) carriage. For Use Case III the checklist was composed of five main parts: (i) accessibility and spontaneity; (ii) safety and security; (iii) social constraints; (iv) weather and topography; (v) other.

The data collected were post-processed through normalization of values (range between 0 and 1), since some of the items included in the checklists were based on Likert scales. Quintile frequency distribution of data related to the analysis of structured open data made it possible to compare observations results (focusing on CFCs, FCs and IPs) related to the railway infrastructures and docking stations characterized by high levels of accessibility for women (highest quintile) and those characterized by low levels of accessibility for women (lowest quintile).

⁵ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁶ See 'Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns'.

Results

Within the objectives of DIAMOND, the results of the proposed analysis allowed to characterize the sample of suitable urban railway infrastructures (Use Case I) and bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III), which were further investigated through social-media data collection and survey questionnaires focused on women passengers’ needs and expectations.

Use Case I – FGC

Data analysis allowed for the comparison of observation results between the urban railway infrastructures (Use Case I - FGC), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility (see Figure 9).

Figure 9 Observations results (Fairness Characteristics – Level 2) related to the railway infrastructures managed by FGC.

Use Case I – ZTM

Data analysis allowed for the comparison of observation results between the urban railway infrastructures (Use Case I - ZTM), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility (see Figure 10).

Figure 10 Observations results (Fairness Characteristics – Level 2) related to the railway infrastructures managed by ZTM.

Use Case III – VELIB

Data analysis allowed for the comparison of observation results between the bike-sharing docking stations (Use Case III - VELIB), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to their level of accessibility (see Figure 11).

Figure 11 Observations results (Fairness Characteristics – Level 2) related to the docking stations managed by VELIB.

4. Experimental tests analysis for Use case II

Introduction

A series of experiments, in a simulator laboratory setting, were executed to collect data to objectively validate the impact of autonomous vehicles driving experience (Level 4 of automation), passengers' emotional appraisal, considering gender and other relevant intersectional variables in transport.

A series of autonomous driving scenarios were designed considering different environmental, traffic and driving conditions (i.e. independent variables) to elicit emotional reactions from participants. In the experiment session two types of data were gathered:

1. Passenger physiological signals to obtain emotional indicators of different driving situations.
2. Subjective participant assessment after the simulated autonomous driving experience by means of UESI questionnaire.

This document includes the description of the process performed for emotional indicators calculation, physiological signals and the validation of the passenger emotional state estimation obtained from physiological signals.

Additionally, the result of the analysis of UESI questionnaires from the experimental session is included in this document, including the significance tests for exploring differences related to gender aspects.

Experimental design

The sample included a total of 40 participants, drivers between 25-55 years old, divided in two experimental factors. This sample size is statistically representative enough when addressing two characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual (gender, and travelling with or without dependent people) as was calculated in the D2.1, section 4.2.2.1.

To explore the influence of gender, according to bibliographic review, it has been considered necessary to control the family composition in the experimental design. Trip chaining is usually related to care mobility that has a high gender bias (Perez, 2019). An example of care mobility would be a parent dropping children to school. The presence of children in families, therefore, represents a relevant factor and ensures the participation of "trip-chainers" in the study.

Thus, main factors of the experimental design were:

- Gender, considering two main levels: women and men.

- With and Without children under 12 years old⁷, family composition involving care mobility duties.

The experimental design was divided equally in terms of these two main factors, defining four groups of participants:

- G1: 10 women with children under 12 years
- G2: 10 women without children under 12 years
- G3: 10 men with children under 12 years
- G4: 10 men without children under 12 years old.

Additionally, sample respondents' age was equally distributed among groups to avoid biases in between-subjects results.

There are also two more relevant aspects considered in the selection of the participants for the experimental design: whether participants enjoy driving and participants which have affinity with the technology. These parameters were not strictly considered for the inclusion but sample selection pursued a balance between the groups with respect to these aspects. In the selected sample, for the questions related to “driving enjoyment” and “interest in technology” there are not significant differences among genders or groups.

Figure 12: Distribution of age in each group

⁷ In Spain, 12 years old, represents the end of primary school, and contrary to other countries, because of extended cultural issues, is usually the end age for kids walking accompanied by an adult to school.

Emotional indicators calculation and validation

Introduction

The main goals of Use Case II experiments were the identification of gender-driven stressors related to autonomous driving emotional experience and obtaining emotional indicators from the physiological signal of the passenger. These emotional indicators were defined as variables of Use Case II fairness characteristic level 3.

The emotional indicators aim to estimate the passenger's state following a dimensional approach, based on the parameter's arousal (the level of intensity) and valence (negativity, neutrality or positivity) obtained from the physiological signals of the passenger measured on board while travelling in a dynamic simulator of an L4 autonomous car.

Figure 13: IBV autonomous car dynamic simulator

With the hypothesis that scenario design would elicit differences in emotional state and considering the potential influence of gender on the emotional state six autonomous driving scenarios were designed considering different environmental, traffic and driving conditions:

- Trust in autonomous driving in different weather conditions (Trust)
- Sportive driving mode in time constrain scenario (Sport)
- Comfort driving mode in time constrain scenario (Comfort)
- Driving and simultaneously doing an activity (Simultaneity)
- AV Failure while driving (Breakdown)
- Dangerous driving event (I don't want to die, IDWTD)

From these scenarios the physiological indicators were calculated for DIAMOND UC II FC database:

- Trust_neutral: Arousal and valence values during AV driving in neutral condition
- Trust_bad weather: Arousal and valence values during AV driving in unfavorable weather conditions.

- Trust_failure: Arousal and valence values when the AV car indicates a failure and must stop.
- Trust_failur_not_solved: Arousal and valence values when the AV car cannot solve the failure (indicates manual driving).
- Trust_Safety: Arousal and valence values when an event affects personal safety perception.
- Sim_calm: Arousal and valence values during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment (and the 2nd time).
- Sim_enriched: Arousal and valence values during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in enriched external environment. (and the 1st time).
- Time_OK: Arousal and valence values when reaches destination on time.
- Time_late: Arousal and valence values when reaches destination out of time.
- Comfort: Arousal and valence values when driving in comfort driving mode.
- Sport: Arousal and valence values when driving in sport driving mode.

Figure 14 shows the steps followed for the calculation of the emotional indicators, from signal acquisition to emotional indicators data base.

Figure 14: Flow chart for the calculation of emotional indicators

Acquisition and signal processing

Equipment for physiological signal acquisition

The physiological signals are obtained by measuring them with Biosignal Plux®,⁸. It is an advanced wireless toolkit designed for researchers to collect and analyse reliable, high definition, biosignal data.

A number of sensors, Figure 15, for the recording of the following signals have been included in the protocols:

- ECG sensor for obtaining the electrocardiogram related parameters such as heart rate (HR) and the heart rate variability (HRV) (Nardelli et al, 2015).

⁸ <https://plux.info/12-biosignalsplux>

- A skin conductance sensor to record the Electro Dermal Activity (EDA) (Laparra-Hernández et al. 2009; Zhou et al. 2012).
- Two facial Electro Myography sensors (EMG) recording the muscle activity of zygomaticus major and corrugator supercilia (Laparra-Hernández et al. 2009)

Figure 15: Biosignal Plux® sensors (left) facial EMG (center) ECG (right) EDA

Biosignal Plux® records the participants physiological signals continuously during the experiments sampled at 1kHz. The physiological signals were synchronized with IBV's driving simulator in order to match the driving contexts (scenario, driving events...) to the participants' state.

Signal processing and parameter calculation

The algorithms, aiming to extract the key parameters of the physiological signal, are built in Python Programming Language (high-level, general-purpose programming language) and divided in three main stages: reading and managing signals from the equipment, fragmenting the signal and processing signals for the extraction of specific parameters.

The exportation of the signals from the Biosignal Plux® equipment is a .txt file that contains a header and the columns corresponding to the different channels recorded. All channels are collected in specific units that need to be transformed with a specific transfer function provided by Plux to convert to units of interest, like microSiemens (in the case of the GSR), or volts (in the case of the ECG).

In each scenario, main relevant events (another car overtaking, rain begins, car braking...) are characterized and identified. For every participant, data from the sensors is fragmented (Figure 16) to locate the relevant events in the scenarios using synchronization with IBV driving simulator and scenarios.

Figure 16. Scheme of fragments extracted from the signal.

The “fragments” (pink bands in Figure 16) are the ones around a punctual relevant event. This fragmentation step is common to all signals compiled from the equipment with the objective of calculating the physiological parameters in fragments associated with relevant events.

For the relevant fragment of the signals, the algorithms calculate all the relevant parameters. Table 4 shows the list of the parameters extracted for each physiological signal.

Table 4: Physiological parameters extracted from ECG, EDA and EMG signals

Signal type	Type	Parameters
ECG	General	Average, Standard Deviation, 1st Difference, 1st Difference normalized, 2nd Difference, 2nd Difference normalized, Maximum, Minimum, Ratio, RootMeanSquare
ECG	InterBeat Interval (nn)	Average, Standard Deviation, RootMeanSquare, Frames over 50ms, Frames over 20ms, %Frames over 50ms, %Frames over 20ms
ECG	Heart Rate Variability	VLF (very low frequency band) power, VLF average, LF (low frequency band) power, LF average, HF (high frequency band) power, HF average, VLF power (Frequency Domain (FD)), VLF average (FD), LF power (FD), LF average (FD), HF power (FD), HF average (FD)
EDA	GSR tonic	Average, Standard Deviation, Maximum, Minimum, Ratio, RootMeanSquare, First Derivative, Second Derivative, Negative Slope,
EDA	GSR phasic	Average, Standard Deviation, Maximum, Minimum, Ratio, RootMeanSquare, First Derivative, Second Derivative, Negative Slope,
EMG	Corrugator	Average, Standard Deviation, 1st Difference, 1st Difference normalized, 2nd Difference, 2nd Difference normalized, Maximum, Minimum, Ratio, RootMeanSquare
EMG	EMG zygomatic	Average, Standard Deviation, 1st Difference, 1st Difference normalized, 2nd Difference, 2nd Difference normalized, Maximum, Minimum, Ratio, RootMeanSquare

Arousal and Valence calculation

With these sensors and signals it is possible to have a good representation of the emotional state of the participants. However, as each physiological signal has its own representation, all of them require to be set in the same proper scale. For this purpose, a number of tools have been used such as Likert Scales (Lang, Bradley, and Cuthbert 1999), the Self-Assessment Manikin rating scale (SAM) and others (Geethanjali et al. 2017).

Therefore, the goal is to have a representation of the emotional state of the participant in the domains of valence and arousal in relevant events of driving scenarios from the recordings of the physiological signals.

For this purpose, we have calculated arousal and valence by two different methods to select the most representative of participant emotional state.

- **Direct calculation methods.** In this method arousal and valence are calculated with validated dependencies in the bibliography. Arousal scale is calculated from ECG and EDA parameters and valence scale from EMG parameters.
- **Regressors models.** In this case, the aim is having a continuous representation of the emotional state of the participant (in the domains of valence and arousal) from the recordings of the physiological signals, and these signals will be calibrated among participants' self-reported emotional status at some specific times. In our case, the self-assessment of the emotion will be performed using SAM.

Direct calculation with parameters

Estimation of Arousal (Test of relation HRV – GSR)

One of the dependencies widely validated in the bibliography is the relation between the phasic component of the Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) with the arousal. The proven dependency states that with higher arousal, the phasic GSR increases. On the other hand, the relation between the Heart Rate Variability (HRV) of the Low Frequency Band (0.04 – 0.15 Hz), is the opposite, for the HRV tends to decrease with an increase of arousal.

Among all the parameters obtained through our signal processing algorithms, the relevant ones for the arousal calculation consist of: the amplitude of the low frequency band of the HRV (obtained from ECG measurement) and the amplitude of the phasic band of the GSR.

To verify the approach, in the representation of both variables (the average of the GSR phasic component on the y axis, and the average of the low frequency band of HRV on the x axis) the tendency of the data must be negative. Reviewing the tendency of the experimental data, it could be appreciated that the trend is negative.

Once the approach was validated as viable, for each of the fragments of interest, the data are standardized:

$$ST_{HRV}(fragment) = \frac{HRV(fragment) - mean(HRV)}{STD(HRV)}$$

$$ST_{GSR}(fragment) = \frac{GSR - mean(GSR)}{STD(GSR)}$$

From this output, the value of Arousal is calculated by:

$$Arousal(fragment) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} ST_{GSR}(fragment) - ST_{HRVi}(fragment)$$

As a normal distribution, all the values obtained are among +3 and -3. As the scale of interest in this case are values of Arousal among 0 and 9, a transformation of scale is performed following a sigmoid of this type:

$$ScaledArousal = \frac{9}{1 + e^{-1.5 * Arousal}}$$

Values out of the scale were revised and outliers, due to a signal acquisition problem, were discarded. Other values out of scale were assigned to nearest extreme values of the scales. This way a distribution of values rescaled from 0 to 9 is obtained and used to characterize each of the fragments of interest.

Estimation of Valence (Test of activation of Zygomatic and Corrugator)

The zygomatic activation is mainly related to a positive valence, and the corrugator to a negative valence. For the valence calculation, one of the key parameters from the EMG was extracted: the normalized average value of muscle activation. In this case, it is relevant to consider the level of the activation in the fragment of interest, as well as a neutral fragment previous to them.

For each of the fragments of interest, the data are standardized:

$$ST_{ZYGO}(fragment) = \frac{ZYGO(fragment) - mean(ZYGO)}{STD(ZYGO)}$$

$$ST_{ZYGO}(pre\ fragment) = \frac{ZYGO(pre\ fragment) - mean(ZYGO)}{STD(ZYGO)}$$

$$ST_{CORRU}(fragment) = \frac{CORRU(fragment) - mean(CORRU)}{STD(CORRU)}$$

$$ST_{CORRU}(pre\ fragment) = \frac{CORRU(pre\ fragment) - mean(CORRU)}{STD(CORRU)}$$

In order to calculate the values of valence following the criteria set out in Table 5.

Table 5: Criteria to valence value calculation

Criteria	Meaning
If (Value of Zygomatic in Fragment) – (Value of Zygomatic in Neutral) is greater than 0	There is a positive increase in valence
If (Value of Corrugator in Fragment) – (Value of Corrugator in Neutral) is greater than 0	There is a negative increase in valence

Valence is calculated through this algorithm:

```

if (zygo_fragment - zygo_neutral > 0):
    ValenciaPositiva = zygo_fragment - zygo_neutral
if (corru_fragment - corru_neutral > 0):
    ValenciaNegativa = corru_fragment - corru_neutral
if (zygo_fragment - zygo_neutral < 0):
    ValenciaNegativa = - zygo_fragment + zygo_neutral
if (corru_fragment - corru_neutral < 0):
    ValenciaPositiva = - corru_fragment + corru_neutral
if (ValenciaPositiva > ValenciaNegativa):
    Valencia = ValenciaPositiva
else:
    Valencia = - ValenciaNegativa
    
```

As in the case of arousal, all the values obtained are among +3 and -3. As the scale of interest in this case are values of Valence among 0 and 9, a transformation of scale is performed following a sigmoid of this type:

$$ScaledValence = \frac{9}{1 + e^{-1.5 \cdot Valence}}$$

For the outlier value's signals, the procedure was similar as in arousal calculation, thus, a distribution of values rescaled from 0 to 9 is obtained and characterize valence for each of the fragments of interest.

Figure 17 represents for a participant the values of arousal and valence in the main events of all scenarios.

Figure 17: Arousal and Valence calculated for relevant events in the six scenarios for a participant

Regressors model's viability study

In this case, the continuous representation of the emotional state of the participant (in the domains of valence and arousal) is obtained from the recordings of the physiological signals, and these signals will be calibrated against a participants self-reported emotional status at some specific times.

Several models were implemented to obtain the relationship between the physiological parameters with the emotional state, subjectively reported by the participants. It means the generated model should, from the physiological signals (through the parameters that characterize them) estimate the emotional state of the passenger by calculating the values of valence and arousal.

For this purpose, firstly a matrix is generated with the values of each parameter (in columns, corresponding to the 46 extracted parameters) of the physiological signals measured in each fragment of interest during each of the trips for each of the users. The next step consists in adding two columns with the subjective values of valence and arousal stated by the subjects for each of the situations of the driving simulator in the next tests using a SAM (self-assessment-manikin) (Figure 18).

Figure 18 Scheme of the data that build the model.

With this dataset the goal was to test every type of regressor models trained with the DIAMOND dataset, study the behavior and evaluate the adequacy of calculating arousal and valence with one of the regressor models.

A comparison of several regression models has been performed using the scikit-learn library in Python. The following models have been tested and Table I shows the accuracy (%) of each of them:

- Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB) model: they are a family of simple "probabilistic classifiers" based on applying Bayes' theorem with strong (naïve) independence assumptions between the features. They are among the simplest Bayesian network models, but coupled with kernel density estimation, they can achieve higher accuracy levels.
- Linear Support Vector Regressor (LSVR): Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a very popular Machine Learning algorithm which is similar to Linear Regression in that the equation of the hyperplane is a line function which is $y = wx + b$
- Support Vector Regressor (SVR): In this case the kernel of the algorithm changes and is not linear, but quadratic.
- Nu Support Vector Regressor (NuSVR): This model is similar to the last two but the function has a parameter to control the number of support vectors.

- Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) Neural Network (NN): A MLP consists of at least three layers of nodes: an input layer, a hidden layer and an output layer. Except for the input nodes, each node is a neuron that uses a nonlinear activation function. MLP utilizes a supervised learning technique called backpropagation for training. It can distinguish data that is not linearly separable.
- Partial Least Square Regression (PLS): it is a statistical method that bears some relation to principal components regression; instead of finding hyperplanes of maximum variance between the response and independent variables, it finds a linear regression model by projecting the predicted variables and the observable variables to a new space.

Table 6: Models' performances in percentage of correct classification of the validation dataset

Model	GNB	LSVR	SVR	NuSVR	NN	PLS
Arousal	18.25	2	3	0.5	Convergence issues	Convergence issues
Valence	14	1.4	2	0.2	Convergence issues	Convergence issues

The results obtained by regressors using the DIAMOND database (physiological signals and subjective assessment acquired in the experimentation) were, in general, poor. The best performance has been obtained with the Gaussian Naïve Bayes model, as it minimizes the error obtained in the classification of each register. The Support Vector Regression is not achieving even a minimum performance, and for the Neural Network and a Partial Least Square Regression we have obtained convergence errors in the performance of the classification, that is why the values are not shown in Table I.

This poor performance is mainly due to the limited number of samples. Other reasons for explaining this include the fact that the questionnaires are applied to passengers after each scenario, and therefore the participants make the self-assessment by comparison between the events after having felt all the experiences, while the physiological measurements are recorded in real time. Additionally, in the self-assessment participants assess one specific event and the physiological measurements are the results of the influence of all contextual factors around participants during simulated driving; also the difficulty of participants to assess the emotion in a quantitative way should be considered.

The result of the application of the models did not improve the arousal and valence calculated compared with direct calculation methods, thus, the method was discarded to obtain a classification tree model (Fuzzy Tree model, D2.1 Section 4.2.2.1) capable to predict emotional indicators when persons face different scenarios. However, the Arousal and Valence variables obtained through self-assessment (SAM) were considered to study differences between genders and travelling with dependents (next sections).

Validation of the emotional passenger state calculation

In each scenario, arousal and valence have been calculated from physiological signals following the direct method calculation in each relevant event.

Thus, for each relevant event, we obtained four variables related to the passenger's emotional state:

- Arousal elicited measured by physiological signals (Arousal_Fisio)
- Arousal self-assessed by participants using the SAM questionnaire (Arousal_SAM).
- Valence elicited measured by physiological signals (Valence_Fisio)
- Valence self-assessed by participants using the SAM questionnaire (Valence_SAM).

The experimental design was based on the hypothesis that scenario design would elicit differences in emotional state. Additionally, scenarios were designed considering the potential influence of gender in the emotional state elicited.

To validate this hypothesis, we have analyzed the influence of scenarios and their main events on the participants' emotional state, considering gender as a factor, finding differences in the emotion elicited.

Analysis of emotions elicited in each scenario

The following factors have been considered as the most relevant to be tested to analyse the scenario influence in passenger emotional state:

- SCENARIO: Six levels according to the driving scenario (Breakdown, Comfort, IDWTD, Simultaneous, Sport, Trust).
- GENDER: two levels for men and women.
- Arrival on time (OK): If the participant is arriving late or on time to destination during this driving experience (this factor was randomized in experimental design).

For this purpose, a model has been fitted in which the two components of emotions analysed (Arousal and Valence) can depend on the gender of the passenger, the scenario, the arrival on time (OK) and the interaction between Gender and Scenario. An ANOVA test has been performed for each of the four variables analysed, Arousal_Fisio, Arousal_SAM, Valence_Fisio and Valence_SAM.

Both tools (physiological signals and self-assessment) have been able to find differences between scenarios (

Table 7).

Table 7 Results of the ANOVA for the Arousal and Valence. Results are for the estimated emotions with physiological signals and self-perceived emotions assessed with the SAM tool.

	Gender	Scenario	OK	Gender:Scenario
Arousal_Fisio	0.396	0.000	0.120	0.010
Arousal_SAM	0.069	0.000	0.021	0.075
Valence_Fisio	0.197	0.019	0.813	0.369
Valence_SAM	0.003	0.000	0.000	0.027

As it can be seen, different scenarios are eliciting different emotions for all variables. Some differences have found in the emotions declared in the SAM when the participant arrived on time (OK factor) or not, but these differences haven't been found in the physiological signals. Some differences have been found also related to Gender.

[Analysis of the arousal](#)

The arousal elicited in each scenario depends on the interaction of Scenario and the Gender of the driver (

Table 7 factor Gender:Scenario).

In the case of men, Comfort scenario was the scenario eliciting less arousal, and Simultaneity the highest. In both scenarios, we found differences between men and women, Comfort scenario elicited more arousal in women than men and Simultaneity scenario elicited more arousal in men than women (Figure 19). In Simultaneity scenario the participant performed a cognitive task; cognitive effort usually increases the arousal levels.

In the case of men, the significant differences indicate the classification of scenarios (Figure 19); from lower to higher arousal, we find:

1. Comfort.
2. Trust.
3. Break down and I don't want to die.
4. Sport driving and simultaneity task.

In the case of women, there are two groups of scenarios with significant differences (Figure 19):

1. Breakdown, Comfort and Trust with lower arousal.
2. Sport driving, I don't want to die and simultaneity task with higher arousal.

Figure 19 Relationship of arousal and scenarios measured with physiological signals.

In general, Comfort, Breakdown, and Trust scenarios elicit less arousal than I don't want to die, Simultaneity task and Sport driving scenarios.

With respect to the arousal self-assessed by the participants significant differences indicate three levels, from lower to higher arousal:

1. Comfort
2. Trust, Break down, I don't want to die and simultaneous task.
3. Sport driving.

Besides, when the trip shown in the scenario was concluded on time, the participant declared lower levels of arousal.

Figure 20 Arousal as self-perceived by passenger in (a) scenarios (b) when on-time vs out-of-time

Comfort scenario is the scenario with the lowest level of arousal declared, and sport driving the highest, while the others remain in the middle (Figure 20.a). Besides, passenger declared lower levels of arousals when the trip arrived on Time (Figure 20.b).

[Analysis with Valence](#)

Valence elicited in each scenario depends on the scenario while the self-assessment of valence depends on gender, scenario and arriving on time (

Table 7).

In the elicited valence measured with physiological signals, differences have been found between the breakdown scenario (less positive Valence) and Simultaneous task and Sport with more positive Valence (Figure 21).

Figure 21 Marginal means for valence estimated using physiological variables.

Regarding Valence values self-declared by the participants, there are differences in gender in Simultaneous task, sport driving and trust (Figure 22).

Figure 22 Marginal means of valence per each scenario as self-perceived by the passengers.

In general, Women declare more positive valence values than men. In particular, Sport, Simultaneity and Trust scenarios have significant difference by gender.

For men, only Sport differs from the other scenarios being perceived as less positive. For women, Breakdown, Comfort and Sport have less positive valence values than I don't want to die (IDWD) and Simultaneous tasks.

Emotional content associated with events in each scenario

To validate the influence of the specific relevant events in the participant emotional state, the same analysis as in the previous point was performed for each of the relevant events of the different scenarios.

In this case, a model has been fitted in which the two components of emotions analysed (Arousal and Valence) can depend on the event, the gender and the interaction of both factors.

Table 8 Results of the Anova for the emotional content of each event.

	Gender	Events	Events:Gender
Arousal_Fisio	0.395	0.000	0.752
Arousal_SAM	0.052	0.000	0.004
Valence_Fisio	0.201	0.187	0.347

Valence_SAM **0.001** **0.000** *0.095*

There are differences in events for Arousal in both methods (the one estimated with physiological signals and the one self-assessed with SAM). There are also differences in self-assessed arousal between genders. For the Valence values, the differences by gender and event have been only found in the self-assessment tool (Table 8).

Analysis of arousal

Differences have been observed in Arousal elicited per each event (Table 8). In the case of self-assessed Arousal, we have also found differences by gender (Table 8).

The lower levels of arousal are associated with neutral driving (cloudy event) and for events while driving slowly (Figure 23), while the events occurring in sportive driving are characterized by much higher arousal. The other peak of arousal is at the beginning of the scenario and at the end of the jam (Figure 23).

Figure 23 Arousal elicited in each event according to the physiological signals. It can be noted that the events in slow driving elicited much less arousal than the events in sport driving.

In self-assessed arousal, there are differences per gender in certain scenarios (Figure 24). Despite there being differences associated with gender in some events, they follow the same trend and, also, with the physiological signals in most events, as it can be seen in the chart.

Figure 24 Arousal self-assessed by the participants in each event.

Analysis of Valence

The most negative valence elicited to the participants occurred in the overtaking and the sportive driving, both in sport scenario, while the most positive values of valence elicited corresponded to slow events (Figure 25).

Figure 25 Valence elicited to passengers estimated from physiological signals.

The self-assessed valence has the highest peak at Failure not solved and the lowest values at Driving closer to other cars and Sportive Swerve (Figure 26). The differences between slow and sport events are not as clear as in self-assessed valence as they are in valence measured with physiological signals.

Figure 26 Valence as self-perceived by passengers. (left) events (right) gender

Regarding gender, women have declared more positive values of Valence than men.

Relationship between emotions estimated with physiological signals and emotions declared by self-assessment.

A mixed model was fitted considering participants as random factor. A significant relationship was found between Arousal measured with physiological signals and arousal self-assessed by participants (p -value=0.033), while no significant relationship was found for valence (p -value=0.463). Some reasons for explaining this fact are that the self-assessment of emotions is difficult to participants, it is made at the end of each scenario and not in real time as physiological measures. Additionally, self-assessment focuses on one specific event and the physiological state is the result of all contextual factors around the participant. The differences between the self-assessment method and physiological estimation of emotions were also a reason for the poor performance regressor models.

Emotional indicators

After the validation, the emotional indicators associated with Fairness Characteristics of level 3 were calculated. These indicators are the arousal and valence values of single events in one particular scenario, or the average from events representative of a driving situation. Table 9 describes the calculation of each indicator.

Table 9: Description and calculation of emotional indicators

Indicator	Description	Calculation
Trust_neutral	Arousal and valence values during AV driving in neutral condition	Scenario Breakdown. Event previous to the failure when the driving is neutral.
Trust_badweather:	Arousal and valence values during AV driving in unfavorable weather conditions.	Scenario Trust. Event when the AV is driving with intense rain.
Trust_failure:	Arousal and valence values when the AV car indicates a failure and must to stop.	Scenario Breakdown. Event when the AV informs the passenger of a failure and indicates they will stop (Safe Stop with Minimal Risk Manoeuvre)
Trust_failure_not_solved.	Arousal and valence values when the AV car cannot solve the failure (indicates manual driving).	Scenario Breakdown. Event in Safe Stop when the AV informs the passenger that the failure cannot be solved and they must continue the trip with manual driving.
Trust_Safety.	Arousal and valence values when an event affects personal safety perception.	Scenario: I don't want to die, (IDWD). Event when another car skips a stop and the AVs brakes suddenly.
Sim_enriched	Arousal and valence values during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in enriched external environment (and the 1st time).	Scenario Simultaneity. Event when AV is driving while the participant must perform simultaneous tasks with an electronic device for the first time during a traffic jam (enriched external environment).
Sim_calm.	Arousal and valence values during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment (and the 2nd time).	Scenario Simultaneity. Event when AV is driving while the participant must perform simultaneous tasks with an electronic device for the second time and traffic is fluid (comfortable external environment)
Time_OK.	Arousal and valence values when reaching destination on time.	Scenarios: Simultaneity, Sport and Comfort. Average of the arrival events from this scenario if the participant reaches destination on time.
Time_late.	Arousal and valence values when reaching destination out of time.	Scenarios: Simultaneity, Sport and Comfort. Average of the arrival events from this scenario if the participant reaches destination on time.
Comfort.	Arousal and valence values when driving in comfort driving mode.	Scenario: Comfort. Average of the event representative of comfort driving (Slow driving, Slow overtaking, Slow breaking)
Sport.	Arousal and valence values when driving in sport driving mode.	Scenario: Sport. Average of the event representative of sport/aggressive driving (Overtaking, Closer, Sportive overtaking, Sportive Swerve)

The values of emotional indications were calculated for every participant in the experimentation to complete the Fairness Characteristic Level 3 for UC II.

Conclusions

Physiological signals (ECG, EDA and EMG) gathered from participants were processed and the main physiological parameters were calculated for the relevant events of each scenario. Arousal and valence for each relevant event were calculated by direct methods. Arousal was calculated from ECG and EDA signals and Valence from EMG signals.

The hypothesis in experimental design was that scenario design would elicit differences in emotional state. To validate this hypothesis, differences have been found in the emotions elicited for the scenarios and the events.

Once the physiological measures were validated, the values of emotional indications were calculated for every participant in the experiment to complete the Fairness Characteristic Level 3 for UC II.

The higher values of arousal measured are associated with situations of driving faster while slow driving is associated with lower levels of arousal, as can be expected. Regarding gender, there are differences between genders in two scenarios. In the case of the Comfort scenario, men elicited less arousal than women, being for men the scenario with lowest arousal. In the case of Simultaneous task scenario women elicited less arousal than men, being for men the scenario with highest arousal.

For arousal, the values measured and self-assessed by the participants are related to each other, while this does not happen with valence.

The most negative valence elicited to the participants occurred during overtakings and the sportive driving, while the more positive values of valence elicited corresponded to slow events.

Scenarios with higher impact in emotional state measured with physiological variables are, on one hand, the scenarios related with a smooth and aggressive driving mode (sport and comfort scenario) and, on the other hand, related to performing a simultaneous task (simultaneity scenario). These scenarios are, additionally, the scenarios where gender differences have a higher impact.

With respect to gender, men have higher differences in the physiological activation (arousal) associated with scenario design than women, thus, men are more sensitive to driving context variables.

Due to driving mode, there are differences in physiological and self-assessed arousal level in both genders, being the smooth driving mode more relaxed than the aggressive driving mode. However, in the physiological arousal this difference is higher for men than for women and the subjective assessment also differs.

Men, in the comfort scenario with a smoother driving mode, are significantly less activated (less arousal) than in the rest of scenarios and, also compared with women. Thus, we find a clear

“relaxing” effect of this scenario for men, while we do not find it for women, for whom the comfort scenario has the same arousal level as the other scenarios.

The sport scenario for men is the most negative (lowest self-declared valence), significantly compared with the rest of scenarios. For men, sport is the second scenario with highest arousal level. For women, the arousal level in the sport scenario is similar to men and significantly higher than in the comfort scenario, however, women do not consider this scenario as negative as men do. For women, comfort and sport scenarios have the same level of self-declared valence.

Therefore, the driving mode impacts the physiological emotional state of both genders in an expected way, however, in men this impact is higher, notably the smooth driving mode has a relaxing effect, and they assess negatively the sport driving mode.

In the simultaneity scenario, where the participant has to perform a simultaneous task, men present the highest activation level compared to the other scenarios and higher than women. This fact could be attributed to a higher cognitive effort of men while performing a simultaneous task. Additionally, women assess more positively this scenario than men do and exhibit a lower activation level.

Descriptive analysis of UESI surveys in UC II experiments.

Introduction

UESI questionnaires were focused on the satisfaction of the end-users related to autonomous vehicles. In the case of UESI questionnaires associated with UC II experiments, the outline was composed by two main parts. The first part is focused on profiling the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users, and was administrated before the execution of the experiments. The second part was focused on evaluating users' satisfaction regarding the autonomous driving performance experienced through the simulation.

The descriptive analysis has been focused on the following factors according to experimental design:

- Gender: Two level factor to explore differences between women and men scores. (**Women/Men**)
- With/without children: Two level factor to explore differences between participants with and without children under 12 years old, involving care mobility duties. (**With children/Without children**)
- Group. Exploring the differences between the four groups obtained combining the two previous factors.
 - G1: 10 women with children under 12 years (**W with child**)
 - G2: 10 women without children under 12 years (**W without child**)
 - G3: 10 men with children under 12 years (**M with child**)
 - G4: 10 men without children under 12 years old. (**M without child**)

The differences were explored by non-parametric significance tests, Kruskal-Wallis and χ^2 test, depending on whether the answer is an ordinal or nominal variable.

The scales used in UESI for ordinal variables are:

- Agreement with the statement (From 1- Strongly disagree to 7- Strongly agree),
- Importance (From 1- Not important at all to 7- Very important),
- Frequency (different frequency scales ordered from lower to higher frequency).

For the other questions, participants must select options from a list (nominal variables).

Kruskal-Wallis is a non-parametric method for testing whether samples originate from the same distribution. It is used for comparing two or more independent samples of equal or different size. The parametric equivalent of the Kruskal–Wallis test is the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). This test has been applied to explore differences in the ordinal variables.

As the sample is limited to 40 participants and the variables are ordinal (scales from 1 to 7) this method is more robust in case of a not normal distribution. Since it is a nonparametric method, the Kruskal–Wallis test does not assume a normal distribution of the residuals, unlike the analogous one-way analysis of variance.

In a few cases where the explored variable is nominal, the differences have been analyzed by a χ^2 test, to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between the expected frequencies and the observed frequencies in one or more categories of a contingency table.

Additionally, for each item of the UESI questionnaire, the mean score and the scores for each group were calculated and represented.

The result of this descriptive analysis is presented in the following sections grouping the questions from the UESI questionnaire in main categories according to their nature.

Results

Displacements profile

Trip chaining and the purpose of the main displacements has been explored.

To the question: “When I go to my work, or in my daily displacements, I make intermediate stops (leaving recycled rubbish in the bin, leave the kids in school, visit a family relative who requires specific care, do shopping...)”, the frequency of trip chaining is significantly higher for women than for men ($p < 0,05$) of the sample.

7 Every day 6 More than three times a week 5 At least once a week 4 Twice/three times a month 3 once a month 2 Almost never 1 Never
 Figure 27: Number of participants according with trip chaining frequency per group (10 participant per group)

In the experimental sample, 50% of women trip chain at least once a week, however, only 25% of men do. As stated by bibliographic research, trip chaining has a gender bias.

However, the factor with/without children is not significant in trip chaining frequency. As it is observed, the 60% of the group of men with children declared they almost never trip chain.

Regarding frequency of displacements per purpose, there are differences due to factor with/without children but not to factor gender.

In general, the most frequent displacement is to the purpose “going to workplace/study” (Figure 28).

Figure 28: Sample and group mean frequency per purpose implying displacements

Factor with/without children is significant in two purposes. The frequency of “own leisure activities” is higher for participants without children ($p < 0.05$) and “accompanying my family to their leisure activities” is higher for participant with children ($p < 0.05$).

Acceptance, potential use and willingness to buy an AV

The Acceptance of autonomous vehicles is similar for all groups (Figure 29), the score of agreement with the statement “I consider the use of AVs acceptable” is between 5 and 6 in agreement scale (1-strongly disagree 7- strongly agree) for the four groups.

Figure 29: Agreement scores for acceptance, willingness to use, willingness to buy.

The willingness to be a user has a similar score to acceptance, slightly lower for all categories of users.

The willingness to buy an AV was assessed before and after the experiment, and both obtain a lower score than Acceptance for all groups.

In this case, the willingness to buy an AV before the experiment is different for men and women. Women have a lower score than men ($p < 0.05$). Women express disagreement with the statement “I would like to buy an AV...” and men have a neutral score. After the experiment, factor gender is not significant anymore but factor with/without children become significant. Participants with children score higher this item than those without children ($p < 0.05$). This change is mainly due to the group of women with children: before the experiment, they expressed disagreement with this statement, however, after the experience in the simulator they are the group with the highest agreement with the statement.

Safety and security. Accident rate and human error

The main statements related with safety are “AVs will reduce the accident rate” and “AVs are safer than conventional cars under any conditions”.

Figure 30: Agreement scores for accident rate and human error statements.

For “AVs will reduce the accident rate” the agreement is similar among all groups, with a mean of 5.7 in the agreement scale. However, in the statement “AVs are safer than conventional cars under any conditions”, the agreement is lower and there exist differences by gender ($p < 0,05$). Women score lower than men, and they slightly disagree with this statement.

Safety and security. Training and infrastructure

The mean score in “Training in AV driving will be easier than for conventional cars” is 4.6, close to neutrality (4) and there are no significant differences among groups.

The statements related to infrastructure management do not show differences for any factor. Statement “I would be comfortable allowing my vehicle to transmit and share data to organizations that manage/maintain the roadway” has a mean score of 5.3 and “AVs will traffic efficiency and management” has a mean score of 5.8.

Figure 31: Agreement scores training and infrastructure management statements.

Comfort. Trust

The main statements related to trust are represented in Figure 32.

Figure 32: Agreement scores for trust related statements.

For the statement “I am suspicious of new technologies...” there are no differences among groups and all score around 3, expressing slight disagreement.

Trust in the automotive industry is high for all groups and notably high for men without children ($p < 0.05$ factor group), but there are not significant differences by gender or by the with/without children factor.

All groups agree with the statement “I believe that I can depend and rely on AVs for my displacements” with a mean score of 5.3 and there are no significant differences due to the factors.

COMFORT. Simultaneity

There are no differences among groups in the scores related to the perception of the capability to perform simultaneous tasks in a AV.

Figure 33: Agreement scores with statements related with capability to perform simultaneous task in an AV.

However, there are differences in the interest of the activity to perform during the trip. Women show higher interest than men in working during displacements in AVs using an electronic device and managing and organizing personal data ($p < 0,05$). Participants with children show more interest in caring for other passengers ($p < 0,05$) than participants without children.

Figure 34: Interest scores for simultaneous activities.

Both for women and men, the activity they are more interested is to use an electronic device (mobile, laptop, tablet), but for women this interest is significantly higher. Activities “to chat and interact” and “to relax/sleep” are also common to all groups.

Women show, in general, higher interest in performing simultaneous activities than men, and the group of women with children under 12 is more interested in performing different activities.

Table 10: Mean interest score of groups in simultaneous activities

Women with children <12	Interest	Women without children <12	Interest
19. To use an electronic device	6,2	19. To use an electronic device	6,5
21. To eat.	5,7	18. To manage and organise personal data	5,8
23. To care for other passengers	5,4	22. To chat and interact with passengers	5,6
22. To chat and interact with passengers	5,4	20. To work in the car during my displacements	5,3
18. To manage and organise personal data	5,4	17. To relax/sleep/take a nap	4,8
17. To relax/sleep/take a nap	4,7	21. To eat.	4,7
20. To work	4,5		
26. Final dressing and grooming	4,4		
Men with children <12	Interest	Men without children <12	Interest
19. To use an electronic device	5,5	19. To use an electronic device (mobile, laptop, tablet)	5,7
22. To chat and interact with passengers	4,9	21. To eat.	5,7
23. To care for other passengers	4,6	22. To chat and interact without specific objective	5,1
17. To relax/sleep/take a nap	4,3	18. To manage and organise personal data	4,6
		17. To relax/sleep/take a nap	4,1

Women are more interested than men in working during displacements (score < 4) and “to manage and organize personal data”

For men and women with children the interest “to care other passengers” is higher than for people who do not have children.

MOBILITY. Traffic efficiency, travel time and congestion

As shown in Figure 35, participants agree on the improvement of traffic efficiency, travel time and parking with AVs. Agreement scores are between 5,5 and 6.

Figure 35: Agreement scores for traffic, travel time and parking related statements.

There are not significant differences according to any factor (gender or with/without children) in these statements.

MOBILITY. Accessibility and priorities

In the assessment of AVs' accessibility improvement, "I think AVs will facilitate the mobility of people who are not able to drive or to take a conventional car ..." the mean score is high (6.2) without differences among the observed groups.

Additionally, UESI questionnaires gather the three main priorities in AV vehicle design according to accessibility targets. Figure 36 represents the percentage of the sample and per group that indicates that target as a main priority.

Figure 36: % of the sample that consider important each accessibility priority

In general, the main priorities in accessibility needs are: Elderly people or with moderate problems (72%) and People with disability (60%),

Children needs are a priority only for women, with significant differences among gender ($p < 0.05$ in X^2), notably for the group of women with children ($p < 0.05$ in X^2 in factor "group"). For this group children's needs is the first priority (80%).

Making easier weekly house hold shopping has higher priority for the group of men without children ($p < 0.05$ in X^2 in factor "group") than for the other groups, being the second priority for this group.

ECONOMY.

Figure 37 shows the scores for the statements related to the economic aspects of AVs in the UESI questionnaires.

Figure 37: Agreement scores for economy related statements.

Regarding the perception that “AVs will be too expensive” there exist differences among groups with/without children ($p < 0.05$), Participants without children (5.8) agree more with this statement than participants with children (4.8). For the group of women with children this score is significantly lower ($p < 0.05$ factor group) with an opinion close to neutrality (4.3) about this statement.

In the statement “The overall cost (energy, maintenance, repairs) of AVs will be reduced compared to traditional cars” the mean answer is neither agree or disagree (4.1) and there are no differences according to any factor in the analysis.

ENVIRONMENT. Emissions and Noise

All statements related to the environment improvement due to AVs are agreed on by participants, with a mean score of around 6 (Figure 38)

Figure 38: Agreement scores for environment related statements.

For the statement “AVs will reduce ecological impact” there exist differences by gender ($p < 0.05$). Women agree more than men ($p < 0.05$) with this statement; however, this difference is due to the lower agreement of men without children ($p < 0.05$ factor group).

DESIGN OPTIONS. External shape

In general, regarding the targets of external shape included in the UESI questionnaire (Figure 39), participants are more in agreement that the external shape of AV should make easier the access of people with reduced mobility in comparison to the target's “aerodynamics” and “differentiation with conventional cars”.

For the group of men with children “the access of people with reduced mobility” and “aerodynamics” are at the same level, around 5.3, with lower agreement with the target “differentiation with conventional cars” (3.2).

Figure 39: Agreement scores for external shape statements.

In this statement “make easier the access of people with reduced mobility” all factors are significant ($p < 0.05$ for gender and with/without children). This fact is due to the differences between the groups of women without children and men with children. Women without children score the statement close to the maximum agreement (6,9) and men with children score it lower (5,4).

In the other statements, there are not significant differences according to any factor. In general, the statement “optimize aerodynamics” has a score of 5.5 and regarding whether the AVs should be differentiated from conventional car, participants neither agree or disagree with this proposal (3.9).

DESIGN OPTIONS. Criteria for AVs decisions making

Figure 40 shows the importance score assigned by participants to the different criteria for AVs decision making.

Figure 40: Importance scores for criteria for AV decision making.

The most important criterion for participants is the optimization of wellbeing of other road users. In this criterion women score higher than men ($p < 0.05$), however, although the differences are significant, they are small (0.3). In general, this criterion is followed in importance by the optimization of traffic flow and dynamic comfort of passengers.

The importance score for optimization of energy efficiency criterion also differs for women with respect to men ($p < 0.05$), specially for women with children ($p < 0.05$), scoring higher this criterion.

DESIGN OPTIONS. Importance of keeping the control.

On average, the importance of keeping control of the different features is similar among all features except for the selection of variables related to ecological impact, that exhibits lower importance, especially for men.

Figure 41: Importance scores for keeping the control of different driving features.

In general, women (especially those without children) score the importance of keeping the control and the features highly. The UESI questionnaire includes a related statement “For me it is very important to keep a minimum sense of control of AVs even if I am not driving” where women have a higher score ($p < 0.05$).

In particular, women score ($p < 0.05$) the importance of controlling the type of driving mode, the selection of the route and the variables related to ecological impact higher than men.

Participants without children score the importance of controlling the speed and the interaction mode with the car (voice, visual...) higher than participants with children ($p < 0.05$). In these features, as we observe in the values in Figure 41, these differences are due to the scores of women without children, however it is not significant ($p < 0.1$ factor group).

Conclusions

The **overall perception of autonomous vehicles of the sample is positive**. Some assessments of AVs' benefits are shared by all participants without differences among genders or by the presence of children in the family composition, while some were not shared.

The **acceptance** of autonomous vehicles is similar for all groups, between 5 and 6 on the agreement scale. The average **trust in the AV automotive industry is high** (mean 6) and **trust in the autonomous vehicle** displacement (mean 5,3) and do not show significant differences according to the factors under study. All participants **agree on the improvement of traffic efficiency, traffic management, travel time and parking** due to AVs with agreement scores between 5,5 and 6. Participants would also be comfortable sharing data for these purposes.

Regarding **safety aspects**, the perceived **reduction of accident rate** with AVs is similar for all groups, with a mean of **5.7** in the agreement scale. However, in the statement "**AVs are safer than conventional cars under any conditions**", the agreement is lower close to neutrality and there exist differences by gender. **Women score lower than men and do even slightly disagree (3.7)** with this statement.

In the assessment of the **AVs accessibility improvement** "I think AVs will facilitate the mobility of people who are not able to drive or to take a conventional car ..." the agreement score is high (6.2) without differences according to the factors considered. In general, the main priorities in accessibility needs are shared: Elderly people or with moderate problems (72%) and People with disability (60%). However, it was also found that **Children's needs are a priority only for women**, notably for the group of women with children (80%) for whom this is their first priority.

In the perceived **reduction of ecological impact due to AVs, women agree (6.3) more than men (5.5)** with this statement, this difference is due to the lower agreement of men without children.

Regarding the main criteria of **AVs decision making**, all groups agree that the most important criterion for participants is the optimization of wellbeing of other road users. However, the importance score for **optimization of energy efficiency** criterion differs for women than men, **women score higher the importance of this criterion**.

The perception of the capability to perform simultaneous tasks in an AV is similar and high for all groups. However, **women show, in general, higher interest in performing simultaneous activities than men**, and especially the group of women with children under 12. Regarding work during displacement, **women are more interested in working during** displacement than men. For men and women **with children the interest "to care for other passengers" is higher**.

Women score, in general, higher the importance of keeping the control of the driving features, and especially women without children.

Willingness to buy an AV, surveyed before the experiment, is different for men and women. Women express disagreement while men assign a neutral score. After the experiment, gender is not significant anymore but factor "with/without children" becomes significant. **Women with**

children, that before the experiment expressed disagreement with this statement, after the experience in the simulator are the group with the highest agreement with the statement. However, this answer could be influenced by the perceived cost; for the statement that AVs will be too expensive, women with children express lower agreement.

In transport habits we found differences, **50% of women trip chain at least once a week, however, only 25% of men do**. As stated by bibliographic research, trip chaining has a gender bias, however, the factor “with/without children” is not significant in trip chaining frequency.

The **frequency of displacements per purpose is similar between genders**, but frequency of displacements for “own leisure activities” is higher for participants without children and “accompanying my family to their leisure activities” is higher for participant with children.

As we observed, **AV perception is positive and shared in main aspects**. However, we found **relevant differences, that need to be addressed for a fair user centred design of this technology**. In particular, we found defences in the perception related to **environmental aspects, safety aspects, differences in design priorities** (decision making criteria, accessibility needs, control features) **transport habits** and differences in the interest in performing **simultaneous tasks**. These differences must be further explored and translated into design features to address the needs of different users.

Regression analysis on UESI surveys results

Descriptive sample statistics

In UC II UESI questionnaires were collected by two different sources. In the experimental sessions in IBV, participant answered the UESI questionnaires after the experiments in the autonomous driving simulator to gather their opinion. The other source was through an online survey with a Spanish and English version. A total of 96 questionnaires were collected (40 in the experimental session, 47 in the Spanish version of the online survey and 9 in the English version). The responses of those who met the following criteria were analysed for this report:

- Identified as either male, female, trans female, trans male, nonbinary, or prefer not to say.
- Completed the questionnaire

The sample of participants in the experimental session followed an experimental design. In particular, the sample was a total of 40 participants, drivers between 25-55 years old. The sample was equilibrated in two experimental factors, 50% men and 50% women, and 50% had at least a child under 12 years old and 50% do not have children under 12 years old.

In the total sample of 96 respondents, 44 of respondent were males, 45 females, 1 nonbinary, and 6 prefer not to say whose ages ranged from 18 years to above 65 years were included. The majority of respondents age was between 25- and 55-years old (71.8%), 21.4% younger than 25 years old and 5% older than 55 years old.

The 100% of the sample have a driving licence and the majority (89.6%) drives at least twice a week and most respondents lives in an urban area (83.3%)

The percentage of sample living with dependents is 57.3% and 40.6% in the sample travel with dependents on weekly basis. Regarding trip chaining, 41.7% of the sample in their daily displacements, making intermediate stops at least once a week.

Table 11: Frequency and percentage data of gender, age and living area demographics by gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non binary (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Total (100%)
	44 (45.8)	45 (46.9)	1 (1.0)	6 (6.3)	96
AGE					
18-24 years	7 (15.9)	2 (4.4)	1 (100)	0 (0)	10 (10.4)
25-34 years	5 (11.4)	6 (13.3)	0 (0)	0 (0)	11 (11.5)
35-44 years	17 (38.6)	18 (40)	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	37 (38.5)
45-54 years	13 (29.5)	17 (37.8)	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	32 (33.3)
55-64 years	2 (4.5)	1 (2.2)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	4 (4.2)
Above 65	0 (0)	1 (2.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.0)
Prefer not to say	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	1 (1.0)
AREA					
Rural	4 (9.1)	3 (6.7)	1 (100)	1 (16.7)	9 (9.4)
Urban	36 (81.8)	39 (86.7)	0 (0)	5 (83.3)	80 (83.3)
Suburban	3 (6.8)	3 (6.7)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6 (6.3)
Prefer not to say	1 (2.3)	(0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.0)

Table 12: Frequency and percentage data of income, and dependent in the family unit by gender

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non binary (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Total (100%)
	44 (45.8)	45 (46.9)	1 (1.0)	6 (6.3)	96
SALARY INCOME					
No Income	2 (4.5)	(0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (2.1)
Less than 10,999	1 (2.3)	1 (2.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (2.1)
11,000-20,999	11 (25.0)	10 (22.2)	1 (100)	0 (0)	22 (22.9)
21,000-30,999	9 (20.5)	6 (13.3)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	16 (16.7)
31,000-40,999	13 (29.5)	16 (35.6)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	30 (31.25)
41,000-50,999	5 (11.4)	2 (4.4)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	8 (8.3)
51,000-70,999	1 (2.3)	1 (2.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (2.1)
More than 70,000	0 (0)	1 (2.2)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	2 (2.1)
Prefer not to say	2 (4.5)	8 (17.8)	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	12 (12.5)
IN YOUR FAMILY UNIT, DO YOU LIVE WITH ANY DEPENDENTS (E.G. CHILDREN, ELDERLY, CARING FOR DISABLED)?					
No	20 (45.5)	17 (37.8)	1 (100)	3 (50)	41 (42.7)
Preschool Children (under 5)	6 (13.6)	15 (33.3)	0 (0)	1 (16.7)	22 (22.9)
School Age Children (5-16 Years)	15 (34.1)	12 (26.7)	0 (0)	2 (33.3)	29 (30.2)
Disabled Person	2 (4.5)	1 (2.2)	0 (0)	(0)	3 (3.125)
Elderly	1 (2.3)	(0)	0 (0)	(0)	1 (1.0)

In general terms, the majority of respondents have an age between 25- and 55-years olds (71.8%), lives in urban area (83.3%), drives frequently, at least twice a week (89.6%). The sample is equilibrated in terms of women (46.9%) and men (45.8 %), also in living with a dependent person (57.3%), travel with dependents in a weekly base (40.6%) and trip chaining.

It is important to highlight that some of the sample descriptive are influence with the experimental sample design in UC II experiments.

Regression analysis

From the correlation matrix showed below, the area in red indicates a correlation index lower than 0.40: the correlation between the variables is very low.

1. Figure 42: Correlation Matrix for Use case II dataset.

Three different cluster were defined from the dataset collected and they were used to predict using a stepwise regression approach the following dependent variables:

1. **Autonomous vehicle excitement**, predicted on the cluster named the blue cluster about “**car usage background and familiarity with different type of assisted driving technologies**” that also include demographic characteristics
2. **Own control need** was predicted on the cluster of variables called the yellow cluster about **user needs for trips types and frequency and user preferences on driving characteristics**
3. **Acceptance of AV** predicted on the cluster named the green cluster about “**AV characteristics and user preference and priority assigned to those characteristics**”

Table 12: Variables used to predict Excitement of the drivers for the use of autonomous vehicles

ACCESS TO A CAR	personal activities	Adaptive cruise control use
DRIVING_EXPERIENCE	shopping	Lane keep assistance use
DRIVING_FREQUENCY	holidays	Automatic emergency braking use
DRIVING_ENJOY	holidays long distance	Backup cameras and parking sensors use
work commute	PRIOR_KNOWLEDGE	Speed monitoring and warning signals use
kids school	USE_INVEHICLE_TECH	New technology propensity
family activities no leisure	Automatic Parking use	New technology interest
family activities leisure		

Table 13: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach to predict 'Autonomous vehicle excitement'.

Predictors	Autonomous Vehicle excitement		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	1.96	-0.67 – 4.59	0.141
USE_INVEHICLE_TECH	0.25	0.08 – 0.41	0.004
Backup cameras and parking sensors use	-0.10	-0.23 – 0.03	0.144
New technology propensity	0.14	-0.06 – 0.34	0.179
New technology interest	-0.27	-0.48 – -0.07	0.010
Age	-0.36	-0.62 – -0.10	0.007
Income	0.20	0.06 – 0.35	0.006
Professional status	0.21	0.07 – 0.35	0.004
Illness/incapacity	1.60	0.16 – 3.03	0.029
Nationality	0.68	-0.02 – 1.39	0.057
Gender	0.40	-0.04 – 0.83	0.073
Discrimination	0.97	-0.18 – 2.11	0.096
Travel time	-0.02	-0.04 – 0.00	0.063
Observations	96		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.410 / 0.325		

In the first regression model applied to predict **Excitement of the drivers for the use of autonomous vehicles** the variables describing car usage background and familiarity with different type of assisted driving technologies that were found to be relevant (alongside the demographic) are the following:

- New technology propensity,
- Experience in use of in vehicle assisted driving technologies
- Age, Income
- Professional status and Illness.
- Nationality and Gender were found mildly interesting in this.

Table 14: Variables used to predict propensity for the drivers to retain own control on the AV

TRIP_CHAINING	WITHOUT_STEERINGWHEEL	TIME_VS_TRAFFIC_FLOW
TYPE_DISPLACEMENT_FREQ	SPORT_DRIVING	Optimise energy efficiency
Frequency home purchases trips	COMFORT_DRIVING	Optimise the wellbeing
frequency Own activities trips	SIMULTANEOUS_ACTIVITIES	Reduce time to destination point
Go to my workplace or to study	INTERACTION_TYPE_NORMAL	Optimise the dynamic comfort
frequency of performing tasks	INTERACTION_TYPE_EMERGENCY	Facilitate the performance of other tasks
SAFETY	TIME_VS_ECO	Facilitate passenger interaction
TRUST_IN_INDUSTRY	TIME_VS_CONFORT	

Table 15: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach to predict 'Own control need'.

Predictors	OWN_CONTROL_NEED		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	3.28	0.19 – 6.36	0.038
TYPE_DISPLACEMENT_FREQ	-0.21	-0.38 – -0.03	0.022
frequency Own activities trips	0.19	-0.04 – 0.42	0.110
Go to my workplace or to study	0.19	-0.00 – 0.37	0.052
SIMULTANEUS_ACTIVITIES	-0.10	-0.24 – 0.05	0.182
TIME_VS_ECO	0.19	0.02 – 0.37	0.029
TIME_VS_CONFORT	-0.17	-0.36 – 0.03	0.088
Optimise energy efficiency	0.22	-0.03 – 0.46	0.079
Optimise the wellbeing	-0.19	-0.46 – 0.09	0.179
Reduce time to destination	0.44	0.21 – 0.68	<0.001
Optimise the dynamic comfort	-0.23	-0.54 – 0.09	0.159
Facilitate passenger's interaction	0.13	-0.06 – 0.32	0.165
Country	-0.58	-1.15 – -0.01	0.046
Illness/incapacity	-1.37	-2.98 – 0.24	0.093
Gender	0.74	0.24 – 1.24	0.004
Discrimination	1.42	0.18 – 2.65	0.025
Travel time	-0.02	-0.04 – 0.01	0.166
Observations	96		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.484 / 0.372		

In the second regression model applied to predict the propensity of the driver to retain control on an autonomous vehicle, the variables describing user needs for trips types and frequency and user preferences on driving characteristics that were found to be relevant (alongside the demographic) are the followings:

- The need to reduce time to destination,
- Gender was found very relevant (As female responders in the sample have expressed more of an interest in retaining control)

- Type of frequency for different trip purposes (such as using the car for own activities, or for caring responsibilities)
- The need to optimise time vs environmental impact
- Country of responders
- And having experienced discrimination on public transport before (which make the users more likely to use a car instead).

Table 16: Variables used to predict propensity for drivers' acceptance for AV

select route to destination point	optimise aerodynamics of the vehicle	benefits_safer	safer_congestion
select variables related to ecological impact	easier access of prm	benefits_simultaneity	trust
Speed control	information_exchange	benefits_interaction_passenger	simultaneity
degree of fulfilment with traffic norms	training	benefits_parking	boring
select variables of interior comfort conditions	data_share	prob_expensive	pleasant
select preferred interface interaction mode	exclusive_infrastructure	prob_reliability	time
prioritize mobility of people with problems	benefits_inclusiveness_do -- not_drive	prob_unsafe	city_traffic
prioritize transporting bulky loads	benefits_traffic_flow	prob_decision	inclusive_mobility
prioritize pregnant women's needs	benefits_faster_displacement	prob_boring	expensive
prioritize oversized people needs	benefits_eco	prob_traffic	cost_reduce
prioritize mobility of people with disability	control_congested	prob_complex	ecology
prioritize features household shopping	less_control_congested	accident_rate	reduce_noise
exterior_shape	knowledge	traffic	control
	use_little_interest	safer_normal	purchase

Table 17: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach to predict 'Acceptance'.

Predictors	ACCEPTANCE		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	5.68	2.59 – 8.76	0.001
select route to destination point	0.13	-0.02 – 0.29	0.096
Speed	-0.25	-0.42 – -0.08	0.005
Degree of fulfilment with traffic norms	-0.08	-0.20 – 0.05	0.217
prioritize pregnant women's needs	-0.67	-1.08 – -0.27	0.002
prioritize mobility of people with disability	0.38	-0.07 – 0.83	0.097
prioritize features household shopping	0.39	-0.06 – 0.84	0.090
easier access of PRM	0.41	0.13 – 0.68	0.004
INFORMATION_EXCHANGE	0.34	-0.08 – 0.75	0.111
TRAINNING	-0.22	-0.32 – -0.11	<0.001
DATA_SHARE	0.19	0.08 – 0.31	0.001
EXCLUSIVE_INFRASTRUCTURE	-0.09	-0.21 – 0.02	0.118
BENEFITS_TRAFFIC_FLOW	-0.23	-0.44 – -0.02	0.031
BENEFITS_FASTER_DISPLACEMENT	0.32	0.15 – 0.50	<0.001
BENEFITS_ECO	0.26	0.09 – 0.42	0.003
BENEFITS_INTERACTION_PASSENGER	-0.23	-0.37 – -0.09	0.002
PROB_EXPENSIVE	0.27	0.13 – 0.42	<0.001
PROB_DECISION	-0.16	-0.31 – -0.01	0.034
PROB_BORING	-0.15	-0.29 – -0.01	0.039
ACCIDENT_RATE	0.25	-0.02 – 0.52	0.065
SAFER_NORMAL	-0.13	-0.32 – 0.07	0.200
SAFER_CONGESTION	-0.33	-0.56 – -0.11	0.005
TRUST	0.48	0.28 – 0.67	<0.001
BORING	0.31	0.18 – 0.45	<0.001
CITY_TRAFFIC	-0.42	-0.63 – -0.21	<0.001

EXPENSIVE	0.09	-0.07 – 0.25	0.241
CONTROL_CONGESTED	-0.23	-0.36 – -0.10	0.001
LESS_CONTROL_CONGESTED	-0.16	-0.27 – -0.04	0.010
KNOWLEDGE	-0.27	-0.41 – -0.14	<0.001
USE_LITTLE_INTEREST	-0.38	-0.50 – -0.25	<0.001
PURCHASE	0.22	0.09 – 0.34	0.001
Country	0.65	0.22 – 1.08	0.004
Education	0.09	-0.00 – 0.19	0.054
Household	-0.13	-0.26 – -0.00	0.042
Live w dependent	-0.16	-0.36 – 0.03	0.096
Illness/incapacity	1.48	0.51 – 2.44	0.003
Nationality	-0.69	-1.26 – -0.12	0.019
Ethnicity	-1.85	-2.60 – -1.10	<0.001
Gender	-0.32	-0.69 – 0.05	0.085
Travel time	-0.04	-0.06 – -0.03	<0.001
BENEFITS_SAFER	-0.15	-0.36 – 0.06	0.152
Observations	96		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.834 / 0.714		

In the third regression model applied to predict drivers' acceptance of AV, the variables used describe AV characteristics and user preference and priority assigned to those characteristics that were found to be relevant (alongside the demographic) are the following:

- The possible benefits of faster displacements,
- The need to address capacity to manage city traffic and be safe in traffic congestions
- The need to have training for this new mode of transport and the knowledge required for the users
- Capacity to address the needs of passengers with reduced mobility (PRM)
- The need to address the users concern about how expensive this mode of transport is going to be
- The possible ecological benefits offered by AVs

Among the demographic characteristics the following elements appeared significant:

- Whether the responder is affected by a chronic illness (looking at the coefficient associated with this characteristic in the regression analysis people with this situation appear to be more prone to accept AV)
- Household type (younger responders with no dependents appear to be keener on accepting AV)
- Level of education of the responders (higher education level are associated with highest likelihood of acceptance of AV).
- Ethnicity (this variable is a binary variable where 0 is associated with the majority or “in-group” characteristic which in this case is “white-Caucasian” while 1 is associated with the minority or “out-group” characteristic, that is, non-white Caucasian. The regression indicates that outgroup responders were less keen on AV acceptance).

It is important to note that the sample size was very small and some of those considerations may change if the sample size was to be increased, as we had 87 responders out of 97 concentrated in one country only (Spain) and only 6 out of the 97 responders were above 54 years of age.

5. Analysis of users' concerns from social media

Objective of the analysis and alignment with the general DIAMOND's methodology

With DAD and UESI surveys we can shed light on the priorities, satisfaction and opinions of users on different aspects of the services, with a fine-grained characterization of the users along different demographic attributes. This allows us to carry out an accurate analysis that accounts for many different aspects. On the downside, for such analyses we can only rely on limited samples of users, that we were able to reach through various means in the data collection phase, and that were available to take the time for answering the surveys.

With social media data analysis (see Fig. 2) we aim to complement the analysis of survey data with larger samples of users, although at the expense of user characterization, as we do not have demographic attributes of social media users.

By retrieving from the Twitter API all messages related to a relevant topic, such as “Velib” or “autonomous vehicles”, we can virtually access all conversations that take place in the social network related to these topics, and get a picture of the concerns of users with regards to such topics.

Furthermore, while survey-based analyses are naturally bound by the questions that need to be planned in advance, with social media analysis we just need to have general keywords as input, and relevant topics emerge spontaneously from users' messages. For example, when the questionnaires were developed coronavirus was not yet such a prominent issue, and no questions related to the pandemic were included; instead, as we will see issues related to transport and covid emerged naturally in the conversations we tracked in social media.

Although demographic characteristics of Twitter users are not available, we can infer gender so we can look at the differences between men's and women's discourse about each topic. In this way, our approach can help us to unveil gender differences in concerns and feelings related to transport from larger samples of the population, and give us precious hints about issues that are relevant for women and underestimated by men in current transport systems.

Data and Methods

We chose to focus our social media analysis on Twitter, given its widespread usage, and the availability of APIs that allow one to retrieve user-generated content in real time.

Data from Twitter were retrieved using Kalium, a tool developed by Eurecat that allows one to efficiently and flexibly manage the tracking of social network data in real time (Napalkova et al, 2018). Kalium ensures robustness, scalability and flexibility when it comes to collecting and managing social network data.

Keywords based Twitter data collection

Content based data were collected by retrieving in real time all tweets mentioning any keyword from a list that we elaborated with the help of the partners involved in each use case.

The table below shows the keywords selected for each use case, and the corresponding numbers of tweets collected. Keywords were carefully selected in order to avoid ambiguities, and therefore generate comprehensive yet clean datasets.

Keywords for use case I and use case III were univocally associated with service in the area of Barcelona, Warsaw and Paris, respectively; for Use case II, data were collected at global level from the whole twittersphere, with strong predominance of tweets in English.

Table 18: keywords used for Twitter data collection in each use case, and number of tweets collected

	Keywords	Language	# tweets
UC I FGC (Barcelona)	ServeiFGC, @FGC, #ferrocarrils	Catalan, Spanish	20k
UC I ZTM (Warsaw)	KartaWarszawiaka, tramwajewarszawskie, tramwaj, wtpwarszawa, ztmwarszawa, ztmwaw, @WTP_Warszawa	Polish	25k
UC II Autonomous vehicles (global)	autonomouscar, autonomoscars, SelfDrivingCar, selfdrivingcars, driverlesscar, driverlesscars, Driverless, selfdriving, automateddriving, autonomousdriving, connectedautomateddriving, autonomousvehicle, autonomousvehicles, driverlessvehicle, driverlessvehicles, SelfDrivingVehicle, SelfDrivingVehicles, driverlessmobility, autopilot, robotaxi, robotaxis Volvo360c, TeslaAutopilot, AudiAicon, ContinentalCUbE	English	1.1M
UC III Velib (Paris)	velib	French	42k

Gender inference

Gender inferred through the m3Inference tool, that relies on deep learning models, trained over a large sample of users from different countries (Wang et al, 2019). The method was proved to achieve high accuracy for all major European countries and languages.

Based on the user name, short bio and picture, the tool returns the estimated probability of a user to be man or woman. We assign a gender to users having a probability above a threshold of 0.9 for one of the two genders. In this way we ensure that we only have reliable estimation, and leave gender unassigned for the remaining users.

We are aware that this method has the limitations of not dealing with non-binary gender, and of not further characterizing women according to other demographic characteristics. Unfortunately, these limitations are embedded in the method, that allows us to study a much larger sample of users, but with coarser-grained granularity. Still, we believe that this analysis can add value as it encompasses a large sample of users, up to hundreds of thousands (any user who expressed thoughts or feelings in tweets including keywords associated with our use cases).

General analysis of concerns: word and hashtag frequency

To detect gender differences in the concerns about our use cases, we compare the frequency of words in tweets where the author was identified to be woman, with respect to those where the author was identified to be a man. To have a richer picture, we compare the use of words, as well as the use of bigrams, and of hashtags. This allows us to identify words, hashtags or bigrams that are used more or less frequently by women, with respect to men, which can point out gender differences in user preferences and concerns.

To highlight gender differences, we do not just show the simple frequency of words appearing in tweets posted by men and women; instead, we go one step further, and show the difference in frequency: on one side we show words that are more frequently used by women than by men, and on the other side, conversely, words that are more frequently used by men than by women. We measure the difference in frequency and show it in such a way that it is possible to identify the words that are used with much higher frequency by women than by men, and vice-versa (Laniado et al, 2012). We show this information in tag clouds, a well-known visual model that allows one to immediately grasp the content of a set of words (Halvey & Keane, 2007). We also show in a bar-chart the words with the highest difference in frequency in favour of men and women.

Detailed analysis: word co-occurrence

For a more detailed analysis of gender differences in concerns with respect to specific topics, we then look at the words that co-occur more often with some specific selected words.

For each selected word, we look at the words that co-occur more often with it in tweets posted by women and men, respectively.

To this end, we represent each word as a vector, with a cell for each tweet: value 1 when the tweet contains the keyword, value 0 otherwise. We then compute the co-occurrence weight between two words as the cosine similarity between their corresponding vectors. In this way, the co-occurrence weight is higher the more two words occur together, and the less they appear alone in the dataset.

Sentiment analysis

For sentiment analysis we rely on the NRC-VAD lexicon, where 20,000 frequent English words are labelled on a scale according to valence, arousal and dominance (Mohammad, 2018). A text is then assigned a value of valence according to a weighted average, where each word contributes with a score, based on its valence weighted by the frequency.

We then are able to evaluate the overall score of a text along these dimensions, as well as the contribution of each individual word in it.

According to valence, words are divided between positive (more positive than the average valence score) and negative (more negative than the average valence score).

To compare valence by gender, we draw a shift graph (Gallagher et al, 2021) where we show the top words that contribute most to a gender difference in valence, distinguishing four cases, corresponding to positive/negative words that are more/less frequently used by women with respect to men.

Negative words are depicted in blue (full blue, on the left, for negative words used more frequently by women; faded blue, on the right, for negative words used less frequently by women), positive words are depicted in yellow (full yellow, on the right, for positive words used more frequently by women; faded yellow, on the left, for positive words used less frequently by women).

In this way it is possible to assess not only whether women use a more positive or more negative language than men with respect to the topic under analysis, but also why, e.g. which are the words that make women's tweets more positive and more negative.

Results

We first describe the general results of user gender identification, and the size of the enriched datasets for each use case; then we describe the results obtained use case by use case.

Sentiment analysis works reliably on large volumes of text data, and tools available are better suited for the English language. Therefore, given the size of the Twitter dataset collected for Use case II in English is one order of magnitude higher than for the other use cases, we only report results for English; for the other languages, the size of the datasets after discarding users whose gender could not be identified (see next section) was too small.

User gender distribution

The table below shows the number of users that were labelled as men and women with estimated accuracy above 90%; the remaining users were left unlabelled.

Table 19: Number of users whose gender could be automatically inferred in each use case

	men	women	unlabelled	total users
UC1-FGC	6265	1899	15991	20357
UC1-ZTM	4862	1580	22497	25779
UC2	217925	55852	1174411	1336484
UC3	15633	4171	32928	44390

Use case 1 – FGC

General analysis of concerns: word and hashtag frequency

Figure 42: UCI – FGC. Tag clouds showing the words that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and by women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are excluded.

Looking at the difference in hashtag use, we see that women are more concerned about the environment when speaking about FGC. They also mention more often issues related to fares (“usual”).

Use case 1 – ZTM

General analysis of concerns: word and hashtag frequency

Figure 44. UCI – FGC. Tag clouds showing the words that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and by women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are excluded.

Figure 45. UCI ZTM: Tag clouds showing the words that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are included.

Detailed analysis: word co-occurrence

Table 21. UCI ZTM: Top 10 most co-occurring words by cosine similarity with each selected word (first column), in messages posted by men (second column) and women (third column).

	men	women
autobus	jaka, dzien, najpierw, czekac, zdaze, przyjechal, rower, metro, samochod, pociag	przystanku, musze, ludzi, dopiero, spoznie, pociag, pozniej, tez, przyjechal, potem
tramwajow	tez, mniej, miescie, wroclawiu, wiecej, zakonczono, liczbe, pociagow, utrudnienia, kursowaniu	ludzi, chodzi, chyba, ogole, kurwa, wczoraj, chcialam, ludzie, jezu, miescie, gente, mas

With respect to "autobus", men speak about other means of transport, bike (rower), subway (metro), car (samochod), train (pociag).

In both cases (autobus and tramway), women speak more about people (ludzi), express more frustration and use more swear words.

Use case II – Autonomous vehicles

General analysis of concerns: word and hashtag frequency

Figure 46. UC2 – Autonomous vehicles. Tag clouds showing the hashtags that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and by women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are excluded.

Figure 47. UC2 Autonomous vehicles. Tag clouds showing the words that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and by women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are excluded.

While men tend to focus more on aspects related to technology and business, women are more concerned with social impact and social context and feelings.

Detailed analysis: word co-occurrence

Table 22. UC2 Autonomous vehicles: Top 10 most co-occurring words by cosine similarity with each selected word (first column), in messages posted by men (second column) and women (third column).

	men	women
feel	confident, predicting, minute, sometimes, numb, autopilot, life, living, peaceful	empty, days, ever, numb, else, anyone, anymore, lately, autopilot
crash	killed, ntsb, video, enabling, game, needless, playing, finds, inquiry, fatal	drivers, killed, distracted, ntsb, video, game, playing, finds, inquiry, fatal
future	libra, I3th, artiicialinterlligence, meatless, kitchens, impact, including, positive, conversation, wef20	cash, pedestrian, near, solutions, selfdriving, autonomousvehicles, age, curing, introduces, swappable
covid19	bigdata, socialdistancing, medical, justify, centers, roi, deployments, mules, impacts, cloudcomputing	single, highest, programs, florida, treat, patients, transport, prevent, cases, illinois

Looking at words co-occurring with “feel”, we see that for men word “confident” has the highest cosine similarity, and then we find other positive words such as “peaceful”.

Sentiment analysis

The graph below represents the difference in valence between tweets by women and by men.

Figure 48. Word shift graph of valence of women tweets, in comparison to men’s tweets. Word shifts show the top fifty contributing words to the difference in sentiment: on the left, the words that contribute to women’s tweets being more negative than men’s tweets (either for higher frequency of negative words, depicted in full blue, or for lower frequency of positive words, depicted in faded yellow), while words to the right on the opposite contribute to make women’s tweets more positive than men’s tweets (either for higher frequency of positive words, depicted in full yellow, or for lower frequency of negative words, depicted in faded blue). Bars at the top show the overall sentiment difference and the effect of each type of word contribution on that difference.

The graph shows how sentiment in women’s language differs from men’s language: on the left, words that make women have a lower valence than men, on the right words that give an opposite contribution. As we can see, women tend to have overall a more negative language when speaking about AVs. This is mostly due to a lower use of positive words related to business, such as “money” or “cash”, and of positive words that can be associated with innovation, such as “amazing”, “breakthrough” or “success”; women’s more negative tone also depends on a higher use of negative words like “protest”, “wrong” or “ill”. On the other hand, positive words used more frequently by women include general positive words, and words related to social and daily life, such as “life”, “feel”, “today”, “health”, “family”, “school”. So, both for positive and negative words, women seem less interested than men in business and technological aspects, and more interested in the impact of AVs on the social context and on daily life.

Use case III

General analysis of concerns: word and hashtag frequency

Figure 49. Tag clouds showing the words that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and by women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are included.

The graphs show that the debate on Velib in Twitter is quite politicized, both among men and women. The former appears to be more interested in the electoral campaign (“Hidalgo” is the current major, running for reconfirmation), the latter on strikes and feminism.

Figure 50. UC3 – Velib. Tag clouds showing the words that are more frequent in tweets posted by men (left) and by women (right). Size is proportional to the difference in frequency. Retweets are included.

Looking at words frequency difference, again we see a quite politicized debate.

Detailed analysis: word co-occurrence

Table 23. UC3 Velib: Top 10 most co-occurring words by cosine similarity with each selected word (first column), in messages posted by men (second column) and women (third column).

	men	women
station	vide, menilmontant, rue, bonjour, bloques, aucun, pyrenees, velib, velos, pleine	velib, velo, fonctionnent, impossible, fonctionne, velos, electriques, aucun, bonjour, pleine
hidalgo	cyclistes, masques, fiasco, bilan, gratuits, pollution, mme, villani, metros, anne	merci, parisiens, mieux, gratuite, tout, seulement, faut, toutes, velib, lieu
covid	specifique, novlangue, poursuivre, elegante, hygiene, relais, paris 17, covid19fr, enrichit, frei	deconfinement, ainsi, dernieres, lemondedapres, developper, paris 19, made, opportunité, post, pret

In tweets involving the major’s name, men speak of “fiasco”, while women’s top co-occurring word is merci (“thanks”).

6. Analysis of user satisfaction surveys on service provisions and employment conditions

The survey was conducted in person by the DIAMOND research team on Rail Service operators in different countries (e.g., Ireland, Spain, Poland) via trains and stations at pre-approved routes and times. A consent form was included which outlined that respondents' participation in the survey was entirely voluntary, their replies would remain anonymous, and that gathered data was in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. Respondents were also provided with a brief description of the DIAMOND project including the aims of the overall project, and the specific purpose of the survey. The survey took 15-20 mins to complete. Approximately 50 questions covered all fairness characteristics considered from WP2. The raw data is made available in the diamond sharepoint repository and will be made available on the diamond toolbox after permission from the end user is confirmed.

Objective of the analysis and alignment with the general DIAMOND's methodology

The user satisfaction questionnaire responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs and perception for fairness characteristics of the service or employment analysed in each case study when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features. However, the analysis for use case II related to Autonomous Vehicles has been discussed in chapter 4 as it is connected with the simulation and the collection of physiological data from participants that were able to take part in the simulation study as well. For all other use cases the analyses of the user satisfaction surveys also enable a regression analysis on the main drivers and predictors identified for each use case when compared to the key variables used to describe users' appreciation or satisfaction for the service of employment conditions considered.

Methods used for the analysis

Descriptive statistics and Anova testing

The data was analysed using the statistical software programs SPSS (Version 26) and R. To examine whether the responses differed significantly ($p < .05$) for each item according to gender, one-way Analyses of Variance (ANOVAs) or non-parametric analyses were conducted on questions with Likert scale responses (1 to 7). Means of answers are presented in graph form in the Key Findings section. To examine intersectionality between different demographic information on responses, univariate analyses (e.g., two-way ANOVAs, non-parametric) were conducted. General linear modelling was also conducted to examine the relationships between the variables. Dichotomous answers were evaluated using relative percentages and statistical significance was verified using a chi squared analysis.

Factor analysis

To reduce the complexity of the dataset and make sense of the data, we grouped together the questions that tend to follow similar patterns, i.e. that tend to receive similar responses from the same users.

We first performed two statistical tests to make sure that the data are not unrelated and are suitable for structure detection: Bartlett's test and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test.

Then we computed the eigenvalues corresponding to each possible number of factors, and found a trade-off between accuracy and efficiency, choosing a number that ensures good quality and consistency of the grouping, with the minimum number of factors.

We then grouped the questions in the corresponding factors. We inspected manually the questions belonging to each factor to look for a common characteristic or topic, if any, and we named each factor accordingly.

For each factor, we then analysed the difference between different categories of respondents according to each demographic features. For the most relevant features for which we found significant differences through ANOVA test, we highlighted such differences through a boxplot.

Stepwise Regression analysis

The **stepwise regression** (or stepwise selection) used was aimed at identifying, for the variables included from the survey results, the one more relevant in predicting general satisfaction with fairness and inclusiveness for service users (use case I) and for the employees of transport organizations included for the use cases (use case IV). The method consists of iteratively adding and removing predictors, in the linear regression predictive model, so as to find the subset of variables in the data set that can provide the best performing model (which is to say the model with the lowest prediction error).

A stepwise regression approach can follow mainly three strategies (James et al., 2014; Bruce and Bruce, 2017):

1. **Forward selection**, which iteratively adds the most contributive predictors in the model starting from a no predictors situation and stops when the improvement is no longer statistically significant.
2. **Backward selection** (or **backward elimination**), which starts from a model that includes all predictors (full model) and then iteratively removes the least contributive predictors. It stops when there is a model where all predictors are statistically significant.
3. **Stepwise selection** (or sequential replacement) is a combination of forward and backward selections. The model starts with no predictors, then sequentially adds the most contributive predictors (like forward selection). After adding each new variable, any variable that no longer provides an improvement in the model fit is removed (like backward selection).

It is important to note that forward selection and stepwise selection can be applied in high-dimensional configurations, where the number of samples n is inferior to the number of predictors p , while backward selection requires that the number of samples n is larger than the number of variables p , so that the full model can be fit.

For the purpose of the present project, we have used the Stepwise selection approach in R, using the R MASS package for computing stepwise regression. The function used was “stepAIC()” as it chooses the best model using the **Akaike information criterion (AIC)**, which is an estimator of in-sample prediction error and thereby relative quality of statistical models for a given set of data. Suppose that we have a statistical model of some data. Let k be the number of estimated parameters in the model and let Lik_{max} be the maximum value of the likelihood function for the model. Then the AIC value of the model is expressed by the following function(1):

$$AIC = 2k - 2 \ln (Lik_{max})$$

Given a set of candidate models for the data, the preferred model is the one with the minimum AIC value. AIC rewards goodness of fit (as assessed by the likelihood function), and at the same time provides a penalty that is an increasing function of the number of estimated parameters. The penalty discourages overfitting, which is desired because increasing the number of parameters in the model almost always improves the goodness of the fit.

The function that allows this operation in R has an option named direction, which can take the following values: i) “both” (for stepwise regression, both forward and backward selection); “backward” (for backward selection) and “forward” (for forward selection). It returns the best final model.

The code line used is the following:

```
step.model <- stepAIC(full.model, direction = "both", trace = FALSE) summary(step.model)
```

Results for Use Case I

Use Case I - Summary of results

The survey aimed to assess the capability of the organisation in meeting the required needs, the accessibility, and the safety and security of transport users. The capability was assessed by a series of questions that examined the users’ ability to:

- travel in an appropriately designed transport system that met basic expectations and was environmental sound, and the user’s ability to access activities and services that people have reason to value;
- travel safely and securely using the public transport system;
- consider the service accessible to all groups in terms of design and comfort provided e.g., those with children, and in terms of fares and costs for those with lower income, including distribution of costs and benefits.

The variables considered in the user satisfaction questionnaire are aligned with the fairness characteristics defined in WP2 and they can be summarised in the following table.

Table 24: Summary of alignment between variables considered in the user satisfaction questionnaire and fairness characteristics for the use case

Q	Question TEXT	Level 2 fairness characteristics	Label
A1	It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service	Travel Purpose	easy to get to dest
A2	The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs	Service availability and efficiency	frequency service
A3	Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs	Service availability and efficiency	operational hrs
A4	I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station	Travel & Wayfinding information provision	travel infos station
A5	The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations) at this station meet my travel needs	Travel & Wayfinding information provision	announcements
A6	I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning services available on a smartphone app or online	Ticketing options & fares	travel ticketing
A7	I am satisfied that all services, exits, and platforms are clearly signposted	Travel & Wayfinding information provision	signs
A8	Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips	Travel Purpose	travel satisfaction
A9	Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security	Service availability and efficiency	travel satisfaction time, security
A10	I can easily travel to my work place using public transport, if this applies to you	Travel Purpose	travel to work satisfaction
A11	Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and better value for money than traveling by private car	Ticketing options & fares	value for money
B1	Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts, rail etc)	Universal Design	accessibility station
B2	There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station.	Universal Design	lighting
B3	The cleanliness and maintenance of the environment (station and the train) are adequate.	Cleanliness & Maintenance	cleanliness
B4	Facilities such as seating, backrests, and restrooms are adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities	Universal Design	seating
B5	The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs)	Furniture & Facilities	facilities
B6	There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.	Furniture & Facilities	parent facilities
B7	I Feel comfortable with air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.	Confort with ventilation	ventilation A/C
B8	I feel comfortable with the personal space available to me at stations and in carriages.	confort with eprsonal space (overcrowding)	confort with space
B9	I can easily get to my destination from the station by walking or using other means of transport	Ease of Intermodality	walking from station
B10	At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles.	Ease of Intermodality	safe access and parking

Q	Question TEXT	Level 2 fairness characteristics	Label
B11	When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.	Feeling safe	feel safe
B12	Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.	Safe belonging	safe belonging
B13	There are enough CCTV systems and other security measures visible to make me feel safe	CCTV Harassment & pickpocketing	cctv
B14	If needed, I am satisfied that I could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g. security staff, emergency number).	Harassment & pickpocketing	get help
B15	I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).	Overcrowding & Emergency Situations	evacuation

In general, across all use cases from the Northern European case study (Irish Rail), the southern European case study (FGC) and the Eastern European case study (ZTM) highlighted the following key findings:

- The questions were not very strongly correlated with correlation matrices indicating a correlation index below 0.45 for most cases. The connections where correlation was higher than 0.45 were around safety and security (variable such as B11, B12, B13 in table above), accessibility and conform (variable such as B7, B8, in table above) and general service satisfaction (A9, A8, A2 in table above) for both the Northern European rail service, Southern European and Eastern European sample.
- The results of stepwise analysis on linear regression on the prediction of general satisfaction highlighted salient characteristics that may differ from the Northern to the Southern and Eastern European sample, overall they all highlighted A3 (“Operational hours”) and or A2 (frequency of services), A4/A5 (“travel information and announcements about situations), A6 or A11 (“travel ticketing and prices”), B9 (easy to get to destination by walking or intermodality), B10 (“feeling safe all times of the day”), B4 (“How facilities are adequate for all gender and abilities”) B7 or B8 (conform with air conditioning and in general) B8 (“comfortable with the personal space”) B11 (“feeling safe at station any time of the day” and B10 (parking and access near station).
- In the demographic characteristics for the Northern European and Eastern European data set significant variables are “travelling with a dependent person” and “Having a chronic illness/disability”, in general the aspect of accessibility (for the Eastern European caring responsibility is also found as a factor), travelling with mobility aid is also relevant for the Southern European dataset where also income and coming from urban and or suburban/ rural areas were found to be relevant and Gender is found to be relevant when considering the satisfaction with “the travel to work” purpose for the southern and northern European sample
- The age group between 35-44 years seems to be more critical of the service provided than other age groups. This may also be because of higher demand and family responsibilities

experienced by the people in this age group such as caring responsibilities associated with young children.

- Gender is determinant for the perception of safety in data from the Northern European, Southern European and Eastern European data sample, where women are less satisfied than men about safety and security issues, and non-binary users even less.
- In all cases there is a high variability in perceived safety across stations; however, while in the FGC data users from urban areas are more satisfied with safety and users from rural areas less satisfied, in Irish Rail we observe the opposite. One statement that has consistently rated lower than others is “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, showing a lack of specific facilities for parents. This is true for all use cases.
- Users that have experienced discrimination tend to have lower satisfaction in all aspects of the service
- Similarly, for the Eastern European dataset, we found that ethnicity was also a relevant factor as significant difference between in-group, out-group respondents were found across multiple areas related to service needs and safety and security.

Use case 1 Irish rail

Although Irish Rail does not appear in Section 3, 4 nor 5, this company allowed us to gather additional UESI data so as to collaborate with DIAMOND broadening the data. In this way, this information was an opportunity to compare and validate the results coming from FGC and ZTM.

Overview and descriptive statistics

The responses of those who met the following criteria were analysed for this report:

- Identified as either male, female, trans female, trans male, non-binary, or prefer not to say.
- Completed the questionnaire.

A total of 336 rail transport users (163 males, 161 females, 12 non-binary) whose ages ranged from under 25 years to above 75 years were included. The majority of respondents were white (87.2%), Christian (59.6%), single (39.8%), heterosexual (85.6%) with a third level education (67.9%). The majority also did not have any dependents (69.8%), did not travel with dependents on weekly basis (87.8%), and were in paid employment (56.1%) that was full-time (70.1%).

Table 25: Frequency and percentage data of age and living area demographics by gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non Binary (%)	Total (100%)
	163 (48.5)	161 (47.9)	12 (3.6)	336
AGE				
18-34 years	70 (42.9)	74 (46)	3 (25)	147
35-44 years	30 (18.4)	32 (19.9)	3 (25)	65
45-64 years	41 (25.4)	37 (23)	1 (8.3)	79
Above 65 years	12 (7.4)	16 (9.9)	4 (33.3)	32
Prefer not to say	3 (1.8)	1 (.6)	-	4
AREA				
Rural	54 (35.1)	58 (37.4)	2 (16.7)	115 (36.1)
Suburban	4 (2.6)	2 (1.3)	2 (16.7)	10 (1.9)
Urban	12 (7.8)	18 (11.6)	6 (50)	30 (9.4)

Table 26: Frequency and percentage data of income, and marital/family status demographics by gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non Binary (%)	Total (100%)
SALARY INCOME				
No Income – 10,999	28 (18.6)	29 (18.9)	-	57 (18.3)
11,000-20,999	11 (7.3)	16 (10.6)	-	27 (8.7)
21,000-30,999	16 (10.6)	21 (13.9)	1 (8.3)	38 (12.2)
31,000-40,999	18 (11.9)	16 (10.6)	1 (8.3)	35 (11.2)
41,000-50,999	10 (6.6)	5 (3.3)	-	15 (4.8)
51,000-70,999	14 (9.3)	23 (15.2)	1 (8.3)	38 (12.2)
More than 70,000	25 (16.6)	11 (7.3)	1 (8.3)	37 (11.9)
Prefer not to say	29 (19.2)	30 (19.9)	6 (50)	65 (20.8)
MARITAL/FAMILY STATUS				
Married/Civil Partnership/Heterosexual	54 (35.1)	58 (37.4)	3 (25)	115 (36.1)
Married/Civil Partnership/Same Sex	4 (2.6)	2 (1.3)	-	6 (1.9)
Cohabiting	12 (7.8)	18 (11.6)	-	30 (9.4)

Lone Parent	7 (4.5)	5 (3.2)	-	12 (3.8)
Single	65 (42.2)	61 (39.4)	1 (8.3)	127 (39.8)
Prefer not to Say	12 (7.8)	11 (7.1)	6 (50)	29 (9.1)
IN YOUR FAMILY UNIT, DO YOU LIVE WITH ANY DEPENDENTS (E.G. CHILDREN, ELDERLY, CARING FOR DISABLED)?				
No	110 (74.3)	98 (64.9)	6 (50)	215 (69.8)
Yes	38 (23.3)	53 (32.9)	2 (16.7)	93 (27.7)

Overall, the respondents are quite a homogenous group in terms of ethnicity, race, religion, sexuality, education etc., and have minimal responsibilities in terms of caring for dependents. The rail users' similar characteristics may indicate that public transport appeals best to only certain sectors of the population (e.g., single employed with no dependents). However, it is also important to note that due to collecting data during the busiest times on weekdays, there is the possibility that commuters were over sampled. DIAMOND is currently collecting data from respondents who do not use public transport in order to provide further insight into the key findings.

Figure 51: Correlation matrix for the variables considered in the User satisfaction questionnaire for Irish rail

In the correlation matrix reported in the figure above safety and security are the variables represented as B11, Feeling safe, B12" Safe belonging- Harassment and pickpocketing, B13 "CCTV

and Harassment & pickpocketing protection”. While B7” Comfort with ventilation”, B8 “comfort with personal space” are representative variables for accessibility and comfort. Variables such as “travel ticketing, value for money, walking from station, frequency of service etc. are indicative of general satisfaction with service efficiency. The questions were not very strongly correlated with each other; the area in light yellow indicates a correlation index below 0.45. The areas in yellow are around safety and security (B11, B12, B13), accessibility and comfort (B7, B8) and general service satisfaction (A9, A8, A2).

Factor analysis

For this step of the analysis, in order to have an overview of the responses across different demographic groups, we now group questions into factors, or groups of questions that tend to follow similar response patterns.

The graph below (scree plot) shows the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors. Based on this graph, we chose 4 as the number of factors for this dataset, as it produces remarkably lower values than 3, and only slightly higher than with 5. It provides a good balance, producing acceptable results with a reasonable and manageable number of factors.

Figure 52: Use case I – Irish rail. Scree plot showing the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors

We now show the resulting factors, that group the questionnaire’s questions in four groups. We attributed a name to each factor based on manual inspection of the questions, to identify the main topics behind each of them.

Factor 0 - Accessibility and comfort

- Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts, rail etc)
- There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station.
- The cleanliness and maintenance of the environment (station and the train) are adequate.
- Facilities such as seating, backrests, and restrooms are adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities
- The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs)
- There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.
- I Feel comfortable with air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.
- I feel comfortable with the personal space available to me at stations and in carriages.
- At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles.

Factor 1 – Safety and security

- When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.
- Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.
- There are enough CCTV systems and other security measures visible to make me feel safe
- If needed, I am satisfied that I could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g. security staff, emergency phone number).
- I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).

Factor 2 - Service organization

- The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs
- Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs
- I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station
- The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations) at this station meet my travel needs
- I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning services available on a smartphone app or online
- I am satisfied that all services, exits, and platforms are clearly signposted

Factor 3 - Capability to address service needs

- It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service
- Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips
- Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security

- I can easily travel to my work place using public transport, if this applies to you
- Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and better value for money than traveling by private car
- I can easily get to my destination from the station by walking or using other means of transport

The factors tend to overlap with the Diamond project's higher-level categorization of features. However, they do not coincide exactly; in the subsequent analysis we will stick to these four factors that represent groups of questions that tend to be homogeneous, and therefore can be more easily analysed together.

Demographic differences by factor

We now look at how each demographic variable influences user satisfaction with respect to each set of questions (i.e., with respect to each factor), and show the corresponding differences with boxplots. We report only results for relevant cases in which we found evidence of statistically significant differences according to an ANOVA test, and omit all the other combinations of factors and demographic variables.

Factor 0 - Accessibility and comfort

Figure 53: UC 1 – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Station.

Figure 54: UC I – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Environment.

Figure 55: UC I – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Academic formation.

Users from rural environment and with lower levels of education tend to express higher satisfaction with respect to station accessibility and facilities.

Factor 1 – Safety and security

Figure 56: UC I – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Station.

Figure 57. UC I – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by whether users are living with some dependent person.

Figure 58: UC 1 – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Gender.

Satisfaction with respect to safety results to be dependent on gender, with lower satisfaction expressed by women and, to a higher extent, non-binary users; and on living with dependents, with users living with pre-school children having lower satisfaction. Irish citizens and people experiencing discrimination also report lower satisfaction (data not shown).

Factor 2 - Service organization

Figure 59: UC 1 – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Environment.

Figure 60. UC 1 – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by Academic formation.

Lower satisfaction with respect to service organization is expressed by users having lower education or living in urban or suburban areas, as well as users experiencing discrimination or taking longer journeys (data not shown).

Factor 3 – Capability to address service needs

Figure 61. UC I – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 3, grouped by Income.

Figure 62. UC I – Irish Rail. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 3, grouped by Age range.

Elderly people rated higher satisfaction with respect to this set of questions.

Responses for different types of demographic characteristics

We now follow a complementary approach, and take a more detailed look into the responses by the questionnaire's statements from different demographic groups.

Responses By Area (Urban Vs. Suburban Vs. Rural)

In the Figure below, the means for each question (1 = strongly disagree, 7 = strongly agree) by the area in which respondents live (Urban, Suburban, Rural) are presented. There is evidence that all respondents' needs are generally being met by the organisation. However, correlation analysis indicated that there were significant differences by living areas across a number of statements.

Figure 63: Means of total responses for all areas

The key differences identified on the basis of living in a rural, suburban and or urban environments are for the following statements:

- “The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 5.51$, $SD = 1.44$) agreed more with this statement than respondents in urban areas ($M = 4.85$, $SD = 1.66$).
- “I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 5.73$, $SD = 1.27$) agreed more with this statement than respondents in urban areas ($M = 5.20$, $SD = 1.48$) and suburban areas ($M = 5.24$, $SD = 1.49$).
- “Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts etc.)”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 4.67$, $SD = 1.49$) agreed more with this statement than respondents in suburban areas ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 1.61$).

- “Facilities such as seating, backrests, and restrooms are adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 4.78$, $SD = 1.44$) agreed more with this statement than respondents in urban areas ($M = 4.20$, $SD = 1.65$) and suburban areas ($M = 3.97$, $SD = 1.63$).

In sum, respondents living in rural areas indicated a higher level of agreement that their needs are being met than respondents living in urban and suburban areas, in particular with respect to service frequency, efficiency and accessibility. This may be because the people interviewed from rural areas are also in the older age groups/retired and in Ireland they travel for free and don't travel for work related reasons.

Responses By Age

In the Figure below, the means for each question by age group are presented. Again, there is evidence that all respondents' needs are generally being met by the organisation. However, correlation analysis indicated that there were significant age differences across a number of statements, with one group (35-44 years) showing more dissatisfaction than younger (18-35 years) and older age groups (65+ years).

Figure 64: Means of total responses by Age for questions related to ‘Capable of Meeting Required Needs’ questions.

Further analysis indicated that the age groups differed in their level of agreement with the following statements:

- “The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs (“respondents whose ages ranged from 18-35 ($M = 4.86$, $SD = 1.65$) and 35 – 44 years ($M = 4.97$, $SD = 1.64$) showed more disagreement with this statement than other respondents. “I can easily travel to

my work place using public transport, if this applies to you”, respondents whose ages ranged from 18-35 years ($M = 5.08$, $SD = 1.50$) agreed more with this statement than other respondents, especially those in age group of 35 – 44 years ($M = 4.24$, $SD = 1.8$).

- “Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and better value for money than traveling by private car” respondents who were aged 65 years or older ($M = 5.33$, $SD = 1.9$) agreed more with this statement than respondents in other age groups. This is indicative of the Irish policy of “free-travel” for all citizens over 65 years of age.
- “There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station” respondents whose ages ranged from 35-44 years ($M = 4.52$, $SD = 1.62$) disagreed more with this statement than respondents of other age groups.
- “I Feel comfortable with air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.” Respondents whose aged ranged from 35-44 years ($M = .98$, $SD = 1.77$) disagreed more with this statement than respondents of other age groups.
- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day” respondents aged 65 years or older ($M = 5.47$, $SD = 1.14$) agreed more with this statement than other age groups.
- “Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day” respondents aged 65 years or older ($M = 5.23$, $SD = 1.33$) agreed more with this statement than other age groups.

In sum, older respondents indicated a higher level of agreement with statements than other respondents whereas respondents aged between 35-44 years overall indicated less agreement with statements, in particular with respect to facilities (e.g., lighting, air conditioning) and safety. The higher level of agreement by older users may be due to the ‘free travel scheme’ and other services that serve people over 66 years.

[Responses by people living with vs. living without dependents](#)

Most respondents (69.8%) did not live with any dependent person (e.g. children, elderly, caring for a disabled person) nor travelled on a weekly basis with a dependent person (87.8%). There was no significant difference between genders within this group. However, people travelling with person with disabilities express a lower agreement with the statement “it is easy to get to my destination” and “I feel comfortable with the seatings” when compared to the rest of the sample.

Figure 65: Means of total responses by People living with dependents vs. not

Thus, in regard to travel services provided to people living with/caring for dependents with disabilities, improvement is needed for ease of travel and design of seating such as wheelchair access and seating, which can be limited.

Responses by people travelling with vs. without dependents

Figure 66: Means of total responses by People with travelling with dependent person vs. not

In the Figure above, the means for each question by people travelling with dependents vs. not travelling with dependents are presented. Those traveling with dependents are more dissatisfied in relation to cleanliness, lighting, and the facilities with which they can “get help” if needed. There was no significant difference between genders in this subgroup. It is important to notice that the sample of users travelling with dependent was very low (12.2%) while a larger sample declared living with dependent (30.2%) but not travelling with them.

Responses by People Who Have Faced Discrimination for Their Appearance Vs. Have Not Faced Discrimination

Most respondents (90.6%) report they have not experienced discrimination for their appearance. There were significant differences for gender, (chi square = 12.03, df = 5, p = .007), with nonbinary respondents (N = 3)⁹ reporting greater discrimination than other genders.

⁹ See: ‘Deliverable 4.1 Dataset creation’

Figure 67: Means of total responses by people who have faced discrimination (vs. not) for their appearance

In Figure above, the means for each question by people who faced discrimination for their appearance vs. have not faced discrimination. Overall, those who faced discrimination disagreed more with the statements, especially the statements related to the theme of safety and security but also in general service conditions. Specifically, respondents who faced discrimination have lower satisfaction in relation to the following: statements

- “The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 4.10, SD = 1.93$) vs ($M = 5.23, SD = 1.52$) for rest of sample.
- “I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning services available on a smartphone app or online”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 4.76, SD = 1.57$) vs ($M = 5.39, SD = 1.49$) for rest of sample.
- “Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 4.31, SD = 1.73$) vs ($M = 5.06, SD = 1.64$) for rest of sample.
- “There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 4.41, SD = 1.75$) vs ($M = 5.15, SD = 1.43$) for rest of sample.
- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 2.54, SD = 1.30$) vs ($M = 3.25, SD = 0.55$) for rest of sample, which is overall rated low.

- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 3.56$, $SD = 1.88$) vs ($M = 4.71$, $SD = 1.53$) for the rest of the sample.

In summary, those who faced discrimination indicated a lower level of agreed satisfaction in many areas than those who have not faced discrimination for their appearance.

Regression analysis

When we look at the Irish Rail data set from users’ responses using a **linear regression analysis taking as depended variable A8 (for general user satisfaction with the service)** the variables that become relevant in the linear regression model obtained through a stepwise regression approach are:

The results of stepwise analysis on linear regression on the prediction of general satisfaction highlighted salient characteristics such as A3 (“Operational hours “), A4 (“travel information”), A6 (“travel ticketing”), A9 (“travel requirements in terms of time, price, security”), B3 (“cleanliness and maintenance”), B5 (“facility and service availability within the station”, this may be because we are tackling longer distance train services probably), B9 (easy to get to destination by walking or intermodality), B10 (“feeling safe all times of the day”), while in the demographic characteristics significant variables are “travelling with a dependent person” and “Having a chronic illness/disability”).

The models obtained through the AIC stepwise approach in R is reported in the tables below.

Table 27: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach to predict 'travel satisfaction'

Predictors	travel satisfaction		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	0.97	0.27 – 1.67	0.007
operational hrs	0.09	-0.01 – 0.18	0.064
travel infos station	0.13	0.02 – 0.23	0.020
travel ticketing	-0.07	-0.17 – 0.03	0.163
travel satisfaction time, security	0.39	0.30 – 0.48	<0.001
travel to work satisfaction	0.40	0.31 – 0.50	<0.001
accessibility station	-0.07	-0.17 – 0.03	0.145
cleanliness	0.07	-0.02 – 0.17	0.133
facilities	-0.11	-0.20 – -0.02	0.017
travelling with dep	-0.35	-0.77 – 0.08	0.112
chronic illness or not	0.35	-0.14 – 0.84	0.162
Observations	334		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.505 / 0.489		

Gender is not a significant variable in respect to general satisfaction, however it became a slightly more significant predictor if the variable to be predicted was the satisfaction with the actual capacity to travel to work (A10).

Table 28: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach to predict ‘travel to work satisfaction’

travel to work satisfaction			
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	1.49	0.79 – 2.18	<0.001
travel satisfaction time, security	0.37	0.27 – 0.47	<0.001
value for money	0.13	0.04 – 0.23	0.005
facilities	0.10	-0.00 – 0.21	0.059
parent facilities	-0.12	-0.24 – 0.01	0.068
ventilation A/C	0.09	-0.03 – 0.20	0.147
comfort with space	-0.10	-0.21 – 0.01	0.079
walking from station	0.19	0.08 – 0.30	0.001
safe access and parking	0.12	0.02 – 0.22	0.014
safe belonging	0.11	-0.01 – 0.24	0.076
cctv	-0.13	-0.27 – 0.02	0.083
get help	-0.09	-0.20 – 0.02	0.116
Observations	334		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.363 / 0.341		

Table 29: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach to predict ‘easy to get destination’

Predictors	easy to get to dest		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	2.08	1.34 – 2.82	<0.001
frequency service	0.20	0.12 – 0.28	<0.001
travel infos station	0.10	-0.01 – 0.22	0.075
announcements	0.09	-0.02 – 0.20	0.123
signs	0.08	-0.03 – 0.18	0.158
travel satisfaction time, security	0.13	0.06 – 0.21	0.001
cleanliness	-0.07	-0.16 – 0.02	0.106
walking from station	0.22	0.13 – 0.30	<0.001
safe belonging	0.06	-0.03 – 0.16	0.164
get help	-0.09	-0.18 – -0.00	0.048
evacuation	-0.13	-0.24 – -0.01	0.027
environment	0.17	0.02 – 0.32	0.027
time	0.00	-0.00 – 0.01	0.161
Observations	334		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.350 / 0.326		

Interim Conclusion for Irish Rail sample in use case I

In conclusion, preliminary findings of the user survey for this northern European rail service provider indicate that most people are satisfied with the level of service. Specifically, the main highlights are:

- The results of stepwise analysis on linear regression on the prediction of general satisfaction highlighted salient characteristics such as A3 (“Operational hours “), A4 (“travel information”), A6 (“travel ticketing”), A9 (“travel requirements in terms of time, price, security”), B3 (“cleanliness and maintenance”), B5 (“facility and service availability within the station”, this may be because we are tackling longer distance train services probably), B9 (easy to get to destination by walking or intermodality), B10 (“feeling safe all times of the day”), while in the demographic characteristics significant variables are “travelling with a dependent person” and “Having a chronic illness/disability”)
- The age group between 35-44 years seems to more critical of the service provided than other age groups. This may also be because of higher demand and family responsibilities

experienced by the people in this age group such as caring responsibilities associated with young children.

- There are discrepancies and disagreements regarding fare discounts and pricing, as well as safety and security for certain demographics (gender being a relevant variable, with women tending to feel less safe than men).
- One statement that has consistently rated lower than others is “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, showing a lack of specific facilities for parents.
- Users that have experienced discrimination due to their appearance tend to have lower satisfaction in all aspects of the service.
- Users from rural areas tend to have higher satisfaction than users from urban and suburban areas, possibly due to being older (availing of free travel scheme) and travelling for non-work purposes.
- Gender is not a significant variable in respect to general satisfaction, however it became a slightly more significant predictor if the variable to be predicted was the satisfaction with the actual capacity to travel to work (variable A10).
These issues are being further explored in interviews and focus groups whose preliminary results will be discussed in Deliverable 4.2.

Use case I FGC

Overview and descriptive statistics

This report covers the responses for FGC on use Case I of those who meet the following criteria:

- Completed questionnaire
- Participants who identified as male, female, transsexual female, non-binary and/or prefer not to say.

Initial demographics of the survey included transsexual male in the list/selection of identity, however, collected data had no participants in this category. Thus, for this report the analysed criteria of response examine participants as meets the above asserted criteria.

A total of 443 rail transport users for Line 1 and Line 2 (155 males, 284 females, 1 transsexual female, 1 nonbinary and 2 prefer not to say) whose ages ranged from 18 years to above 75 years were included. Most respondents were Spanish/Catalan (72.2%), white (69.5%), married or in stable relationship (45.1%), heterosexual (92.3%), earning less than €20,999 (66.8%) and living in an urban area (81%). The majority also did not have any dependents (75.8%), did not travel with dependents on weekly basis (91.2%), and were in paid full-time employment (66.4%).

The Southern European operator asked us specifically to differentiate user preferences between two lines. Correlated to the set of stations selected specifically for Line 1: Llobregat - Anoia Line and Line 2: Barcelona – Vallès Line. There is evidence that male and female respondents’ needs are generally being met alongside train facilities and services accessibility by this public transport service on Line 1 and Line 2. Nonetheless, Line 1 seems to report lower travel satisfaction scoring throughout the categories.

Table 30: Southern European rail overall frequency breakdown Line 1 and 2

	Male	Female	Transexual Male	transexual Female	Non-Binary	Prefer not to say
Overall Train Line	155 (35%)	284 (64.1%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.2%)	1 (0.2%)	2 (0.5%)
Line 1: Llobregat - Anoia Line	66	96	0	0	1	0
Line 2: Barcelona - Vallès Line	89	188	0	1	0	2

Table 31: Frequency and percentage data of age and living area demographics by gender

Line 1: Llobregat - Anoia Line	Male	Female	Transexual Female	Non-Binary	Prefer not to say
Participant Sample	66 (40.5%)	96 (58.9%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.6%)	0 (0%)
AGE					
18-24 years	27 (40.9%)	31 (32.3%)	-	-	-
25-34 years	15 (22.7%)	22 (22.9%)	-	-	-
35-44 years	13 (19.7%)	21 (21.9%)	-	1 (100%)	-
45-54 years	4 (6.1%)	10 (10.4%)	-	-	-
55-64 years	6 (9.1%)	10 (10.4%)	-	-	-
65-74 years	1 (1.5%)	1 (1.0%)	-	-	-
75 years or more	-	1 (1.0%)	-	-	-
AREA					
Rural	10 (15.2%)	27 (28.2%)	-	-	-
Suburban	10 (15.2%)	9 (9.4%)	-	-	-
Urban	46 (69.7%)	60 (62.5%)	-	1 (100%)	-

Line 2: Barcelona - Vallès Line	Male	Female	Transexual Female	Non-Binary	Prefer not to say
Participant Sample	89 (31.8%)	188 (67.1%)	1 (0.4%)	0 (0%)	2 (0.7%)
AGE					
18-24 years	19 (21.3%)	25 (13.3%)	-	-	-
25-34 years	34 (38.2%)	50 (26.6%)	-	-	1 (50.0%)
35-44 years	11 (12.4%)	47 (25.0%)	1 (100%)	-	-
45-54 years	18 (20.2%)	39 (20.7%)	-	-	1 (50.0%)

55-64 years	4 (4.5%)	22 (11.7%)	-	-	-
65-74 years	2 (2.2%)	4 (2.1%)	-	-	-
75 years or more	1 (1.1%)	1 (0.5%)	-	-	-
AREA					
Rural	4 (4.5 %)	7 (3.7%)	-	-	-
Suburban	5 (5.6%)	12 (6.4%)	-	-	-
Urban	80 (89.9%)	169 (89.9%)	1 (100%)	-	2 (100%)

Table 32: Frequency and percentage data of income and marital/family status demographic by gender

Line 1: Llobregat - Anoia Line	Male	Female	Transexual Female	Non-Binary	Prefer not to say
Participant Sample	61(41.5%)	85(57.8%)	0 (0%)	1 (0.7%)	0 (0%)
Salary Income					
No Income	14 (23.0%)	15 (17.6%)	-	-	-
Less than 10,999€	18 (29.5%)	27 (31.8%)	-	-	-
11,000 – 20,999€	15 (24.6%)	37 (43.5%)	-	1 (100%)	-
21,000 – 30,999€	8 (13.1%)	3 (3.5%)	-	-	-
31,000 – 40,999€	6 (9.8%)	1 (1.2%)	-	-	-
41,000 – 50,999€	-	1 (1.2%)	-	-	-
51,000 – 70,999€	-	1 (1.2%)	-	-	-
More than 70,000€	-	-	-	-	-
Prefer not to say	-	-	-	-	-
Marital/Family Status					
Married/Civil Partnership-Heterosexual	25 (41.0%)	34 (40.5)	-	-	-
Married/Civil Partnership-Same Sex	-	1 (1.2%)	-	-	-
Cohabiting	14 (23.0%)	25 (29.8%)	-	1 (100.0%)	-
Lone Parent	13(21.3%)	16 (19.0%)	-	-	-
Single	9 (14.8%)	8 (9.5%)	-	-	-
Prefer not to say	-	-	-	-	-
Living with dependant in family unit (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled)					
No	47 (77.0%)	64 (75.3%)	-	1 (100%)	-

School Age Children (5-16 years)	7 (11.5%)	8 (9.4%)	-	-	-
Preschool and School Age Children (under 5years)	3 (4.9%)	7 (8.2%)	-	-	-
Disabled Person	-	4 (4.7%)	-	-	-
Elderly	4 (6.6%)	2 (2.4%)	-	-	-

Line 2: Barcelona – Vallès Line	Male	Female	Transexual Female	Non-Binary	Prefer not to say
Participant Sample	87 (32.3%)	179 (66.5%)	1 (0.4%)	0 (%)	2 (0.7%)
Salary Income					
No Income	6 (6.9%)	9 (5.0%)	-	-	-
Less than 10,999€	11 (12.6%)	26 (14.5%)	-	-	-
11,000 – 20,999€	38 (43.7%)	78 (43.6%)	-	-	1 (50%)
21,000 – 30,999€	16 (18.4%)	37 (20.7%)	-	-	-
31,000 – 40,999€	2 (2.3%)	8 (4.5%)	-	-	-
41,000 – 50,999€	4 (4.6%)	3 (1.7%)	-	-	1 (50%)
51,000 – 70,999€	2 (2.3%)	-	-	-	-
More than 70,000€	-	1 (0.6%)	-	-	-
Prefer not to say	8 (9.2%)	17 (9.5%)	1 (100%)	-	-
Marital/Family Status					
Married/Civil Partnership-Heterosexual	37 (42.5%)	90 (50.6%)	1 (100%)	-	1 (50%)
Married/Civil Partnership-Same Sex	-	1 (0.6%)	-	-	-
Cohabiting	40 (46.0%)	56 (31.5%)	-	-	1 (50%)
Lone Parent	1 (1.1%)	14 (7.9%)	-	-	-
Single	8 (9.2%)	14 (7.9%)	-	-	-
Prefer not to say	1 (1.1%)	3 (1.7%)	-	-	-
Living with dependant in family unit (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled)					
No	66 (75.9%)	141 (78.8%)	1 (100%)	-	1 (50%)
School Age Children (5-16 years)	13 (14.9%)	21 (11.7%)	-	-	-

Preschool and School Children (under 5 years)	4 (4.6%)	7 (3.9%)	-	-	-
Disabled Person	-	1 (0.6%)	-	-	-
Elderly	4 (4.6%)	9 (5.0%)	-	-	1 (50%)

Users from line 1 seem to have longer travel times (40.3 minutes average) than line 2 (35.7 minutes average). Likewise, both lines recorded a lower income category on average, lower education, younger age (Line 1 - 18 years to 44 years and Line 2 – 18 years and 54 years) in average and associated more with a rural or suburban environment.

Overall, the respondents are quite a homogenous group in terms of ethnicity, race, religion, sexuality, education etc., and have minimal responsibilities in terms of caring for dependents. The rail users' similar characteristics may indicate that public transport appeals best to only certain sectors of the population (e.g., single employed with no dependents). However, it is also important to note that due to collecting data during the busiest times on weekdays, there is the possibility that commuters were over sampled. DIAMOND collected interviews from respondents who do not use public transport frequently in order to provide further insight into the key findings, this should be reported in a further version of Deliverable 4.2.

The below correlation matrix shows that there is some limited correlation across some variables that can be grouped together in topics such as 1) comfort/accessibility (Accessibility, Seating, Facilities, A/C ventilation, comfort with space, lighting etc.) 2) safety (evacuation, get help, feel safe, safe belonging) and 3) capability to meet service needs such as (travel to work, announcements, frequency of services, operational hours, etc.).

Considering the results of the correlation matrix it makes sense to organize the responses in three macro areas:

- **Capable of meeting required needs;** ability to travel in an appropriately designed transport system meeting basic expectations and being environmentally sound.
- **Accessible;** ability to access activities and services that people have reason to value; accessible to all groups also in terms of design and comfort provided, e.g., those with children, and in terms of fares and costs for those with lower income, including distribution of costs and benefits.
- **Safety and Security;** ability to travel safely and securely for all type of users.

Figure 68: Correlation Matrix for Use case I FGC dataset

With accessibility, question – “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them” is seen to be rated the lowest across the statements regardless of categories.

Factor analysis

For the next step of the analysis, we now group questions into factors, or groups of questions that tend to follow similar patterns. This will allow us to get an overview on which demographic characteristics affect satisfaction with respect to different aspects of the service.

The graph below (scree plot) shows the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors. Based on this graph, we chose 3 as number of factors for this dataset, as it produces remarkably lower values than 2, and only slightly higher than with 4. It provides a good balance producing acceptable results with a reasonable number of factors.

Figure 69: Use case I – FGC. Scree plot showing the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors

We now show the resulting factors, that group the questionnaire’s questions in three groups. We attributed a name to each factor based on manual inspection of the questions, to identify the main topic behind each of them.

Factor 0 – Safety and comfort

- The cleanliness and maintenance of the environment (station and the train) are adequate.
- There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.
- I Feel comfortable with air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.
- I feel comfortable with the personal space available to me at stations and in carriages.
- At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles.
- When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.
- Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.
- There are enough CCTV systems and other security measures visible to make me feel safe
- If needed, I am satisfied that I could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g., security staff, emergency phone number).
- I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).

Factor 1 – Capability to address service needs

- It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service
- The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs
- Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs
- I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station
- The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations) at this station meet my travel needs
- I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning services available on a smartphone app or online
- Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips
- Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security
- I can easily travel to my work place using public transport, if this applies to you
- Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and better value for money than traveling by private car
- I can easily get to my destination from the station by walking or using other means of transport

Factor 2 - Accessibility

- I am satisfied that all services, exits, and platforms are clearly signposted
- Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts, rail etc)
- There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station.
- Facilities such as seating, backrests, and restrooms are adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities
- The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs)

Demographic differences by factor

We now look at how each demographic variable influence user satisfaction with respect to each set of questions (i.e., with respect to each factor), and show the corresponding differences with boxplots. We report only relevant results for cases in which we found evidence of statistically significant differences according to an ANOVA test and omit all the other combinations of factors and demographic variables.

Factor 0: Safety and comfort

Figure 70: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Station.

Figure 71: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Environment.

Figure 72.: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by whether respondents are affected by a chronic illness.

A determinant feature to predict user satisfaction with respect to the questions in factor 0 (related to security) was the station, with high variability among stations.

We further observe that urban and foreigner users tend to be more satisfied with security and comfort, while Spanish citizens (data not shown), users from rural areas, users suffering for chronic illnesses and users who reported experiencing discrimination (data not shown) are generally less satisfied.

Factor 1: Capability to address service needs

Figure 73: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Academic formation.

Figure 74: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by whether respondents live with some dependent person.

Figure 75: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Nationality.

The categories of users that seem to be more affected by issues related to the efficiency of the service are users living with disabled dependents, Spanish citizens and people who experienced discrimination.

Factor 2: Accessibility

Figure 76: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by Station.

Figure 77: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by Environment.

Figure 78: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by whether respondents live with some dependent person.

Accessibility issues seem to affect especially users living with disabled dependents, users from rural areas and Spanish citizens (data not shown).

Responses for different types of demographic characteristics

We now take a more in-depth look at how each demographic characteristic affects satisfaction on specific statements from the survey and we also examine them differentiating between the two lines to see if significant differences could be highlighted also in relation to some element that are specific to the characteristics of the lines and connectivity they offer.

Responses by Gender in each Line

Significant differences across genders were found for the following statements that related to the capability of addressing service needs:

- “The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs”, Line 2 female respondents (M = 5.84, SD = 1.53) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 male respondents (M = 4.91, SD = 1.80)
- “Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs”, Line 2 female respondents (M = 5.71, SD = 1.68) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 male respondents (M = 4.80, SD = 2.07).
- “The availability of travel information and directions (e.g., maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations) at this station meet my travel needs”, Line 2 male respondents (M = 5.93, SD = 1.31) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 female respondents (M = 4.67, SD = 1.79).
- “I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning needs that are met using a smartphone app or online platform”, Line 2 male respondents (M = 5.44, SD = 1.97) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 female respondents (M = 4.97, SD = 1.68).
- “Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and good value for money than traveling by private car”, Line 2 male respondents (M = 5.73, SD = 1.61) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 female respondents (M = 4.76, SD = 1.91).

It is important to note that there was an insufficient number of responses from transsexual female (N =1), nonbinary (N =1) and prefer not to say (N =2) in the sample. Thus, there is not enough evidence in this group to conclude a representation in the total analysed response.

Figure 79: Means of total female & male responses (line 1 and 2) for questions related to ‘Capable of Meeting Required Needs’.

For accessibility related variables differences across genders were found for the following statements:

- “The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs)”, Line 2 female respondents ($M = 6.00$, $SD = 1.29$) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 female ($M = 4.92$, $SD = 1.72$).
- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, Line 2 male respondents ($M = 5.46$, $SD = 2.45$) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 male respondents ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 2.53$).

Figure 80: Means of total female & male responses (line 1 and 2) for questions related to ‘satisfaction with Accessibility’.

Similarly, for satisfaction related to safety and security statements the following differences across genders were found:

- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day”, Line 2 male respondents (M = 6.02, SD = 1.27) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 female respondents (M = 4.80, SD = 1.90).
- “Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day”, Line 2 male respondents (M = 5.94, SD = 1.23) agreed more with this statement than Line 1 female respondents (M = 4.86, SD = 1.82).

Figure 81: Means of total female & male responses (line 1 and 2) for questions related to ‘Safety and Security’

As is visible from the charts there are stronger differences in terms of user experiences in Safety and Security across the two lines than across different genders in the users of the lines. Users of Line 1 are in general less satisfied with safety and security than those using Line 2. In general, female users are always expressing lower average responses in terms of all the categories related to safety and security than the males on the same line. This difference is very significant for Line 1 where female users feel significantly less safe when arriving and leaving the station than males on the same line.

Responses by Area (Urban Vs. Suburban Vs. Rural)

In the Figures below, the means for each question by the area in which respondents live (Urban, Suburban, Rural) are presented. There is evidence that all respondents’ needs are generally being met by the organisation. However, analysis indicated that there were significant differences for living areas across several statements.

Figure 82: Means of total area responses (line 1 and 2) for questions related to ‘Capable of Meeting Required Needs’.

Line 1 - capacity to address service needs. The key differences across the urban rural and suburban environments for Line 1 on capacity to address service needs can be found for the following statements:

- “It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service”, respondents in Rural (M = 5.84, SD = 1.50) and Urban areas (M = 5.83, SD = 1.37) agreed more with this statement than respondents in suburban areas (M = 5.21, SD = 2.04).
- “I can easily travel to my workplace using public transport, if this applies to you”, respondents in Rural (M = 5.22, SD = 1.77) and Urban areas (M = 5.53, SD = 1.88) agreed more with this statement than respondents in suburban areas (M = 4.79, SD = 2.53).
- “The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations,) at this station meet my travel needs”, respondents in Urban areas (M = 5.07, SD = 1.74) agreed more with this statement than respondents in Rural (M = 4.46, SD = 1.82) and suburban areas (M = 4.63, SD = 1.71).
- “Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and good value for money than traveling by private car”, respondents in Urban areas (M = 5.30, SD = 1.94) agreed more with this statement than respondents in Rural (M = 4.35, SD = 1.86) and suburban areas (M = 4.68, SD = 1.97).

Line 2 - capacity to address service needs: The key differences across the urban rural and suburban environments for Line 2 can be found for the following statements:

- “It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service”, agreement with this statement across areas differs with respondents in Urban areas (M = 6.06, SD = 1.34), Rural (M = 6.64, SD = 0.93) and suburban areas (M = 5.41, SD = 2.18).
- For the statement: “I can easily travel to my workplace using public transport, if this applies to you”, respondents in Rural (M = 7.00, SD = 1.61) and Urban areas (M = 6.05, SD = 1.55) agreed more with this statement than respondents in suburban areas (M = 5.94, SD = 1.75).
- “I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning needs that are met using a smartphone app or online platform”, respondents in Urban areas (M = 5.27, SD = 2.03) agreed more with this statement than respondents in Rural (M = 6.09, SD = 2.39) and suburban areas (M = 5.06, SD = 1.92).
- “At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles”, respondents in Urban areas (M = 6.11, SD = 1.88) agreed more with this statement than respondents in Rural (M = 5.09, SD = 2.46) and suburban areas (M = 5.24, SD = 2.02).

Figure 83: Means of total area responses (line 1 and 2) for questions related to ‘satisfaction with Accessibility’.

Line 1 - accessibility. For accessibility related variables differences across urban, suburban and rural environments in line 1 were found for the following statements:

- “There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station”, respondents in Urban areas (M = 5.76, SD = 1.45) agreed more with this statement than respondents in Rural (M = 4.92, SD = 2.06) and suburban areas (M = 5.11, SD = 1.56).
- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, agreement with this statement across areas differs with respondents in Urban areas (M = 4.58, SD = 2.46), Rural (M = 4.05, SD = 2.34) and suburban areas (M = 3.63, SD = 3.04).

Line 2 - accessibility: Similarly, for accessibility related variables differences across urban, suburban and rural environments in line 2 were found for the following statement:

- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, respondents in Suburban areas (M = 4.41, SD = 2.67) and Urban areas (M = 5.31, SD = 2.48) agreed more with this statement than respondents in Rural (M = 2.55, SD = 2.41).

Figure 84: Means of total area responses (line 1 and 2) for questions related to ‘Safety and Security’

Line 1 - safety and security. Similarly for safety and security related variables differences across urban, suburban and rural environments in line 1 were found for the following statement:

- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day”, respondents in Urban areas (M = 5.40, SD = 1.58) agreed more with this statement than respondents in rural areas (M = 4.38, SD = 2.07).

Line 2 - safety and security. For safety and security related variables, differences across urban, suburban and rural environments in line 2 were found for the following statement:

- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day”, respondents in suburban (M = 6.29, SD = 1.45) and Urban areas (M = 5.85, SD = 1.43) agreed more with this statement than respondents in rural areas (M = 4.64, SD = 2.45).
- “Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day”, respondents in suburban (M = 6.29, SD = 0.99) and Urban areas (M = 5.79, SD = 1.47) agreed more with this statement than respondents in rural areas (M = 4.45, SD = 2.10).

In sum, respondents living in rural areas indicated a lower level of satisfaction with respect to safety and security than respondents living in urban and suburban areas.

Responses by people living/travelling with dependents vs without dependents.

Figure 85: Means of female & male responses (line 1 and 2) by dependants for questions related to ‘Capable of Meeting Required Needs’.

Line 1 - capability to address service needs. When considering users “travelling with dependents” on Line 1 the following differences were found across the statements related to capability to address service needs:

- “The availability of travel information and directions (e.g., maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations,)” female respondent with dependants (M = 6.38, SD = 0.74) agreed more with the statement than female respondents without dependants (M = 4.57, SD = 1.75).
- “At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles” female respondent with dependants (M = 6.75, SD = 1.75) and male respondents with dependants (M = 6.67, SD = 2.08) agreed more with the statement than female respondents without dependants (M = 5.17, SD = 1.94) and male respondents without dependants (M = 5.49, SD = 1.66).

Line 2 - capability to address service needs. When considering users “travelling with dependents” on Line 1 the following differences were found across the statements related to capability to address services needs:

- “Public transport fulfils your daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security” male respondents with dependants (M = 6.14, SD = 1.11), female respondents without dependants (M = 6.16, SD = 1.18), male respondents without dependants (M = 6.04, SD = 1.23) agree more with the statement than female respondent with dependants (M = 5.35, SD = 1.90).
- “Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and good value for money than traveling by private car” female respondents with dependants (M = 5.94, SD = 2.30), female respondents without dependants (M = 5.71, SD = 1.61), male respondents without dependants (M = 5.62, SD = 1.61) agree less with the statement than male respondent with dependants (M = 7.00, SD = 1).

Figure 86: Means of female & male responses (line 1 and 2) by dependants for questions related to ‘satisfaction with Accessibility’.

Line 1 – accessibility. When considering users “travelling with dependants” on Line 1 the following differences were found across the statements related to accessibility: “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them” male respondent with dependants ($M = 6.67$, $SD = 2.52$) agreed more with the statement than female respondents without dependants ($M = 4.48$, $SD = 2.46$) and male respondents without dependants ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 2.49$).

Line 2 – accessibility. When considering users “travelling with dependants” on Line 2 the following differences were found across the statements related to accessibility: “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them” male respondent with dependants ($M = 6.43$, $SD = 2.44$) agreed more with the statement than female respondents without dependants ($M = 4.98$, $SD = 2.90$).

Line 1 & Line 2 – Safety and Security Most respondents (75.8%) did not live with any dependent person (e.g., children, elderly, caring for disabled person) nor traveled on a weekly basis with a dependent person (91.2%). Maybe for this reason there was no significant difference in relation to Safety and Security between people travelling or not with dependent in the observed sample.

Responses by People with Chronic Illness Vs. No Chronic Illness

Most respondents (97.4%) did not have a chronic illness with only 2.6% of respondents stating they had a chronic illness (including mental illness) or physical, learning or sensory disability that affected their capacity to use public transport. In the figures below the means for each question by people with chronic illness vs. no chronic illness are presented. Again, there is evidence that all respondents' needs are generally being met by the organisation, however there is general disagreement with the statement: "there are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them". There was no significant difference between population on line 1 and line 2.

Line 1 participant respondents with chronic illness (including mental illness) or physical, learning or sensory disability are generally seen to agree less with statements across Capable of Meeting Required Needs, Accessibility and Safety and Security in comparison to Line 2 responses.

Figure 87: Means of total responses (line 1 and 2) by people with chronic illness vs. no chronic illness Capable of Meeting Required Needs'

Figure 88: Means of total responses (line 1 and 2) by people with chronic illness vs. no chronic illness for questions related to 'satisfaction with Accessibility'.

Figure 89: Means of total responses (line 1 and 2) by people with chronic illness vs. no chronic illness for questions related to 'Safety and Security'

Responses by Age

In Figure below, the means for each question by Age are presented. Correlation analysis indicated that there were significant age differences across a number of statements and we differentiate age groups within female and male responders.

Female Response Line 1 & 2

Figure 90: Means of total female responses (line 1 and 2) by Age for questions related to ‘Capable of Meeting Required Needs’.

Female responses Line 1. The key differences across age groups for Line 1 on capacity to address service needs can be found for the following statements:

- “It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service”, respondents whose ages ranged from 25-34 years (M = 4.95, SD = 2.19) agree less with this statement than other aged respondents.

- “Public transport fulfils your daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.70$, $SD = 2.21$) agreed less with the statement than other aged respondents.
- “Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.40$, $SD = 2.37$) agreed less with the statement than other aged respondents.
- “I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.20$, $SD = 2.20$) agreed less with the statement than other aged respondents.
- “I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning needs that are met using a smartphone app or online platform” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years ($M = 6.10$, $SD = 1.73$) agreed more with the statement than respondents whose ages ranged from 18-24 years ($M = 4.42$, $SD = 1.57$) years, 25-34 years ($M = 4.95$, $SD = 1.62$), 35-44 years ($M = 5.14$, $SD = 1.98$), 55-64 years ($M = 5.00$, $SD = 1.05$).

Female responses Line 2 The key differences across age groups for Line 2 on capacity to address service needs can be found for the following statement:

- “I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning needs that are met using a smartphone app or online platform” respondents whose ages ranged from 18-24 years ($M = 4.96$, $SD = 2.13$) agreed less with the statement than respondents of other ages.

Figure 91: Means of total female responses (line 1 and 2) by Age for questions related to ‘satisfaction with Accessibility’.

Female responses Line 1 The key differences across age groups for Line 1 on accessibility can be found for the following statements:

- “There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years (M = 4.70, SD = 2.21) agreed less with the statement than respondents of other ages.
- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years (M = 3.40, SD = 2.72) agreed less with the statement than respondents in ascending order 18-24 years (M = 4.39, SD = 2.68) and 25-34 years (M = 4.29, SD = 2.65), then 35-44 years (M = 5.24, SD = 2.39) and 45-54 years (M = 5.00, SD = 2.26)
- “I Feel comfortable with air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years (M = 4.20, SD = 1.81) agreed less with the statement than respondents of other ages

Female responses Line 2. The key differences across age groups for Line 2 on accessibility can be found for the following statement:

- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them” respondents whose ages ranged from 18-24 years (M = 5.24, SD = 2.82) agreed more with the statement than respondents in descending order 25-34 years (M = 5.04,

SD = 2.28) and 55-64years (M = 5.18, SD = 2.72), then 35-44years (M = 4.84, SD = 2.45) and 45-54years (M = 4.82, SD = 2.94)

Figure 92: Means of total female responses (line 1 and 2) by Age for questions related to ‘Safety and Security’

Female responses Line 1. The key differences across age groups for Line 1 on safety and security for Female responders can be found for the following statement:

- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years (M = 4.10, SD = 2.33) agreed less with the statement than respondents of other ages.

Female Responses Line 2. The key differences across age groups for Line 1 on safety and security can be found for the following statements:

- “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.” respondents whose ages ranged from 35-44 years (M = 5.94, SD = 1.31) and 45-54 years (M = 5.92 SD = 1.49) agreed more with the statement than respondents from other ages.
- “Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.” respondents whose ages ranged from 35-44 years (M = 6.11, SD = 0.96) agreed more with

the statement than respondents whose ages ranged from 25-34 years (M = 5.66, SD = 1.88), 45-54 years (M = 5.64, SD = 1.74), 18-24 years (M = 5.44, SD = 1.53) and 55-64 years (M = 5.32, SD = 1.91).

- “If needed, you could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g., security staff, emergency phone number).” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 (M = 5.36, SD = 1.98) agreed less with the statement than respondents whose ages ranged from 18-24 years (M = 5.60, SD = 2.02), 25-34 years (M = 5.94, SD = 1.45), 35-44 years (M = 5.85, SD = 1.44) and 55-64 years (M = 5.55, SD = 2.09).

Male Response Line 1 & 2. The male population in different age groups mostly align with the female population with the exception of safety and security statements.

Figure 93: Means of total male responses (line 1 and 2) by Age for questions related to ‘Capable of Meeting Required Needs’.

Male responders Line 1

The key differences across age groups for Line 1 on capacity to address service needs can be found for the following statements and are the same as the one highlighted for the female population:

- “It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service.” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.83$, $SD = 1.94$) agreed less with the statement than respondents of other ages range.
- “Public transport fulfils your daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.50$, $SD = 2.35$) years and 45-54 years ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 2.45$) agreed less with the statement than respondents from other ages.
- “The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 2.48$) agreed less with the statement than respondents of other age range.
- “Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs.” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 2.28$) than respondents of other age range.
- “The availability of travel information and directions (e.g., maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations,) at this station meet my travel needs” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 2.61$) than respondents of other age range.

Male responders Line 2 The key differences across age groups for Line 2 on capacity to address service needs can be found for the following statement which is the same highlighted for the female population:

- “*I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning needs that are met using a smartphone app or online platform.*” respondents whose ages ranged from 18-24 years ($M = 6.21$, $SD = 2.12$) and 55-64 years ($M = 7.25$, $SD = 2.06$) agreed the most with the statement than respondents whose ages ranged from 35-44 years ($M = 4.36$, $SD = 1.63$), 45-54 years ($M = 5.06$, $SD = 1.63$) and 25-34 years ($M = 5.32$, $SD = 2.00$).

Figure 94: Means of total male responses (line 1 and 2) by Age for questions related to ‘satisfaction with Accessibility’.

Male Responses Line 1. The key differences across age groups for Line 1 on accessibility can be found for the following statements (that are the same ones found for the female populations):

- “Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts, rail etc).” respondents whose ages ranged from 55-64 years (M = 4.83, SD = 2.32) agreed the least with the statement than respondents of other age range.
- “The facility for comfort such as seating, backrests, restrooms is adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years (M = 4.00, SD = 2.16) agreed the least with the statement than respondents of other age range.
- “The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs...)” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years (M = 3.75, SD = 2.06) agreed the least with the statement than respondents of other age range.
- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 (M = 2.50, SD = 2.38) years and 55-64 (M = 3.30, SD = 1.76) years agreed less with the statement than respondents of other age range

Male populations Line 2. The key differences across age groups for Line 2 on accessibility can be found for the following statement (that is the same one found for the female populations): “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 ($M = 4.11$, $SD = 2.14$) years and 55-64 ($M = 3.75$, $SD = 3.20$) years agreed less with the statement than respondents of other age range

Figure 95: Means of total male responses (line 1 and 2) by Age for questions related to ‘Safety and Security’

Male responses Line 1. When considering the variables related to safety and security the female and male populations of different ages differ. For the male population the only significant differences found were for the statements:

- “Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 2.16$) agreed the least with the statement than respondents of other age range.
- “There are enough CCTV systems and other security measures visible to warranty my safety” respondents whose ages ranged from 45-54 years ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 2.16$) agreed the least with the statement than respondents of other age range.

No differences across ages in safety and security was found for Line 2.

In summary, there were mixed results for age across gender and across Line 1 and Line 2. For line 1, overall men and women aged between 55-64 years indicated a lower level of agreement across many of the statements in particular those regarding time, price, security, and travel information

provided. Few differences existed on Line 2 – except that younger groups were more satisfied with facilities provided for parents and younger people (18-24 years) less satisfied with online information provided.

Responses by People Who Have Faced Discrimination Vs. those who have not

Figure 96: Means of total responses by people who have faced discrimination (vs. not) for their appearance for questions related to ‘capability to address service needs’

When considering variables related to **capability to address service needs** the following differences were found:

- “Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs”, respondents who had faced discrimination (M = 4.21, SD = 2.23) disagreed more with the statement than those who had not face discrimination (M = 5.47, SD = 1.73).
- “The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations,) at this station meet my travel needs.”, respondents who had faced discrimination (M = 4.46, SD = 1.95) disagreed more with the statement than those who had not face discrimination (M = 5.57, SD = 1.62).

Figure 97: Means of total responses by people who have faced discrimination (vs. not) for their appearance for questions related to ‘Accessibility’

When considering variables related to **accessibility** the following differences were found:

- “The facility for comfort such as seating, backrests, restrooms is adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities.”, respondents who had faced discrimination (M = 4.79, SD = 1.75) disagreed more with the statement than those who had not face discrimination (M = 5.80, SD = 1.39).
- “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, respondents who had faced discrimination (M = 3.94, SD = 2.75) disagreed more with the statement than those who had not face discrimination (M = 4.94, SD = 2.54).

Figure 98: Means of total responses by people who have faced discrimination (vs. not) for their appearance for questions related to ‘Safety and Security’

When considering variables related to **safety and security**, the following difference was found: “When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.”, respondents who had faced discrimination ($M = 4.49$, $SD = 2.12$) disagreed more with the statement than those who had not faced discrimination ($M = 5.67$, $SD = 1.56$).

In summary, those who faced discrimination indicated a lower level of agreement with the statements than those who have not faced discrimination for their appearance.

Regression Analysis

When looking at the data set using a linear regression analysis with dependent variables as listed below for satisfaction, the variable that becomes relevant in the linear regression model obtained through as stepwise regression approach with results on prediction of highlighted prediction:

Survey analysis also encompassed key variable for satisfaction and perception which includes:

- I. **Determinants of Travel to work satisfaction;** Value for money, walking to destination from station, announcements and clarity about situation, frequency of service, travel to work method, travel info at station, safe access and parking, Illness, travel with mobility aid, work contract and gender.

Table 33: Extract Regression analysis using Travel to work satisfaction as dependent variable.

Predictors	travel to work satisfaction		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	0.23	-1.05 – 1.51	0.727
frequency service	0.13	0.05 – 0.22	0.002
travel infos station	-0.11	-0.21 – -0.02	0.022
announcements	0.19	0.11 – 0.28	<0.001
travel satisfaction time, security	0.11	-0.00 – 0.22	0.058
value for money	0.23	0.15 – 0.31	<0.001
travel with mobility aid	0.58	0.05 – 1.11	0.031
walking from station	0.35	0.23 – 0.47	<0.001
safe access and parking	-0.08	-0.16 – -0.00	0.044
illness	-1.00	-1.77 – -0.23	0.011
work contract	-0.10	-0.19 – -0.01	0.031
ethnicity	0.13	-0.05 – 0.32	0.160
sex	0.18	0.00 – 0.36	0.046
travel to work method	0.22	0.08 – 0.35	0.002
Observations	425		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.438 / 0.420		

- II. **Determinants of General travel satisfaction;** Value for money, announcements and clarity about situation, walking to destination from station, comfort with space, frequency of service, safety of belongings, travel to work method, safe access and parking, seating, ventilation A/C, age (older age are somewhat less satisfied), education (users with higher education levels are somewhat less satisfied).

Table 34: Extract Regression analysis using General Travel Satisfaction as dependent variable.

Predictors	travel satisfaction		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	0.79	-0.29 – 1.88	0.151
frequency service	0.10	0.02 – 0.18	0.014
announcements	0.36	0.28 – 0.44	<0.001
travel satisfaction time, security	0.12	0.02 – 0.21	0.018
value for money	0.14	0.06 – 0.21	<0.001
travel with bags	-0.06	-0.15 – 0.02	0.151
accessibility station	-0.08	-0.19 – 0.03	0.145
seating	0.11	0.01 – 0.22	0.039
ventilation A/C	0.08	0.00 – 0.16	0.049
comfort with space	-0.17	-0.28 – -0.06	0.003
walking from station	0.17	0.06 – 0.27	0.003
safe access and parking	-0.05	-0.13 – 0.02	0.164
safe belonging	0.08	0.00 – 0.16	0.046
age	-0.12	-0.20 – -0.04	0.002
education	-0.08	-0.16 – -0.00	0.040
discrimination	0.34	-0.06 – 0.74	0.098
travel to work method	0.17	0.05 – 0.30	0.007
Observations	425		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.504 / 0.485		

III. **Determinants of the perception of ease of provided transport service to destination;** Frequency of service, walking to destination from station, announcements and clarity about situation, environment (urban, suburban or rural), travel ticketing, nationality (as announcements and info are mostly in Spanish), possibility of getting help, education and age.

Table 35: Extract Regression analysis using “ Easy to get to Destination” as dependent variable.

easy to get to dest			
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
(Intercept)	3.70	2.36 – 5.05	<0.001
frequency service	0.16	0.08 – 0.24	<0.001
announcements	0.17	0.08 – 0.26	<0.001
travel ticketing	0.09	0.01 – 0.17	0.022
value for money	0.06	-0.02 – 0.15	0.124
travel with mobility aid	0.42	-0.12 – 0.96	0.125
parent facilities	-0.07	-0.14 – 0.00	0.052
comfort with space	0.09	-0.02 – 0.20	0.112
walking from station	0.26	0.14 – 0.38	<0.001
safe access and parking	-0.06	-0.15 – 0.03	0.161
safe belonging	0.08	-0.02 – 0.17	0.131
get help	0.08	-0.01 – 0.17	0.079
evacuation	-0.12	-0.24 – -0.01	0.031
illness	-0.61	-1.42 – 0.20	0.141
environment	-0.39	-0.67 – -0.10	0.007
age	-0.07	-0.16 – 0.01	0.096
education	-0.09	-0.18 – -0.01	0.036
nationality	-0.60	-0.90 – -0.30	<0.001
ethnicity	0.25	0.05 – 0.46	0.015
Observations	425		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.331 / 0.302		

Interim Conclusion for FGC sample in use case I

In conclusion, preliminary findings of the user survey for this Southern European rail service provider indicate that most people are satisfied with the level of service. Here below a short extract of some key interesting findings:

- Overall data collected for line 1 and 2 had less than 1% of data collected for participants with ages ranging 65 years and above.
- One statement that has consistently rated lower than others is “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, showing a lack of specific facilities for parents.
- Key fairness characteristics that determine the passengers satisfaction with the level of services offered Value for money, announcements and clarity about situation, walking to destination from station, comfort with space, frequency of service, safety of belongings, travel to work method, safe access and parking, seating, ventilation A/C, age (older age are somewhat less satisfied), education (users with higher education levels are somewhat less satisfied) and environment (people coming from suburban and rural environment are less likely to be satisfied).
- Spanish citizens express in general lower levels of satisfaction
- With respect to safety, users from rural areas and people who suffered discrimination are generally less satisfied.

Use case I - ZTM (Eastern European case study)

Overview and descriptive statistics

This report covers the responses of those who meet the criteria below;

- Participants who identified as male, female, transsexual male, nonbinary and/or prefer not to say.
- Completed questionnaire

A total of 472 rail transport users (196 males, 237 females, 1 transexual male¹⁰, 6 nonbinary and 32 prefer not to say) whose ages ranged from 18 years to under 75 years were included. Most respondents were white (89.4%), married or in stable heterosexual relationship (49.6%), heterosexual (76.9%), earning less than €20,999 (54.2%) or had no income (11.2%) and living in an urban area (72%). The majority also did not have any dependents (68.2%), did not travel with dependents on weekly basis (83.5%), and were in paid full-time employment (73.3%).

¹⁰ Due to small sample size, data was noted but excluded from presentation (n=1)

Table 36: Frequency and percentage data of age and living area demographics by gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non Binary (%)	Prefer not to say	Total (100%)
	196 (41.6)	237 (50.3)	6 (1.3)	32 (6.8)	471
AGE					
18-24 years	70 (42.9)	62 (26.2)	4 (66.7)	5 (15.6)	123
24-35 years	74 (37.8)	92 (38.8)	1 (16.7)	12 (37.5)	179
35-44 years	49 (25)	60 (25.3)	1 (16.7)	10 (31.3)	120
45-54 years	14 (7.1)	15 (6.3)	-	4 (12.5)	33
55-64 years	5 (2.6)	4 (1.7)	-	1(3.1)	10
65-74 years	2 (1.0)	4 (1.7)	-	-	
75 years or more	-	-	-	-	
Prefer not to say	-	-	-	-	6
AREA					
Rural	25 (12.8)	21 (8.9)	-	5 (15.6)	51
Suburban	39 (19.9)	39 (19.9)	1 (16.7)	22 (68.8)	82
Urban	132 (67.3)	179 (75.5)	5 (83.3)	5 (15.6)	338

Table 37: Frequency and percentage data of income, and marital/family status demographics by gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non Binary (%)	Prefer not to say	Total (100%)
SALARY INCOME					
No Income	25 (12.8)	23 (9.7)	1 (16.7)	4 (12.5)	53
Less than 10,999	43 (21.9)	84 (35.7)	3 (50)	4 (12.5)	134

11,000-20,999	68 (34.7)	48 (20.3)	2 (33.3)	4 (12.5)	122
21,000-30,999	18 (9.2)	15 (6.3)	-	3 (9.4)	36
31,000-40,999	11 (5.6)	5 (2.1)	-	1 (3.1)	17
41,000-50,999	3 (1.5)	1 (.4)	-	-	4
51,000-70,999	1 (.5)	1 (.4)	-	-	2
More than 70,000	1 (.5)	-	-	-	1
Prefer not to say	26 (13.3)	60 (25.3)	-	16 (50)	102
MARITAL/FAMILY STATUS					
Married/Civil Partnership/Heterosexual	109 (55.6)	111 (46.8)	2 (33.3)	12 (37.5)	234
Married/Civil Partnership/Same Sex	6 (3.1)	3 (1.3)	3 (50)	-	12
Cohabiting	10 (5.1)	25(10.5)	-	1 (3.1)	36
Lone Parent	2 (1)	10 (4.2)	-	-	12
Single	48 (24.5)	67 (28.3)	1 (16.7)	6 (18.8)	122
Prefer not to Say	21(10.7)	21 (8.9)	-	13 (40.6)	55
IN YOUR FAMILY UNIT, DO YOU LIVE WITH ANY DEPENDENTS (E.G. CHILDREN, ELDERLY, CARING FOR DISABLED)?					
No	129 (65.8)	168 (70.9)	5 (83.3)	19 (59.4)	321
Preschool and School Age Children (under 5years)	42 (21.4)	32 (13.5)	-	7 (21.9)	81
School Age Children (5-16 years)	22 (11.2)	31 (13.1)	1 (16.7)	6 (18.8)	60
Disabled Person	-	4 (1.7)	-	-	4
Elderly	3 (1.5)	2 (.8)	-	-	5

Overall, apart from most of the participants coming from an urban area, the respondents are quite a homogenous group in terms of ethnicity, race, religion, sexuality, education etc., and have minimal responsibilities in terms of caring for dependents. The rail users' similar characteristics may indicate that public transport appeals best to only certain sectors of the population (e.g., younger single employed with no dependents).

The below correlation matrix shows that there is some limited correlation across some variables that can be grouped together in topics such as 1) capability to meet service needs such as (frequency of services, operational hours, easy to get to destination, announcements, travel info etc..) 2) safety (feel safe, safe belonging, cctv, get help), 3) and accessibility/ comfort (facilities, seating etc.). The questions were not very strongly correlated with each other with the areas in red indicating a correlation index below 0.40. The areas in yellow are around travelling with dependent and accessibility, safety and security and general service satisfaction.

Figure 99: Correlation matrix among questions and clustering.

Factor analysis

For the next step of the analysis, we now group questions into factors, or groups of questions that tend to follow similar patterns. The graph below (scree plot) shows the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors. Based on this graph, we chose 3 as number of factors for this dataset.

Figure 100: Use case 1 – ZTM. Scree plot showing the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors

We now show the resulting factors, that group the questionnaire’s questions in three groups. We attributed a name to each factor based on manual inspection of the questions, to identify the main topic behind each of them.

Factor 0 – Capability to address service needs

- It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service
- The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs
- Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs
- I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning services available on a smartphone app or online
- I am satisfied that all services, exits, and platforms are clearly signposted
- Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips
- Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security
- I can easily travel to my work place using public transport, if this applies to you
- Fare discounts and ticket options are a more affordable and better value for money than traveling by private car
- I Feel comfortable with air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.
- I can easily get to my destination from the station by walking or using other means of transport
- At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles.

Factor 1 – Station facilities and information

- I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station
- The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations) at this station meet my travel needs
- The cleanliness and maintenance of the environment (station and the train) are adequate.
- Facilities such as seating, backrests, and restrooms are adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities
- The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs)
- There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.
- I feel comfortable with the personal space available to me at stations and in carriages.
- If needed, I am satisfied that I could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g. security staff, emergency phone number).

Factor 2 – Safety and security

- Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts, rail etc)
- There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station.
- When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.
- Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.
- There are enough CCTV systems and other security measures visible to make me feel safe
- I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).

Demographic differences by factor

We now look at how each demographic variable influences user satisfaction with respect to each set of questions (i.e., with respect to each factor), and show the corresponding differences with boxplots. We report only results for cases in which we found evidence of statistically significant differences according to an ANOVA test, and omit all the other combinations of factors and demographic variables.

Factor 0 – Capability to address service needs

Figure 101: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Station.

Figure 102: UC I – FGC. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by Academic formation.

Figure 103: UC 1 – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by age range.

Figure 104: UC 1 – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by journey duration.

People having no formal education degree, and young people, especially between 25 and 34 years old, reported lower satisfaction with respect to service efficiency issues.

Factor 1 – Station facilities and information

Figure 105: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Station.

Figure 106: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Environment.

Figure 107: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by age range.

Figure 108: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Academic formation.

Figure 109: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Household type.

Station facilities and information seem to produce higher levels of satisfaction in urban areas with respect to suburban and rural areas. Users over 65 and below 18 years old also tend to be more satisfied with this aspect of the service.

Factor 2 – Safety

Figure 110: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by Station.

Figure 111: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by gender.

Figure 112: UC I – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by whether respondents reported experiencing discrimination.

Figure 113: UC1 – ZTM. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by journey duration.

Women exhibited lower levels of satisfaction than men with respect to aspects related to safety; with even lower levels are found for users having non-binary gender.

Responses for different types of other demographic characteristics

We now take a more detailed look into the responses to the questionnaire's statements from different demographic groups.

Responses by Gender

Significant differences across genders were found for the following statements that related to the capability of addressing service needs:

Figure 114: Average responses on likert scale distinguished by gender for capability to meet needs

The means for each question by gender are presented in relation to those variables related to the capability of the service to meet required needs.

There is evidence that respondents' needs are generally being met by this public transport service. One-way ANOVA showed **significant difference between the genders for statements related to: Easy to get to destination; operational hours; travel ticketing; signs; Travel satisfaction; Travel to work satisfaction; Value for money**

It is important to note that the number of nonbinary (N = 6) respondents was very small, and this can impact data analyses for these groups.

Figure 115: Average responses on likert scale distinguished by gender for accessibility

In relation to variables related to accessibility, although there is some discrepancy in mean scores by gender for each statement, correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed significant difference between the genders for only two statements, with nonbinary and “prefer not to say” users rating comfort with Seating and comfort with ventilation and A/C lower than other genders. For the statement related to the possibility to have “quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, all respondents scored it really low (below 2).

Figure 116: Average responses on likert scale distinguished by gender for safety and security

In relation to variables related to safety and security there are some discrepancies in mean scores by gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed significant difference between the genders for three statements, where nonbinary users rated the following lower:

- Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.
- If needed, I am satisfied that I could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g. security staff, emergency phone number).
- I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).

Responses by Ethnicity

The means for each question by ethnicity are presented. **The figure below reports the ones related to capability of meeting service needs.** There is evidence that in-group and out-group respondents' needs are generally being met by this public transport service as the average is above the 3.5 mark of the 7-point likert scale. However one-way ANOVA showed significant difference between in-group, out-group and respondents who preferred not to disclose their ethnicity ("prefer not to say" or PNTS) for all statements except for 'Travel Satisfaction time, security', $F(2, 469) = 2.25, p = .107$. Respondents who preferred not to disclose their ethnicity were more dissatisfied across all questions.

It is important to note that the size of the out group (N = 13) and PNTS respondents was relatively small (N = 37) and this can impact data analyses for this group

Figure 117: Average responses on likert scale distinguished by Ethnicity for capability to meet needs

Regarding the questions related to accessibility there is evidence that in-group and out-group respondents' needs are generally being met by this public transport service. One-way ANOVA showed significant difference between in-group, out-group and respondents who stated prefer not to say for all statements except for Seating; Ventilation A/C; and Walking from the station.

Figure 118: Average responses on likert scale distinguished by Ethnicity for accessibility

Regarding questions related to safety and security by ethnicity one-way ANOVA showed significant difference between in-group, out-group respondents for the followings:

- When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.
- Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.
- I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).

Figure 119: Average responses on likert scale distinguished by Ethnicity for safety and security

Responses by People Who Have Travelled with dependent person Vs. Have Not Travelled with dependent person

Most respondents (68.2%) did not live with any dependent person (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled person) nor travelled on a weekly basis with a dependent person (83.5%). There was no significant difference between genders for living with dependents but there were significant differences across gender for traveling with dependents.

There was significant difference between respondents living with/without dependents across three statements: Lighting $F(4,420) = 2.94, p = 0.024$; Facilities $F(4, 420) = 2.45, p = 0.045$; and CCTV $F(4,420) = 4.36, p = .001$

There was significant difference between respondents travelling with dependents and those who do not across the two statements: announcements $F(1, 423) = 4.36, p = .037$; CCTV, $F(1, 423) = 5.39, p = 0.021$.

Figure 120: Means of total responses by people who have travelled with dependent person (vs. not) for questions related to 'Capability to address service needs', 'Accessibility' and 'Safety and Security'.

Responses by People Who Have Faced Discrimination for Their Appearance Vs. Have Not Faced Discrimination

Most respondents (86.4%) report they have not experienced discrimination for their appearance. However, there were significant differences across genders for discriminated users.

There were significant differences between those who did and did not experience discrimination, as the ones who did expressed lower satisfaction for the service for some questions and especially across the safety category.

Figure 121: Means of total responses by people who have faced discrimination (vs. not) for their appearance for questions related to ‘Capability to address service needs’.

Responses by People with and without chronic illness

There was significant difference between chronic and non-chronic respondents for 2 statements: Accessibility to station, $F(1,470) = 7.16, p = 0.008$ and Seating, $F(1,470) = 7.07, p = 0.008$

Figure 122: Means of total responses by people with chronic illness (vs. not) for questions related to ‘Capability to address service needs’.

Regression Analysis

Prediction of general satisfaction highlighted salient characteristics such as “frequency of service” “travel satisfaction security”, “walking form station to destination” “safe belonging” and “travel with Kids under 5”. Some significance was also found for some demographic characteristics such as education and caring responsibilities. No real predictive capacity was associated to gender or age in relation to general satisfaction with the service.

Table 38: Example of linear regression analysis of Eastern European dataset using as depended variable travel satisfaction.

Predictors	travel satisfaction		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	1.79	0.91 – 2.68	<0.001
frequency service	0.18	0.11 – 0.26	<0.001
operational hrs	0.07	-0.00 – 0.14	0.054
travel ticketing	0.08	0.00 – 0.16	0.038
travel satisfaction time, security	0.41	0.33 – 0.49	<0.001
traveling with kids under 5	-0.12	-0.23 – -0.01	0.040
travel with bags	0.09	-0.01 – 0.19	0.075
ventilation A/C	-0.05	-0.12 – 0.02	0.142
walking from station	0.22	0.13 – 0.32	<0.001
cctv	0.12	0.03 – 0.22	0.013
get help	-0.09	-0.18 – 0.00	0.053
evacuation	-0.09	-0.17 – 0.00	0.056
education	-0.07	-0.13 – -0.02	0.011
caring responsibility	0.11	-0.03 – 0.24	0.113
status	-0.04	-0.09 – 0.01	0.088
chronic illness or not	-0.42	-0.79 – -0.04	0.029
sex	-0.09	-0.19 – 0.02	0.111
Observations	472		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.550 / 0.534		

Table 39: Example of Ordinal logistic regression model for Eastern European dataset using as depended variable travel satisfaction.

Predictors	travel satisfaction		
	Odds Ratios	CI	p
1 2	22.40	19.07 – 26.32	<0.001
2 3	80.38	67.83 – 95.25	<0.001
3 4	476.11	388.23 – 583.87	<0.001
4 5	6741.87	5513.86 – 8243.38	<0.001
frequency service	1.55	1.32 – 1.83	<0.001
travel ticketing	1.15	0.97 – 1.36	0.104
travel satisfaction time, security	2.52	2.06 – 3.09	<0.001
traveling with kids under 5	0.85	0.70 – 1.04	0.117
travel with bags	1.16	0.98 – 1.37	0.096
walking from station	1.62	1.32 – 2.00	<0.001
feel safe	0.78	0.58 – 1.03	0.081
safe belonging	1.46	1.10 – 1.95	0.010
education	0.90	0.82 – 0.98	0.022
caring responsibility	1.20	0.95 – 1.52	0.118
Observations	472		
R ² Nagelkerke	0.549		

In the Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) model, ‘education’ becomes a relevant socio-demographic characteristic related to ‘travel satisfaction’.

Interim Conclusion for ZTM use case I

In conclusion, preliminary findings of the user survey for this Eastern European rail service provider indicate that most people are satisfied with the level of service. We can summarise some key more specific findings below:

- There are discrepancies and disagreements regarding fare discounts and pricing, as well as safety and security for certain demographics: women feel less safe than men, and non-binary users even less

- These results are comparable across different locations but in some way also specific to each situation/scenario.
- The users that have experienced discrimination have been found to be significantly less satisfied than the rest of the user sample for the following safety and security characteristics thanks to an ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis test performed on “Feel safe”, on whether the use of CCTV camera can offer some protection and the Safety of their belongings and safe access and parking around the station
- Ethnicity was also a significant factor as people that were out-group experienced in general less satisfaction with the service than people that are in-group.
- Prediction of general satisfaction highlighted salient characteristics such as “frequency of service”, “travel satisfaction security”, “walking form station to destination”, “safe belonging” and “travel with Kids under 5”. Some significance was also found for some demographic characteristics such as education and caring responsibilities. No real predictive capacity was associated with gender or age in relation to general satisfaction with the service.

Results Use Case III

Summary of Results for Use Case III

The survey aimed to assess user perception about bicycle sharing services and the possible challenges and needs of users in terms of service accessibility, safety, impact of social forces, and the effect of weather and local topography. The perception, challenges and needs of users were assessed through a user satisfaction survey with a number of questions and statements covering the four Level I Fairness Characteristics;

- Accessibility and spontaneity,
- Safety and Security
- Social constraints
- Weather and Topography

Table 40 presents the questions considered in the User satisfaction survey and the variables analysed in the report.

Table 40: Summary of alignment between variables considered in the user satisfaction survey and fairness characteristics for use case III

Variable	Question Text	Level 2 FCs	Label
A1	Equipment for transporting children and goods would be relevant	Travelling with children / Carrying things	Childseat_and_basket
A2	I am familiar with the cycling network in my neighbourhood	Public awareness	Network_fam
A3	Signing-up for bike share membership is very easy and flexible.	Sign-up & booking process	Signing-up
A4	A cash payment option for members would be relevant	Sign-up & booking process	Cash_payment
A5	I find it easy to book a bike for a bike-sharing trip	Sign-up & booking process	Booking_a-bike

Variable	Question Text	Level 2 FCs	Label
A6	There is bike-sharing/docking station close to my residential neighbourhood	Proximity of docking station	Stns_near_neighb
A7	The cost of renting a shared bike is very affordable	Membership cost	Rental_cost
A8	Rental charges above one hour are reasonably priced.	Membership cost	Charges_above_1hr
A9	Annual membership cost of the bike sharing scheme is reasonably priced and affordable	Membership cost	Membership_cost
A10	The availability of helmet, high visibility vest, safety flags and, elbow and knee pads for interested users would be relevant	Membership cost	Safety_supplies
A11	Insurance policy to cater for lost or bike damages would be relevant	Membership cost	Insurance
A12	There are always bikes available to rent when needed	Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	Bikes_availability
A13	I can rely on bike sharing services to meet my mobility needs	Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	Reliability
A14	There are always docking stations near	Proximity of docking station	Docking_stns_near
A15	It is easy to access bikes for my trips	Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	Accessing_bikes
A16	There is bike sharing station within residential and low-income neighbourhoods	Proximity of docking station	Low_income_neighb_stns
A17	I am satisfied with the existing cycling network (routes and lanes)	Insufficient Infrastructure	Satisfactions
A18	The entry (sign-up) cost of the bike sharing services is affordable	Membership cost	Entry_cost
A19	I am satisfied with the available accessories and facilities for transporting children and goods	Travelling with children / Carrying things	Satisfactions_acc
B1	I am more comfortable cycling on a segregated bicycle route than sharing the road space with cars	Separate Infrastructure	Comf_on_segr_lanes
B2	I am concerned about the attitude of drivers on the road when cycling on the road	Driver behaviour (attitude of drivers towards cyclist)	Driver_behaviour
B3	I will cycle/ use bike-share more if all bicycle networks are segregated from vehicular traffic	Separate Infrastructure	Segr_lanes_effect

Variable	Question Text	Level 2 FCs	Label
B4	The lighting/visibility on cycle routes is adequate for my security when cycling at night	Safe environment & Personal safety	Network_visibility
B5	The existing cycle network is safe enough to cycle with children.	Safe environment & Personal safety	Network_safety
B6	I am comfortable cycling with cars on the road as I am when cycling on a segregated cycle lane	Traffic safety	Cycling_in_traffic
B7	The lighting/visibility at docking stations is adequate at night	Safe environment & Personal safety	Stns_visibility
B8	There is adequate security (i.e. CCTV coverage) at docking stations for my security	Safe environment & Personal safety	Adequate_security
B9	I feel very safe cycling in my neighbourhood	Safe environment & Personal safety	Neighb_cycling
B10	Lowering traffic speeds on roads with cycle lanes will make me feel safer to cycle/use bike share	Traffic safety	Lowering_speeds
C1	The existing cycle infrastructure is socially accepted to provide a safe environment for cycling with children	Socio-cultural constraints (negative perception)	Acceptable_infr
C2	Cycling or bike sharing are socially acceptable as legitimate forms transport	Socio-cultural constraints (negative perception)	Legitimate_transport
C3	I am concerned about lack of end-of-trip facilities (toilets, changing rooms etc.) at docking stations	Subjective norm (peer influence)	End_of_trip_facilities
C4	Trips involving children are (will be) possible to make with bike sharing services	Family responsibilities	Cycling_with_kids
C5	The social/family responsibility of women poses a significant barrier to using bike share	Family responsibilities	Family_responsibility
D1	Weather such as rain and extreme cold significantly affect my rate of cycling and bike share use	Weather	Weather
D2	Hilly terrains along cycling routes significantly deter me from cycling.	Topography	Terrain
D3	The availability of cycling raincoats (ponchos) for interested users on rainy days would be relevant	Weather	Raincoat

In general, the results indicate that user satisfaction depends on individual age and level of income. The key results of the non-parametric analysis and linear regression analysis are summarised below.

- Most of the questions are not strongly correlated with each other. The correlation matrices indicate correlation index below 0.45 for most questions. The variables with correlation higher than 0.45 were found under Accessibility and spontaneity between A1 and A10, A5 and A15, and A7 and A9; for safety and security, between B2 and B3, and for Social constraint between C1 and C4. Variable C1 was also found to be highly correlated with variable B5 under safety and security.
- The results of the stepwise analysis on the linear regression on the prediction of general satisfaction reinforces the non-parametric analysis and suggest that user's level of satisfaction is positively related to age; respondents between the ages of 45 and 74 are more critical of bike-sharing system compared to respondents aged 18 to 44.
- The perception of safety is linked to traffic speed, lowering traffic on shared vehicle/bicycle network has a direct effect on the perception of safety and consequently user satisfaction. Similarly, visibility and adequate lighting system at the docking station gives a sense of security and significantly influences user satisfaction.
- The absence of accessories for transporting children and carting goods has significant influence on user level of satisfaction with the bike-sharing system. Respondents indicated that the provision of this kind of equipment would increase their level of satisfaction.
- Weather conditions such as rain have significant impact on cycling and bike-sharing. The results suggest that the supply of cycling raincoats could mitigate the impact of rain on cycling and ensure user satisfaction.

Results for Use case III Velib

Overview and descriptive statistics

The responses of those who met the following criteria were analysed for this report:

- Identified as either male or female
- Completed the questionnaire.

A total of 407 bike share users (206 males, 201 females, 0 nonbinary, and 0 prefer not to say) whose ages ranged from 18 to 74 were included. The majority of the respondents have a university degree (50.8%), More than one third of the respondents were single (37.8%). More than two-thirds also did not live with any dependent (73.5%), and did not travel with dependents on weekly basis (85.3%), More female than male respondents travel with dependants. Almost half of the respondents were in paid employment (49.9%); more than a quarter were students (26.8%), and a little over a half of respondents were in full-time employment (50.4%).

Table 41: Percentage of respondents by age and living area demographics, by Gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non binary (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Total (100%)
	206 (50.61)	201 (49.39)	-	-	407
AGE					
18-24 years	65 (31.6)	72 (35.8)	-	-	137 (33.7)
25-34 years	74 (35.9)	71 (35.3)	-	-	145 (35.6)
35-44 years	30 (14.6)	36 (17.9)	-	-	66 (16.2)
45-54 years	23 (11.2)	9 (4.5)	-	-	32 (7.9)
55-64 years	8 (3.9)	9 (4.5)	-	-	17(4.2)
65-74 years	3 (1.5)	4 (2.0)	-	-	7 (1.7)
Above 75	-	-	-	-	-
Prefer not to say	3 (1.5)	-	-	-	3 (0.7)
AREA					
Rural	10 (4.9)	12 (6.0)	-	-	22 (5.4)
Suburban	14 (6.8)	17 (8.5)	-	-	31 (7.6)
Urban	182 (88.3)	172 (85.6)	-	-	354 (87.0)

Table 42: Frequency and percentage data of income, and marital/family status demographics by Gender.

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non binary (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Total (100%)
SALARY INCOME					
No Income – 10,999	42 (20.4)	35 (17.4)	-	-	77 (18.9)
11,000-20,999	25 (12.1)	24 (11.9)	-	-	49 (12.0)
21,000-30,999	35 (17.0)	29 (14.4)	-	-	64 (15.7)
31,000-40,999	32 (15.5)	35 (17.4)	-	-	67 (16.5)
41,000-50,999	19 (9.2)	15 (7.5)	-	-	34 (8.4)
51,000-70,999	7 (3.4)	8 (4.0)	-	-	15 (3.7)
More than 70,000	6 (2.9)	2 (1.0)	-	-	8 (2.0)
Prefer not to say	40 (19.4)	53 (26.4)	-	-	93 (22.9)
MARITAL/FAMILY STATUS					
Married/Civil Partnership/Heterosexual	65 (31.6)	58 (28.9)	-	-	123 (30.2)

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Non binary (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Total (100%)
Married/Civil Partnership/Same Sex	-	-	-	-	-
Cohabiting	35 (17.0)	42 (20.9)	-	-	77 (18.9)
Lone Parent	10 (4.9)	14 (7.0)	-	-	24 (5.9)
Single	81 (39.3)	73 (36.3)	-	-	154 (37.8)
Prefer not to Say	15 (7.3)	14 (7.0)	-	-	29 (7.1)
IN YOUR FAMILY UNIT, DO YOU LIVE WITH ANY DEPENDENTS (E.G. CHILDREN, ELDERLY, CARING FOR DISABLED)?					
No	151 (73.3)	148 (73.6)	-	-	299 (73.5)
Preschool age children (under 5 years)	12 (5.8)	16 (8.0)	-	-	28 (6.9)
School Age Children (5-16 Years)	39 (18.9)	32 (15.9)	-	-	71 (17.4)
Preschool and School Age Children	-	-	-	-	-
Disabled Person	-	2 (1.0)	-	-	2 (0.5)
Elderly	4 (1.9)	3 (1.5)	-	-	7 (1.7)

Figure 123: Correlation matrix for the variables considered in the User satisfaction survey

The correlation matrix of the variables used in the analysis is shown in the Figure above, As reported in Table 40 above, representing level I Fairness characteristics (FC) “Accessibility and spontaneity”, “Safety and Security”, “Social Constraint”, and “Weather and Topography”.

We observe some level of correlation among some of the variables, Correlation of index 0.20 and above are shown in pink and orange in Figure 123. Positive correlation are shown in pink and negative correlation are indicated in orange. The areas indicated red indicates correlation below 0.20.

Factor analysis

For the next step of the analysis, we now group questions into factors, or groups of questions that tend to follow similar patterns.

The graph below (scree plot) shows the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors. Based on this graph, we chose 6 as number of factors for this dataset. This is higher than for Use case I, and it makes sense as the number of questions in this case is higher.

Figure 124: Use case III – Velib. Scree plot showing the eigenvalues obtained for different numbers of factors

The resulting factors are shown, that group the questionnaire’s questions in six groups. A name was attributed to each factor based on manual inspection of the questions, to identify the main topic behind each of them. While the first four factors include questions that are properly associated with user satisfaction with respect to different aspects of the service, similarly to use case I, the last two factors include different kinds of questions, related to expectations with respect to possible improvements of the bike sharing service (factor 4) and general concerns with respect to cycling in the city (factor 5).

Factor 0 – Service efficiency

- I find it easy to book a bike for a bike-sharing trip
- There are always bikes available to rent when needed
- I can rely on bike sharing services to meet my mobility needs
- It is easy to access bikes for my trips
- I am satisfied with the existing cycling network (routes and lanes)
- The lighting/visibility on cycle routes is adequate for my security when cycling at night
- I am comfortable cycling with cars on the road as I am when cycling on a segregated cycle lane
- The lighting/visibility at docking stations is adequate at night
- I feel very safe cycling in my neighbourhood

Factor 1 – Safety and children

- I am satisfied with the available accessories and facilities for transporting children and goods

- The existing cycle network is safe enough to cycle with children.
- There is adequate security (i.e. CCTV coverage) at docking stations for my security
- The existing cycle infrastructure is socially accepted to provide a safe environment for cycling with children
- I am concerned about lack of end-of-trip facilities (toilets, changing rooms etc.) at docking stations
- Trips involving children are (will be) possible to make with bike sharing services
- The social/family responsibility of women poses a significant barrier to using bike share

Factor 2 - Fares

- Signing-up for bike share membership is very easy and flexible.
- The cost of renting a shared bike is very affordable
- Rental charges above one hour are reasonably priced.
- Annual membership cost of the bike sharing scheme is reasonably priced and affordable
- The entry (sign-up) cost of the bike sharing services is affordable

Factor 3 – Cycling and docking stations network

- I am familiar with the cycling network in my neighbourhood
- There is bike-sharing/docking station close to my residential neighbourhood
- There are always docking stations near
- There is bike sharing station within residential and low-income neighbourhoods
- I am more comfortable cycling on a segregated bicycle route than sharing the road space with cars
- cycling or bike sharing are socially acceptable as legitimate forms transport

Factor 4 – Relevant improvements

- Equipment for transporting children and goods would be relevant
- A cash payment option for members would be relevant
- The availability of helmet, high visibility vest, safety flags and, elbow and knee pads for interested users would be relevant
- Insurance policy to cater for lost or bike damages would be relevant
- The availability of cycling raincoats (ponchos) for interested users on rainy days would be relevant

Factor 5 – Cycling concerns

- I am concerned about the attitude of drivers on the road when cycling on the road
- I will cycle/ use bike-share more if all bicycle networks are segregated from vehicular traffic

- Lowering traffic speeds on roads with cycle lanes will make me feel safer to cycle/use bike share
- Weather such as rain and extreme cold significantly affect my rate of cycling and bike share use
- Hilly terrains along cycling routes significantly deter me from cycling.

Demographic differences by factor

This involved observing which demographic characteristics of users have an influence on user satisfaction. Results were only reported for selected relevant demographic characteristics for which we found evidence of statistically significant differences between groups.

Factor 0 – Service efficiency

Figure 125: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Environment.

Figure 126: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 0, grouped by Nationality.

Users who are not French citizens, who experienced discrimination or who live in rural areas are the ones that tend to be more satisfied about aspects related to service efficiency.

Factor 1 – Safety and children

Figure 127: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Gender.

Figure 128: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 1, grouped by Environment.

Women, especially from urban and suburban environment, are less satisfied with respect to safety and children.

Factor 2 - Fares

Figure 129: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 2, grouped by Age range.

Satisfaction with respect to fares and price of the service is generally higher than for other factors; however elder users (over 45 years old) tend to be less satisfied than younger users.

Factor 3 – Cycling and docking stations network

Figure 130: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 3, grouped by Household type.

Figure 131: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing satisfaction with respect to Factor 3, grouped by Professional status.

Single parents and unemployed users have lower satisfaction with respect to this factor.

Factor 4 – Relevant improvements

Figure 132: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing responses for Factor 4, grouped by Gender.

Figure 133: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing responses for Factor 4, grouped by Household type.

Women, single parents and users from urban areas (data not shown) are the ones that attribute higher relevance to the improvements mentioned in the survey, while users with lower education levels or over 65 years old attribute lower relevance (data not shown).

Factor 5 – Cycling concerns

Figure 134: UC III – Velib. Boxplot showing responses for Factor 5, grouped by Gender.

For the last factor, focused on general concerns related to cycling, we find significant differences only by gender, with women reporting higher concern.

Responses for different types of demographic characteristics

A non-parametric analysis of the statements measured on seven-point Likert scale from the four Level I Fairness Characteristics (FCs; Accessibility, Safety and security, Social constraints, and Weather and Topography) is presented. The analysis was carried out using the following variables; Gender, Residential area, Age, Chronic illness, Living with dependent and travelling with dependent as grouping variables.

Responses by Gender (Female vs. Male)

Figure 135 below presents a graph of the means for each question by Gender (male vs female). In general, there was no significant difference in the responses of female and male respondents for most of the statements.

Figure 135: Means of total responses by Gender

Respondents were found to statistical differ in opinion on the following statements:

- “Equipment for transporting children and goods would be relevant”, women (M = 4.950, SD = 1.64) agreed more with this statement than men (M = 4.592, SD = 1.67). Women were found to differ significantly from men in agreement on this statement (chi-square = 5.747, p = 0.017).
- “The availability of helmet, high visibility vest, safety flags and, elbow and knee pads for interested users would be relevant”, women (M = 5.214, SD = 1.64) agreed more with this statement than men (M = 4.791, SD = 1.81). Women were found to differ significantly from men (chi-square = 5.000, p = 0.025).
- “I am satisfied with the available accessories and facilities for transporting children and goods”, women (M = 3.656, SD = 1.58) disagreed with this statement while on average, men were almost neutral (M = 4.083, SD = 1.42). Women were found to differ significantly than men in the opinion on the statement (chi-square = 8.172, p = 0.004).
- “I am concerned about the attitude of drivers on the road when cycling on the road”, the results indicate that both men and women are concerned with the attitudes of drivers towards cyclist on the road. However, women were more concerned (M = 5.607, SD = 1.38) about drivers’ behaviour than men (M = 5.131, SD = 1.59). Women were found to differ significantly than men in the opinion on the statement (chi-square = 8.881, p = 0.003).
- “There is adequate security (i.e. CCTV coverage) at docking stations for my security”, women (M = 4.155, SD = 1.36) disagree with the statement whereas men tend to slightly agree (M = 3.731, SD = 1.44) Women were found to differ significantly from men in the opinion on the statement (chi-square = 9.368, p = 0.002).

Women and men indicated their discomfort when cycling with cars on the road. Both sexes disagree with the statement, “I am comfortable cycling with cars on the road as I am when cycling on a segregated cycle lane”, women ($M = 3.070$, $SD = 1.81$) are more uncomfortable (chi-square = 9.888, $p = 0.002$) cycling with cars than men ($M = 3.650$, $SD = 1.90$). In terms of security, women have a heightened sense of insecurity at the docking station than men. This sense of insecurity is reinforced by the responses of the respondents on the statement, “The lighting/visibility at docking stations is adequate at night”, women ($M = 4.224$, $SD = 1.44$) agreed less with the statement and statistically differ in perception (chi-square = 11.576, $p = 0.001$) than men ($M = 4.689$, $SD = 1.31$). The results also indicate that weather is a significant barrier to cycling for both sexes. Men and women agreed with the statement: “Weather such as rain and extreme cold significantly affect my rate of cycling and bike share use”, however, women ($M = 5.657$, $SD = 1.53$) agree more with the statement than men ($M = 5.248$, $SD = 1.66$). Consequently, women ($M = 5.358$, $SD = 1.63$) and men ($M = 5.364$, $SD = 1.53$) agree on the importance of supplying cyclist raincoat to mitigate the impact of rains.

Responses By Area (Urban Vs. Suburban Vs. Rural)

In the Figure below, the means for each question by the kind of area in which respondents live (Urban, Suburban, or Rural) are presented. However, correlation analysis indicated that there were significant differences by living areas across a number of statements. Further analysis indicated that while the groups shared the same view on most of the statements from the four level I FCs presented (Accessibility, Safety and security, Social constraints, and Weather and Topography), they also significantly differed in their level of agreement with some of the statements from the Level I FCs.

Figure 136: Means of total responses by Area

Summarised below are the key differences identified for respondents living in rural, suburban, and urban environments areas:

- “The social/family responsibility of women poses a significant barrier to using bike share”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 5.545$, $SD = 1.34$) agree with this statement while respondents living in urban areas ($M = 3.251$, $SD = 1.89$) and suburban area ($M = 3.742$, $SD = 1.89$) disagree.
- “I am comfortable cycling with cars on the road as I am when cycling on a segregated cycle lane” While respondents in rural areas ($M = 5.091$, $SD = 1.54$) agree to this statement, respondents from suburban areas ($M = 3.871$, $SD = 1.86$) and urban areas ($M = 3.212$, $SD = 1.84$) significantly disagree at chi-square = 22.835 and, p-value = 0.000.
- “I am satisfied with the available accessories and facilities for transporting children and goods.” even though respondents living in the urban areas disagree with the statement ($M = 3.785$, $SD = 1.51$), respondents in suburban areas ($M = 4.129$, $SD = 1.45$) and rural environment ($M = 4.909$, $SD = 1.23$) agree.
- “The existing cycle network is safe enough to cycle with children”, respondents living in urban ($M = 3.517$, $SD = 0.86$) and suburban ($M = 3.548$, $SD = 1.46$) areas disagree with this statement more than respondents living in rural areas ($M = 4.545$, $SD = 1.58$) and significantly differ in opinion (chi-square = 12.323, $p = 0.002$).

Respondents from the rural environment have a higher level of confidence in cycling than respondents from urban and suburban environments. Similarly, the results indicate that respondents from the urban environment are less comfortable cycling with children in urban centres compared to respondents from the rural environment. Therefore, it is suggested for policy and measures to be directed at bridging the confidence gap of the urban and suburban cyclists and the provision of child-friendly cycling infrastructure and accessories to promote cycling in the urban and suburban environment.

The key concerns identified for respondents living in rural, suburban, and urban environments are summarised below:

- “I find it easy to book a bike for a bike-sharing trip”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 6.50$, $SD = 0.74$) agreed more with this statement and significantly differed in opinion (chi-square = 16.455, $p = 0.000$) than respondents in suburban and urban areas.
- “It is easy to access bikes for my trip”, respondents in rural areas ($M = 6.591$, $SD = 0.80$) agreed more with this statement and significantly differ in opinion (chi-square = 11.075, $p = 0.004$) than respondents in suburban areas ($M = 5.645$, $SD = 1.23$) and urban areas ($M = 5.768$, $SD = 1.36$).
- “The availability of helmet, high visibility vest, safety flags and, elbow and knee pads for interested users would be relevant”. Respondents in rural areas ($M = 6.000$, $SD = 0.98$) agreed more with this statement than respondents in urban areas ($M = 4.907$, $SD = 1.77$) and suburban areas ($M = 5.355$, $SD = 1.60$). The three groups significantly differ in opinion at (chi-square = 9.882, $p = 0.007$)
- “Weather such as rain and extreme cold significantly affect my rate of cycling and bike share use”. All respondents agree with this statement. However, respondents in rural areas appear to be more impacted ($M = 6.364$, $SD = 1.29$) by weather and significantly differ in

opinion (chi-square = 12.482, $p = 0.002$) than respondents in suburban areas ($M = 5.364$, $SD = 1.63$) and urban area ($M = 5.774$, $SD = 1.20$).

- “The availability of cycling raincoats (ponchos) for interested users on rainy days would be relevant”. At (chi-square = 9.011, $p = 0.011$), respondents living in rural areas ($M = 6.136$, $SD = 0.833$) agree with the statement compared to respondents living in urban ($M = 5.277$, $SD = 1.60$) and suburban areas ($M = 5.774$, $SD = 1.52$).

Overall, in terms of accessibility, respondents living in rural environment indicated a higher level of agreement that their needs are met than respondents living in urban and suburban areas. The location of docking stations and the distribution of bikes must be improved to increase the level of accessibility for the urban and suburban dwellers.

All respondents emphasised the negative impact of inclement weather on cycling and bike-share. Therefore, they would subscribe to the supply of weather protective clothing such as cycling raincoat for cyclist on rainy days.

Responses By Age

In the Figure below, the means for each question by Age are presented. Again, there is evidence that all respondents’ needs are generally being met. However, correlation analysis indicated that there were significant differences in responses according to Age across a number of the statements. Further analyses suggest that the age groups differed in their level of agreement with three statements.

Figure 137: Means of total responses by Age.

Summarised below are the key differences identified for respondents of different age range:

- “I am satisfied with the existing cycling network (routes and lanes”, while all respondents agree with the statement, respondents aged between 18 and 44 years agreed more with this statement than respondents aged between 45 and 74 years.
- “Insurance policy to cater for lost or bike damages would be relevant” respondents aged between 18 and 64 years (M = 5.078, SD = 1.59) years agreed with the statement and respondents aged between 65 and 74 years disagreed with the statement (M = 3.714, SD = 2.63).
- “The lighting/visibility on cycle routes is adequate for my security when cycling at night” respondents aged between 18 and 54 years (M = 4.508, SD = 1.43) somewhat agreed with the statement whilst respondents aged between 55 and 74 years (M = 3.833, SD = 1.97) disagreed.

Respondents of all age-bands were relatively consistent and did not show significant variations in their responses to the statements. While they agreed in general, respondents of all age-bands have issues with bike shortages at the docking stations and also indicated their dissatisfaction with the available facilities and accessories for travelling with children and goods. Thus, disagreeing with statements like “I am satisfied with the available accessories and facilities for transporting children and goods” and “There are always bikes available to rent when needed.” The results also show that respondents aged 45-74, representing 13.8% of respondents, are less satisfied with the existing cycling infrastructure than younger respondents. Again, respondents aged 18-64 years, representing 97.5% of respondents agree to the relevance of operators having insurance for their bicycle fleet against loss and damages.

[Responses by People with Chronic Illness Vs. No Chronic Illness](#)

Most respondents (93.4%) did not have a chronic illness with only 3.2% of respondents stating they had a chronic illness (including mental illness) or physical, learning or sensory disability that affected their ability to cycle.

Figure 138: Means of total responses by People with chronic illness vs no chronic illness.

In Figure 138 above, the means for each question by people with chronic illness vs no chronic illness are presented. Again, there is evidence that all respondents generally agree with most of the statements. However, we notice some few disagreements.

- “I am concerned about lack of end-of-trip facilities (toilets, changing rooms etc.) at docking stations” respondents with chronic illness agree (M = 4.769, SD = 1.92) while respondents without disagree (M = 3.187, SD = 1.78), the two groups of respondents were found to significantly differ in opinion ($\chi^2 = 8.209$, $p = 0.004$).
- “The social/family responsibility of women poses a significant barrier to using bike share”, respondents with chronic illness agree (M = 4.308, SD = 1.84) and are found to differ from respondents without chronic illness (M = 3.402, SD = 1.93).

Respondents with chronic illness and those without agree on the negative impact of weather on cycling in general and the relevance of raincoats (ponchos) on rainy days. The two groups also agree on the statement “Hilly terrains along cycling routes significantly deter me from cycling.” However, both groups significantly differ in their level of agreement ($\chi^2 = 6.507$, $p = 0.011$).

Responses by people living with dependents vs not living with dependents

73.5% of respondents indicated they did not live with any dependent person (e.g. children, elderly, disabled person).

Figure 139: Means of total responses by People living with dependants vs not

Figure 140: Means of total responses by People living with dependants vs not

In Figures 139 and 140 above, the means for each question by people living with dependents vs not living with dependents are presented. The two groups of respondents differed slightly in their responses in some statements:

“Equipment for transporting children and goods would be relevant”. Respondents living with dependents agree more ($M = 5.157, SD = 1.59$) with the statement than those who do not ($M = 4.629, SD = 1.67$).

Even though the two categories of respondents agreed with the statement above, respondents living with dependents significantly agree in their level of agreement than respondents without ($\chi^2 = 11.361, p = 0.023$). All the respondents agree with the statement that “Cycling or bike-sharing are socially acceptable as legitimate forms transport” However, they disagree with the suggestion that the available infrastructure, accessories, and facilities provide a safe environment for cycling with children.

Responses by people travelling with dependents vs not travelling with dependents

83.5% of respondents did not travel with a dependent person. There was no significant difference between genders in both cases.

Figure 141: Means of total responses by People with travelling with dependent person vs not

In the Figure above, the means for each question by people travelling with dependents vs not travelling with dependents are presented. The responses of respondents in this category were found to be consistent with those in Figure 140. Respondents travelling with dependents and those not travelling with dependents agree with the statement, “Equipment for transporting children and goods would be relevant”, however, respondents travelling with dependents agree more ($M = 5.301$, $SD = 1.60$) than those who do not ($M = 4.686$, $SD = 1.67$). Again, the two groups of respondents agreed with the statement, “Cycling or bike-sharing are socially acceptable as legitimate forms transport”, but they disagree with the assertion that “The existing cycle network is safe enough to cycle with children.”

Regression analysis

This section presents the linear regression analysis of users’ responses of the dataset from Veib users in France. The analysis uses “Satisfactions” (Satisfaction with the existing cycling network infrastructure (routes and lanes)) as dependent variable.

The results of stepwise analysis on linear regression using MASS R package on the prediction of satisfaction with cycling infrastructure produced the following variables as the relevant characteristics in the linear regression model: Age, Income, “Childseat_and_basket” (Equipment for transporting children and goods would be relevant), “Docking_stns_near” (There are always docking stations near), “Network_visibility” (The lighting/visibility on cycle routes is adequate for my security when cycling at night), “Cycling_in_traffic” (I am comfortable cycling with cars on the road as I am when cycling on a segregated cycle lane), “Neighb_cycling” (I feel very safe cycling in my neighbourhood), “Lowering_speeds” (Lowering traffic speeds on roads with cycle lanes will make me feel safer to cycle/use bike share), “Acceptable_infr” (The existing cycle infrastructure is socially accepted to provide a safe environment for cycling with children), “Legitimate_transport” (Cycling or bike sharing are socially acceptable as legitimate forms transport), “Weather” (Weather such as rain and extreme cold significantly affect my rate of cycling and bike share use) and “Raincoat” (The availability of cycling raincoats (ponchos) for interested users on rainy days would be relevant). The model obtained through the AIC stepwise approach in R is reported in the Figure below.


```

Call:
lm(formula = Satisfaction ~ Age + Income + Childseat_and_basket +
    Docking_stns_near + Network_visibility + Cycling_in_traffic +
    Neighb_cycling + Lowering_speeds + Acceptable_infr +
    Legitimate_transport + Weather + Raincoat, data = dataset)

Residuals:
    Min       1Q   Median       3Q      Max
-3.7302 -0.7271  0.1280  0.8876  3.4298

Coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    1.40521    0.56336   2.494 0.013030 *
Age            -0.18426    0.05205  -3.540 0.000448 ***
Income          0.04264    0.02519   1.693 0.091325 .
Childseat_and_basket -0.07533    0.03827  -1.968 0.049751 *
Docking_stns_near  0.18613    0.05270   3.532 0.000462 ***
Network_visibility  0.08001    0.04553   1.757 0.079622 .
Cycling_in_traffic  0.13510    0.03551   3.805 0.000164 ***
Neighb_cycling   0.09541    0.04740   2.013 0.044781 *
Lowering_speeds   0.13732    0.03452   3.978 8.26e-05 ***
Acceptable_infr   0.11736    0.04409   2.662 0.008094 **
Legitimate_transport 0.13403    0.05183   2.586 0.010069 *
Weather          0.10397    0.03985   2.609 0.009422 **
Raincoat        -0.09647    0.04167  -2.315 0.021137 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
    
```

Figure 142: Linear model resulting from the Stepwise regression approach with all significant variables.

Conclusions use case III

In conclusion, the results indicate that user satisfaction depends on individual age and level of income. The result is consistent with the non-parametric analysis and suggests that the level of satisfaction decreases with increasing age; older respondents (45 - 74 years) are more critical of bike-sharing services than younger respondents (18 – 44 years). Income level of respondents is observed to correlate with the level satisfaction. The effect of the services characteristics on respondents' level of satisfaction is summarised below:

- Lowering traffic speed increase the sense of security and consequently increases user level of satisfaction
- Respondents agreeing to the relevance of equipment for transporting children, are mostly dissatisfied with the lack of it. The provision of which will increase their level of satisfaction.
- Having docking stations near respondents would increase their level of satisfaction.
- Adequate lighting and visibility at the docking station enforce the percepton of security and significantly impact users level satisfaction.
- Respondents comfortable cycling on a shared vehicle/bicycle network tend to be satisfied. Respondents in this category tend to be experienced and confident cyclist. Thus, schemes designed to enhance the confidence of cyclists will similarly increase their level of satisfacton.
- The perception of safety increases one's level of satisfaction; Respondents perception of safety of the cycle network in their neighbourhood influences their perceived level of satisfaction.
- The perception of safety and acceptability of cycling environment for cycling with children also have effect on user level of satisfaction.
- Cycling or bike sharing are socially acceptable as legitimate forms transport:
- User level of satisfaction also depend on their level of acceptance of cycling as a legitimate form of transportation, thus promoting cycling as a legitimate form of transportation could increase user level of acceptance and consequently level of satisfacton.
- Weather such as rain and extreme cold have significant impact on cycling and bike-share. Affected respondents are less satisfied and agree to the supply of cycling raincoats (ponchos) for interested users on rainy days. Thus, the supply of raincoats could mitigitage the impact of rains on cycling and user satisfaction.

Results for Use Case IV

Use case IV – Summary of results

The survey results obtained from employees in the Northern European Use case (Irish rail) indicate that most people are satisfied with their employment conditions and the results of stepwise analysis on linear regression on the prediction of organization inclusive satisfaction showed that the variables found to be relevant are `the presence of job segregation in the social context`, `the inclusiveness offered in the education sector`, `Organizational HR policy`, `Organizational protection against unfair dismissal`, `organizational capacity for good Ergonomics conditions in the work place`, `Organizational facilities for both female and male employees`, `Organizational capacity to address special needs individuals`, `Personal circumstances related to support for carers`, `Personal circumstances in accessing promotion`, `Personal circumstances needs for travel work`, `Individual circumstances related to illness conditions`, `Being part of an Ethnic minority`, `Individual needs for specific skill`. Furthermore, only for the Northern European dataset due to the timing of the survey we were able to collect information related to how Covid affected work conditions and we found that `covid extra duties` (such as caring for children at home while school were closed), and `covid impact` were found very relevant in predicting the level of employee satisfaction with organizational inclusiveness.

In the socio-demographic variables, gender was found as a relevant predictor of employees' perception related to organization inclusiveness, with women often having a lower level of satisfaction with some of the statements such as balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport related to the context, and satisfaction with how the context responders living in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport.

The user survey for FGC rail service provider indicate that `org. inclusive satisfaction` is explained by `the presence of job segregation in the social context`, `equal opportunity offered by the context`, `Organizational HR policy`, `Satisfaction with how Personal Circumstances needs are met`, `how personal circumstances and socio-economic needs are met`, `How Individual Illness may or not affect the job role`, `ethnicity`, `age`, `education`, `having the role of carer for children`, and `sexual orientation`; there are significant differences between different roles and how they are affected by having the role of carer for children on the prediction of `organizational inclusiveness satisfaction`; the variables were not closely related to each other and people are satisfied with the average level of their employment in rail.

The user surveys for ZTM rail service provider suggest that the socio-demographic variables `income`, and background environment were useful to explain the organization inclusive satisfaction and different Individual characteristics were relevant on the prediction of `org. inclusive satisfaction`, such as `Individual Illness affect`, `individual changes flexibility`, `the effect of individual Ethnicity` and `individual experience in role`.

The variables used for the fairness characteristics from the actual questions in the questionnaire are reported in the following table.

Table 43: summary of questions and corresponding variables collected for the Use case IV analysis

Question used in the questionnaire	Variable short name
A.1 In my community/country there is currently an equal balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport.	context job seg
A.2 My community/country offers role models advertising in careers where traditionally less gender balance is achieved	context role mod
A.3 In my community/country National Laws and policies currently exist to support equal opportunity in terms of recruitment and promotion for both female and male candidates	context eq. opp
A.4 There are existing initiatives with schools,colleges and universities that attract more women to the transport sector	context education
A.6 How satisfied are you that the country you live in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport?	context satisf
B.1 My company's HR policies facilitate fair recruitment, and promotion for women in the workplace	Org. HR policy
B.2 My company's terms and conditions support maternity leave	Org Mat leave
B.3 My company's terms and conditions support paternity leave	Org Pat leave
B.4 My company's terms and conditions support employees in their caring role, i.e. family friendly policies	Org fam friendly
B.5 In my company there is prevention of dismissal or demotion during and after maternity periods;	org dismiss
B.6 My company offers flexible Working Hours e.g. Teleworking / Working from home arrangements to all employees	org Flex
B.8 In my company part time and flexible workers have equal opportunity for promotion	org flex eq. opp
C.1 Where I work there is a company culture that promotes diversity as the accepted norm	org culture
C.2 I feel comfortable and accepted in my current work environment	org env accept
C.3 In my company female employees are accepted by the public using transport	org pub accept
C.4 Where I work there is a good level of acceptance of female employees by male colleagues	org. peer accept
D.1 My working environment protects women from violence/harassment/assault	org. protect

Question used in the questionnaire	Variable short name
D.2 My workplace design is ergonomically suitable for all employees	org. ergonomics
D.3 In my work place we have adequate safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons etc.	org. Safety
E.1 In my workplace all employees have equal access to all training programs	org. training access
E.3 My company provides special training and re-skilling after career breaks/maternity leave if required	org. ad hoc training
E.4 My company facilitate up-skilling and training of women for roles that are more male dominated	org training women
E.5 My company provides training about unconscious bias in employment	org. bias training
E.6 My company provides cultural sensitivity training	sensitive training
F.1 In my workplace the provision for female facilities (female toilets and showers, facilities for breastfeeding mothers etc.) are appropriate	org. facilities
F.2 My company meets all current Employment legislation requirements to support individuals with special intellectual needs	org. special needs
F.3 My company meets all current Employment legislation requirements to support individuals with special physical needs	org. special physica needs
G.1 Overall, I am satisfied with the fairness and inclusiveness of women employees in my workplace	org. inclusive satisfaction
I am a CARER	carer
I am a PARENT	parent
PC 1.I require working times that make it possible to accommodate work and family commitments (extended hours, variable start/ finish times, shift-work etc.	PC needs. Working times require
PC 2. I require support in my workplace for dealing with chronic/long-term health conditions of those I care for	PC needs. Support for carer
PC 3.In my workplace I regularly need to exceed my working hours	PC needs extra time
PC 4.Overall how satisfied are you with the way your caring and parenting responsibility needs are supported by your employers?	PC needs satisfaction

Question used in the questionnaire	Variable short name
PC 5.In my environment I feel the need for better access to professional qualification	PC needs qualification
PC 6.In my environment I feel the need for better access to promotion opportunities	PC needs promotion
PC 7.In my environment I feel the need for better access to education to support my career goals	PC need education
PC 8.In my environment I feel the need for role models	PC need role model
PC 9.Overall how satisfied are you with the way your socio-economic needs have been supported in your workplace?	PC socio-economic needs
S 1.I require better access to flexible and affordable childcare services	PC better childcare
S 2.I require better access to the public/private transport to travel to work	PC needs travel work
S 3.I require better financial support for expenses related to travel to work	PC financial support
Overall how satisfied are you with the way your personal circumstances and needs are met in your workplace?	PC overall satisfaction
I have a Long-term illness or disability	Illness
IC 1.My need to progress in my career in my workplace is affected by having a long-term illness/disability	Ind. Illness affect
IC 2.My training and development needs are met as much as other people in my organisation	Ind trainign needs
IC 3.I have the capability to accommodate changing shifts and or working time in my workplace according to my needs	ind chnges flex
Relevant (tick as appropriate):In my work environment and in my current role I feel I belong to an ethnic minority:	Ethnic minority
U 1.In my workplace, belonging to an ethnic minority group affects my career progression	Ethnic affect
U 2.Relevant (tick as appropriate):My age group is above 50:	Age over 50
U 3.I feel that being an aging worker (above 50) negatively affects my job opportunities and career progression	age <30
U 4.My age group is below 30:	age affect

Question used in the questionnaire	Variable short name
U 5.I feel that being a young worker (less than 30) negatively affects my job opportunities and career progression	Ind needs specific skill
U 6.I require specific skills training during work to access job opportunities and progression	ind needs experience
U 7.I require more experience in specific roles to access job opportunities and progression	ind needs satisfaction
COV 1. During the COVID 19 pandemic did you:	covid work
COV 2. IF you continue to work on your regular routine, how satisfied are you with the effort made by your organization to offer necessary training in etiquette, social distancing and ensure all PPE was provided	field work sat
COV 3. If you had to work form home how satisfied are you with the reasonable efforts made by your organisation to ensure that you had the required tools and equipment to perform your role as efficiently as possible? (IT equipment, Broadband, Access to conference calls, etc?)	work form home satis
COV 4. During the current COVID-19 pandemic how satisfied are you in general with the effort made by your organization regarding reasonable measures for the health and safety of each employee?	covid satis
COV 5. During the current COVID-19 pandemic how satisfied are you with the efforts made by your organisation in relation to communication with its employees regarding the evolving situation and its possible impacts	covid comm
COV 6. During the current COVID-19 pandemic how satisfied are you with the efforts made by your organisation to make allowances for extra duties performed by you during the pandemic? (Caring for parents or children)	covid extra duties
COV 7. During the pandemic what impact did you perceive your work condition may have had in potentially exposing you to highest risk of contracting the virus?	covid risk
COV 8. What impact do you perceive that your working conditions had during the pandemic towards your general anxiety level	covid anxiety
COV 9. How did the imposed travel restrictions impact your working condition and shift patterns?Scale from 1 to 7 (1 low impact----7 high impact)	covid impact

Use case IV Irish rail

Although Irish Rail does not appear in Section 3, 4 nor 5, this company allowed us to gather additional UESI data so as to collaborate with DIAMOND broadening the data. In this way, this information was an opportunity to compare and validate the results coming from FGC and ZTM.

A consent form was included which outlined that respondents' participation in the survey was entirely voluntary, their replies would remain anonymous, and that gathered data was in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. Respondents were also provided with a brief description of the DIAMOND project including the aims of the overall project, and the specific purpose of the survey. The survey took 15-20 mins to complete.

Approximately 45 questions covered the following fairness characteristics:

- Socio-Economic Conditions;
- Job Characteristics;
- Personal Circumstances;
- Individual Characteristics.

Overview and descriptive statistics

The responses of those who met the following criteria were analysed for this report:

- Identified as either male, female, trans female, trans male, nonbinary, or prefer not to say.
- Completed the questionnaire.

A total of 129 employees (98 males, 29 females, and 2 prefer not to say) whose ages ranged from 18 years to 75 years were included. The majority of respondents were white (99%), Christian (79.8%), married/in stable relationship that was heterosexual (72.8%), heterosexual (96.8%) with a third level education (58.1%). The majority of respondents are parents (78.2%), not carers (91.3%), do not travel with dependents on weekly basis (74.4%) and earn less than €70,999 (57.3%). The majority worked in public transport in the areas of planning, maintenance and administration (61.2%) and as middle managers (39.5%). Only 8.5% of respondents report having an illness, impairment or disability that affects their work or travel in the last 12 months, and 6.25% of respondents report facing discrimination for working in or using transport due to their appearance.

The survey aimed to examine work environment for employees by examining (a) job segregation/gender balance in their country/community and (b) recruitment and promotion that promotes equality and fairness for women in transport. An overall satisfaction question was also included. Respondents rated questions on a likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree).

Table 44: Frequency and percentage data of age demographics by gender

Participant Sample	Male (%)	Female (%)	Prefer not to say (%)
	98 (77.2)	29 (29)	2 (1.6)
AGE			
18-24 years	1 (1)	-	-
25-34 years	8 (8.2)	3 (10.3)	-
35-44 years	29 (29.6)	6 (20.7)	2 (100)
45-54 years	32 (32.7)	12 (4.6)	-
55-64 years	27(27.6)	8 (27.6)	-
65-74 years	-	-	-
75 years or more	1 (1)	-	-

Table 45: Frequency and percentage data of income demographic by gender

Participant Sample	Male (%)	Female (%)	Prefer not to say (%)
SALARY INCOME			
No Income – 10,999	-	-	-
11,000-20,999	1 (1)	-	-
21,000-30,999	3 (3.1)	-	-
31,000-40,999	3 (3.1)	-	-
41,000-50,999	6 (6.1)	7 (24.1)	1 (50)

51,000-70,999	37 (37.8)	16 (55.2)	-
More than 70,000	32 (32.7)	5 (17.2)	1 (50)
Prefer not to say	16 (16.3)	1 (3.4)	-

From the correlation matrix showed below, we found that the questions were not closely related to each other, observing the area in red which indicates a correlation index lower than 0.40 while the area in yellow corresponds to some of the clusters already considered among the fairness characteristics such as Personal circumstances and related basic needs, organizational policies and workplace characteristics, contextual characteristics and or individual needs that also related to accessibility and safety and security.

Figure 143: Correlation matrix among questions and clustering.

Responses for different types of demographic characteristics

Figure 144: Means of total response grouped by ‘Sex’: ‘Your Work Environment’ * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and ANOVA showed no significant difference between the entries except for two statements:

- A1. “In my country, there is currently an equal balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport”, $F(2,125) = 4.11, p = .019$ and
- A5. “How satisfied are you that the country you live in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport?”, $F(2,125) = 4.45, p = .014$ with women disagreeing more with these statements than men.

Figure 145: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Job Characteristics * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and ANOVA showed no significant difference between the entries. PNTS (N= 2).

Figure 146: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Company Culture * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and ANOVAs showed no significant difference between the genders except for one statement:

- “Where I work there is a good level of acceptance of female employees by male colleagues” $F(2, 125) = 4.42, p = .014$, with women disagreeing more with this statement than men.

Figure 147: Means of total response grouped by ‘Sex’: Safe and Secure * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. PNTS response), correlational analysis and ANOVA analysis showed significant difference between the genders for the statement regarding adequacy of safety equipment such as CCTV camera and panic buttons.

Figure 148: Means of total response grouped by ‘Sex’: Training * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. PNTS response), correlational analysis and ANOVA analysis showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 149: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Practical Amenities * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. PNTS response), correlational analysis and ANOVA analysis showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 150: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Personal Circumstances * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. PNTS response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 151: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Supports for you' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. PNTS response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders except for two statements:

- S1. I require better access to flexible and affordable childcare services, $F(2,105) = 3.66, p = .029$ and
- S2. I require better financial support for expenses related to travel to work, $F(2,122) = 4.27, p = .016$ with PNTS respondents agreeing strongly with statements.

Figure 152: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Individual Characteristic * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. PNTS response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 153: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Satisfaction * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders except for one statements:

- A6. How satisfied are you that the country you live in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport? $F(2,125) = 4.45$, $p = .014$, and
- G1. Overall, I am satisfied with the fairness and inclusiveness of women employees in my workplace, $F(2,124) = 3.92$, $p = .022$ with women disagreeing strongly with statements.

Regression analysis

Table 46: Example of linear regression analysis of Irish Rail dataset using as depended variable 'org. inclusive satisfaction'.

	org. inclusive satisfaction		
Predictors	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	-1.21	-2.62 – 0.20	0.091
context job seg	0.09	0.00 – 0.18	0.043
context education	0.17	0.07 – 0.26	0.001
Org. HR policy	0.20	0.09 – 0.31	0.001
org env accept	0.09	-0.02 – 0.20	0.095
org. peer accept	0.13	-0.01 – 0.26	0.069
org. protect	0.29	0.18 – 0.40	<0.001
org. ergonomics	-0.12	-0.22 – -0.03	0.012
org training women	-0.10	-0.22 – 0.02	0.108
sensitive training	0.09	-0.00 – 0.18	0.055
org. facilities	0.14	0.05 – 0.22	0.002
org. special needs	0.22	0.10 – 0.33	<0.001
PC needs. Support for carer	0.09	0.01 – 0.16	0.027
PC needs qualification	-0.09	-0.20 – 0.02	0.110
PC needs promotion	0.16	0.03 – 0.29	0.013
PC need education	-0.13	-0.25 – 0.00	0.054
PC needs travel work	-0.11	-0.20 – -0.03	0.011
PC financial support	0.16	0.07 – 0.25	0.001

	org. inclusive satisfaction		
<i>Predictors</i>	<i>Estimates</i>	<i>CI</i>	<i>p</i>
Ind. Illness affect	-0.14	-0.25 – -0.03	0.015
Ind training needs	0.07	-0.03 – 0.16	0.156
Ethnic minority	-0.62	-1.22 – -0.03	0.040
Ind needs specific skill	0.10	0.01 – 0.19	0.026
covid extra duties	0.10	0.00 – 0.20	0.044
covid impact	-0.13	-0.20 – -0.05	0.001
environment	0.19	-0.02 – 0.39	0.073
education	-0.18	-0.32 – -0.04	0.011
children	-0.27	-0.41 – -0.14	<0.001
travel with dependent	0.57	0.26 – 0.87	<0.001
citizenship	-0.50	-0.89 – -0.12	0.010
sex	0.37	0.02 – 0.73	0.040
sector	0.27	0.08 – 0.46	0.007
travel time	-0.00	-0.01 – 0.00	0.101
Observations	129		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.866 / 0.823		

Figure 154: Means of total responses by males vs. females for attributes useful to explain ‘org. inclusive satisfaction’.

The significant differences between males and females for attributes useful to explain “org. inclusive satisfaction” are: “between genders the job segregation found in the external context, the level of acceptance employees can find their Organizational Environment and in recent times the amount of extra duty connected with the Covid pandemic and lockdown situation (which includes homeschooling and caring for dependents with limited external support).

COVID Section of the Questionnaire (Irish transport Operator)

- **Covid risk:** During the pandemic what impact did you perceive your work condition may have had in potentially exposing you to highest risk of contracting the virus? (1 low impact----7 high impact).
- **Covid anxiety:** What impact do you perceive that your working conditions had during the pandemic towards your general anxiety level (1 low impact----7 high impact).
- **Covid Impact:** How did the imposed travel restrictions impact your working condition and shift patterns? Scale from 1 to 7 (1 low impact----7 high impact).
- **COV 4.** During the current COVID-19 pandemic how satisfied are you in general with the effort made by your organization regarding reasonable measures for the health and safety of each employee?
- **COV 5.** During the current COVID-19 pandemic how satisfied are you with the efforts made by your organisation in relation to communication with its employees regarding the evolving situation and its possible impacts.
- **COV 6.** During the current COVID-19 pandemic how satisfied are you with the efforts made by your organisation to make allowances for extra duties performed by you during the pandemic? (Caring for parents or children).

Figure 155: % of responses who during the COVID 19 pandemic: worked from home – continued to work on site – other.

During the COVID 19 pandemic:

- 47% of users worked from home.
- 39% of users continued to work on site.
- 14% of users did not work from home and did not continue to work on site.

Interim Conclusion for Irish Rail sample in use case IV

- In conclusion, preliminary findings of the user survey for this northern European rail service provider indicate that:
- Most people are reasonably satisfied with their work environment and their conditions of employment
- The results of stepwise analysis on linear regression on the prediction of organization inclusive satisfaction showed that the variables found to be relevant predictor are: the level of job segregation found in the context also in terms of access to different education (i.e. such education for technical qualifications and STEM carers), the protection offered by HR policies in their own organization, and the protection they offer against unfair dismissal. The ergonomics conditions of different workstations and positions, the facilities for both male and females and the capacity to meet specific personal needs of different employees such as the one determined by chronic illness and support for carer', 'PC needs promotion', 'PC needs travel work', 'Ind. Illness affect', 'Ethnic minority', 'Ind needs specific skill', 'covid extra duties', and 'covid impact'.
- Gender and Sector are significant variables in respect to organization inclusive satisfaction.
- The attributes were not closely related to each other.
- 47% of users worked from home during the COVID 19 pandemic.

Use case IV FGC

Overview and descriptive statistics

The survey was administered online to all employees in FGC railways via an email containing a link to the survey.

A consent form was included which outlined that respondents' participation in the survey was entirely voluntary, their replies would remain anonymous, and that gathered data was in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016 (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. Respondents were also provided with a brief description of the DIAMOND project including the aims of the overall project, and the specific purpose of the survey. The survey took 15-20 mins to complete.

Approximately 45 questions covered the following fairness characteristics:

- Socio-Economic Conditions;
- Job Characteristics;
- Personal Circumstances;
- Individual Characteristics.

The responses of those who met the following criteria were analysed for this report:

- Identified as either male, female, trans female, trans male, nonbinary, or prefer not to say.
- Completed the questionnaire.

A total of 90 employees (50 males, 33 females, 1 nonbinary and 6 prefer not to say) whose ages ranged from 18 years to 64 years were included. The majority of respondents were white (82.2%), of no religion (65.6%), married/in stable relationship that was heterosexual (72.2%), heterosexual (85.6%) with a third level education (71.9%). The majority of respondents are parents (67.1%), not carers (78/8%), do not travel with dependents on weekly basis (68.9%) and earn less than €50,999 (85.6%). The majority worked in public transport in the areas of planning, maintenance and administration (67.8%) and as drivers (15.6%). Only 1.1% of respondents report having an illness, impairment or disability that affects their work or travel in the last 12 months, and 9% of respondents report facing discrimination for working in or using transport due to their appearance.

Table 47: Frequency and percentage data of age demographics by gender

Participant Sample	Male (%)	Female (%)	Prefer not to say (%)
	50 (55.6)	33 (36.7)	6 (6.7)
AGE			
18-24 years	1 (2)	-	-

25-34 years	9 (18)	4 (12.1)	-
35-44 years	14 (28)	13 (39.4)	2 (33.3)
45-54 years	14 (28)	13 (39.4)	3 (50)
55-64 years	12 (24)	3 (9.1)	1 (16.7)
65-74 years	-	-	-
75 years or more	-	-	-

Table 48: Frequency and percentage data of income demographic by gender

Participant Sample	Male (%)	Female (%)	Prefer not to say (%)
SALARY INCOME			
No Income – 10,999	-	-	-
11,000-20,999	1 (1)	2 (6.1)	-
21,000-30,999	4 (8)	6 (18.2)	-
31,000-40,999	21 (42)	12 (36.4)	1 (16.7)
41,000-50,999	10 (20)	7 (21.2)	-
51,000-70,999	5 (10)	2 (6.1)	1 (16.7)
More than 70,000	2 (10)	2 (6.1)	1 (16.7)
Prefer not to say	7 (14)	2 (6.1)	3 (50)

From the correlation matrix showed below, we found that the questions were not closely related to each other, observing the area in red which indicates a correlation index lower than 0.40.

Figure 156: Correlation matrix among questions and clustering.

Responses for different types of demographic characteristics

Figure 157: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Your Work Environment' * 'Job Role'.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across job level for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and ANOVA analysis showed no significant difference between the entries.

Figure 158: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Your Work Environment' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis (Kruskal-Wallis H) showed no significant difference between the entries.

Figure 159: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Company Culture' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis (Kruskal Wallis H) showed no significant difference between the genders except for one statement.

Gender differences: Where I work there is a good level of acceptance of female employees by male colleagues, $H(3) = 8.02$, $p = .046$, with women disagreeing more with this statement than men.

Figure 160: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Safe and Secure' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis showed no significant difference between the genders except for one statement.

Figure 161: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Training' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 162: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Personal Circumstances' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 163: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Individual Characteristic' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 164: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Satisfaction' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Regression analysis

Table 49 :Extract of linear regression analysis of FGC dataset using as depended variable ‘org. inclusive satisfaction’.

Predictors	org. inclusive satisfaction		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	-0.54	-2.24 – 1.16	0.526
context job seg	0.11	0.00 – 0.21	0.048
context eq. opp	0.15	0.02 – 0.28	0.028
Org. HR policy	0.36	0.21 – 0.51	<0.001
Org Pat leave	0.11	-0.01 – 0.23	0.078
PC needs. Support for carer	0.08	-0.04 – 0.19	0.199
PC needs satisfaction	0.27	0.16 – 0.38	<0.001
PC needs qualification	0.15	-0.02 – 0.32	0.085
PC need education	-0.12	-0.29 – 0.04	0.148
PC socio-economic needs	0.20	0.04 – 0.37	0.017
Ind. Illness affect	-0.11	-0.21 – -0.01	0.034
ethnicity	-0.77	-1.29 – -0.25	0.004
age	0.33	0.09 – 0.58	0.008
education	-0.16	-0.30 – -0.02	0.027
children	-0.34	-0.49 – -0.18	<0.001
sexual orientation	-0.23	-0.42 – -0.04	0.018
sector	0.26	-0.01 – 0.53	0.059
Observations	90		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.830 / 0.793		

The variables found to be relevant predictor of ‘org. inclusive satisfaction’ are: ‘context to job seg.’, ‘context eq. opp.’, ‘Org. HR policy’, ‘PC needs satisfaction’, ‘PC socio-economic needs’, ‘Ind. Illness affect’, ‘ethnicity’, ‘age’, ‘education’, ‘children’, and ‘sexual orientation’.

Interim Conclusion for FGC sample in use case IV

In conclusion, preliminary findings of the user survey for this rail service provider indicate that:

- The variables found to be relevant predictor of ‘org. inclusive satisfaction’ are: ‘context to job seg.’, ‘context eq. opp.’, ‘Org. HR policy’, ‘PC needs satisfaction’, ‘PC socio-economic needs’, ‘Ind. Illness affect’, ‘ethnicity’, ‘age’, ‘education’, ‘children’, and ‘sexual orientation’.
- The variables were not closely related to each other.

- There are significant differences between roles and ‘children’ on the prediction of ‘org. inclusive satisfaction’.
- People are satisfied with the average level of rail service.

Use case IV ZTM (Eastern European case study)

Overview and descriptive statistics

The survey was administered online to all employees in ZTM railways via an email containing a link to the survey via google forms.

The responses of those who met the following criteria were analysed for this report:

- Identified as either male, female, trans female, trans male, nonbinary, or prefer not to say.
- Completed the questionnaire.

A total of 140 employees (3 males, 132 females, 2 Prefer not to say and 3 Other/I do not know) whose ages ranged from 18 years to over 75 years were included. Most respondents were white (92.2%), heterosexual (78.7%) with a third level education (55%). The majority of respondents were in paid employment (94.3%), mainly lived in city (69.3%), are parents (71.7%), not carers (90.8%), do travel with dependents on weekly basis (53.6%). 17.2% of respondents report having an illness, impairment or disability. In comparison to the Northern and Southern European sample, the Eastern European sample has lower salary income (see below).

Table 50: Frequency and percentage data of age demographics by gender

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Don't know/ other (100%)
	3 (2.1)	132 (94.3)	2 (1.4)	3 (2.1)
AGE				
18-34 years	70 (42.9)	74 (46)	3 (25)	147
35-44 years	30 (18.4)	32 (19.9)	3 (25)	65
45-64 years	41 (25.4)	37 (23)	1 (8.3)	79
Above 65 years	12 (7.4)	16 (9.9)	4 (33.3)	32
Prefer not to say	3 (1.8)	1 (.6)	-	4

Table 44: Frequency and percentage data of income demographic by gender

Sample:	Male (%)	Female (%)	Prefer not to say (%)	Don't Know/ Other (%)
SALARY INCOME				
No Income – 10,999	2 (66.7)	34 (25.8)	1 (50)	-
11,000-20,999	1 (33.3)	24 (18.2)	-	-
21,000-30,999	-	7 (5.3)	-	-
31,000-40,999	-	-	-	-
41,000-50,999	-	1 (8)	-	-
51,000-70,999	-	-	-	-
More than 70,000	-	-	-	1 (33.3)
Prefer not to say	-	64 (48.5)	1 (50)	2 (66.7)

From the correlation matrix showed below, we found that the questions were closely related to each other, observing the area in red which indicates a correlation index lower than 0.40.

Figure 165: Correlation matrix among questions and clustering.

There was an error in the translation of the Polish Questionnaire for use case IV and the data regarding different job role was not collected unfortunately.

Responses for different types of demographic characteristics

Figure 166: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Your Work Environment * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis (Kruskall-Wallis H) showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 167: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Job Characteristics * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis (Kruskal-Wallis H) showed no significant difference between the entries.

Figure 168: Means of total response grouped by Company Culture * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis (Kruskal Wallis H) showed no significant difference between the genders except for one statement.

Gender differences: In my company female employees are accepted by public using transport, $H(3) = 11.34, p = .010$, with women agree more with this statement than men.

Figure 169: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Safe and Secure * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and non parametric analysis showed no significant difference between the genders except for one statement.

Figure 170: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Training * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and non parametric analysis showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 171: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Practical Amenities * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and non-parametric analysis showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 172: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Personal Circumstances * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 173: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': 'Supports for you' * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 174: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Individual Characteristic * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. nonbinary response), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Figure 175: Means of total response grouped by 'Sex': Satisfaction * Gender.

Although there is some discrepancy in mean scores across gender for each statement (e.g. prefer not to say), correlational analysis and one-way ANOVA showed no significant difference between the genders.

Regression analysis

Table 51: Extract of linear regression analysis of Eastern European dataset using as depended variable 'org. inclusive satisfaction'.

Predictors	org. inclusiveness satisfaction		
	Estimates	CI	p
(Intercept)	0.08	-1.29 – 1.45	0.907
org Flex	-0.08	-0.17 – 0.01	0.071
org flex eq. opp	0.17	0.06 – 0.29	0.003
org culture	0.30	0.16 – 0.44	<0.001
org env accept	-0.24	-0.39 – -0.09	0.002
org. Safety	0.10	0.01 – 0.19	0.024
org. training access	0.12	0.00 – 0.23	0.046
org. special physical needs	0.58	0.48 – 0.68	<0.001
brestfeeding facilities	0.16	0.08 – 0.24	<0.001
women integration satisfaction	-0.13	-0.25 – -0.01	0.030
PC needs qualification	0.09	-0.00 – 0.18	0.062
PC socio-economic needs	0.21	0.07 – 0.35	0.003
PC better chidlcare	-0.13	-0.22 – -0.04	0.004
PC needs travel work	-0.09	-0.16 – -0.03	0.007
Ind. Illness affect	0.11	-0.02 – 0.25	0.096
ind changes flex	-0.13	-0.24 – -0.01	0.029
Ethnic affect	-0.10	-0.21 – 0.00	0.060
ind experience in role	0.16	0.01 – 0.30	0.032
career	0.45	0.10 – 0.80	0.012
environment	-0.18	-0.35 – 0.00	0.056
income	-0.09	-0.16 – -0.02	0.013

sex	0.39	-0.04 – 0.81	0.075
org pub accept	-0.15	-0.32 – 0.02	0.086
Observations	140		
R ² / R ² adjusted	0.849	0.820	

The variables found to be relevant predictor of `org. inclusive satisfaction` are: `context eq. opp`, `context satisf`, `org flex eq. opp`, `org culture`, `org env accept`, `org. Safety`, `org. training access`, `org. ad hoc training`, `org. special physical needs`, `breastfeeding facilities`, `women integration satisfaction`, carer, `PC needs. Working times require`, `PC needs qualification`, `PC needs promotion`, `PC socio-economic needs`, `PC better childcare`, `PC needs travel work`, `PC overall satisfaction`, `Ind. Illness affect`, `ind changes flex`, `Ethnic affect`, `ind experience in role`, `Env`, `income (salary/year)` and `sex`.

Interim Conclusion for ZTM sample in use case IV

In conclusion, preliminary findings of the user survey for ZTM sample in use case IV indicate that:

- The variables were very correlated to each other compared to Irish Rail and FGC sample.
- Among the socio-demographic variables: `income`, gender and environment were useful to explain the organization inclusive satisfaction.
- Different Individual characteristics were relevant to explain `org. inclusive satisfaction` compared to Irish and FGC sample, such as `Individual Illness affect`, `individual flexibilities for change`, `Ethnic affect` and `individual experience in role`.
- Different Individual characteristics were relevant to explain `org. inclusive satisfaction` compared to Irish and FGC sample, such as `Individual Illness affect`, `individual flexibilities for change`, `Ethnic affect` and `individual experience in role`.

7. Dynamic augmentative Delphi method on users and employees' priorities

Objective of the analysis and alignment with the general DIAMOND's methodology

The objective of this analysis of users and employees' priorities data based on Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) analysis is to get a final weighted hierarchy of Fairness characteristics (FCs) of level 1 and 2 gathered through the Dynamic Argumentative Delphi (DAD) Survey, considering people's preferences defined according to several pairwise comparisons (see Figure Figure 2. DIAMOND's data analysis methodological flowchart.). This analysis is included in the next part of the general overall methodology of the Diamond's project (see Figure Figure 1. DIAMOND's overall methodology.).

The DAD survey, already described in the project's deliverable D3.2, is a tool that collects qualitative data about users' and employees' perception to assess priorities about different fairness and inclusiveness characteristics associated with the service and or employment experience they may express. Surveys are prepared based on the procedures defined in the AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) methodology, which do pairwise comparisons between fairness characteristics level 1 and level 2 influencing each use case to establish priorities.

Since for the DIAMOND project is of vital importance to weight and hierarchize the FCs for each use case from an aggregated point of view but also from an intersectional one, a second part of the survey consists of a sociodemographic questionnaire, to collect the mandatory information to be able to establish the ranking of preferences for every specific profile. This questionnaire was developed in consensus with the TinNGo project (the other project participant in the *MG-4-3-2018: Demographic change and participation of women in transport project* call in the H2020 Work Programme 2018-2020 Smart, green and integrated transport) as a potential issue that allows unify the progress achieved in both projects.

The four online DIAMOND DAD surveys, one per use case, are available on the project webpage (<https://diamond-project.eu/survey-gender-inclusive-transport/>) and were translated into 6 languages (Spanish, French, Serbian, Polish, English and Italian) to cover the population of all the project partners so as to gather broad information from the European preferences for women.

Considering participants are required and the need to compare a large number of factors between them leads to a large number of comparisons and responses, a user engagement strategy was developed. Although all the strategies are deeply explained in the D3.2, a brief summary is below:

- The innovative snowball approaches. Participants, considered as seeds, were recruited in a face-to-face event where they were explained the aim of the survey and were asked to fill it. After that, they were encouraged to engage other 3 participants to also fill the survey and so on.

- Social media. Spreading the link of the survey in the social networks of all the DIAMOND partners and in several specific entities related to the topic of each use case according to the communication plan developed.
- E-mailing. Sending the link to several contacts.
- Newsletter. Spreading the survey in the corporative newsletter of the partners following the instructions defined in the communication plan.

The aim of the D4.3 Computational analysis report is to explain the methods used in the analysis and what are the main results coming from it. Regarding the DAD is an online survey and it will remain continuously updated over time, the analysis was performed by using the responses collected up to 20th of May 2020 for each use case and each language. Table 52 shows that 531 surveys analysed which is in total, being 285 surveys about the preferences for the railways infrastructures (UC1), 94 for autonomous vehicles (UC2), 74 for bicycle sharing services (UC3) and 78 for employment in the transport sector (UC4).

Table 52. Number of respondents to the DAD surveys in the analysis performed in June 2020

	UC-I	UC-II	UC-III	UC-IV	TOTAL
SPAIN	60	24	15	21	120
ITALY	3	1	0	0	4
SERBIA	27	12	6	6	51
POLAND	80	27	25	26	158
FRANCE	78	11	11	13	113
ENGLAND	37	19	17	12	85
TOTAL	285	94	74	78	531

In Ireland there is no data collected and in Italy there are only 4 surveys. The reason is that in Italy respondents filled the English version instead of the Italian one and the number of responses is counted by languages and not by countries.

Methods

Traditional AHP vs Fuzzy AHP

Traditional AHP, proposed by Saaty (Saaty, 1980), is a method for ranking decision alternatives and selecting the best one when the decision maker has multiple criteria (Taylor, 2004).

The application of the AHP to the complex problem usually involves four major steps (Cheng, Yang, & Hwang, 1999):

1. Break down the complex problem into a number of small constituent elements and then structure the elements in a hierarchical form.
2. Make a series of pairwise comparisons among the elements according to a ratio scale.
3. Use the eigenvalue method to estimate the relative weights of the elements.

4. Aggregate these relative weights and synthesize them for the final measurement of given decision alternatives.

Classical AHP does not consider the uncertainty of some decision-making problems and cannot reflect the human thinking style (Özdağoğlu & Özdağoğlu, 2007). To solve these different modifications two AHP have been developed. The fuzzy AHP technique can be considered an advanced analytical method developed from the traditional AHP (Özdağoğlu & Özdağoğlu, 2007). Despite the AHP analyses both quantitative and qualitative criteria of multi-criteria decision-making problems based on decision makers judgments, fuzziness and vagueness existing in many decision-making problems may contribute to the imprecise judgments of decision makers in conventional AHP approaches (Bouyssou et al., 2000). For more details of the Fuzzy AHP method, see Section 3.2.3.2 of D2.1 Use Case Definition. Both AHP and fuzzy AHP were applied to the data obtained in order to compare results and establish the method that better allows us the identification of respondents' preferences.

Methodology for the data analysis through AHP

Hereafter it is explained in detail the methodology used to analyse the qualitative data about users' and employees' perception also including some parts of the scripts developed for the calculation.

Merging and translating data

The Typeform platform collects the results gathered for the DAD survey, providing separated Excel files for each use case and language, what means that there are 24 different Excel files (1 per each of the 6 languages and each of the 4 use cases).

Since the FCs level 1 and level 2 are different for each use case, the analysis to hierarchize and weight should be done separately for each one. Therefore, before starting the analysis the different languages should be **merged into one document** that contains the information all together.

Due to ethical aspects, in France it was not possible to ask about participants' sexual orientation, religion or ethnicity, so little manipulation was required in the French dataset before merging all the languages.

Once all data was merged into one dataset, an algorithm was developed to **translate** the information for each column **into English**.

Filtering according to the profile analysed

It was developed a VBA (Visual Basic for Applications) code to automatize filtering the data according to a desired profile:

- For the intersectional analysis, first it is required to filter the sociodemographic information according to the desired profile and later press the button prepared to automatically copy the responses from these specific respondents in a separate sheet.

- For the aggregated analysis, all the information should be analysed and there is no need to press any button.

Fuzzy AHP and AHP analysis

To analyse the data (before starting with Fuzzy AHP or AHP analysis) it was mandatory to convert responses into Saaty's scale and build AHP pairwise comparison matrices of FCs for each respondent (see Table 53 as an example).

Table 53. Example of a pairwise comparison matrix

	FC1	FC2	FC3	FC11
FC1	1	3	5	1
FC2	1/3	1	2	1/3
FC3	1/5	1/2	1	1/5
FC11	1	3	5	1

For the matrices obtained for each respondent it is calculated the **consistency ratio** using the Eq. 1.

$$CR = \frac{(\lambda_{max} - n) / (n - 1)}{RI} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Being λ_{max} the larger or principal eigenvalue of matrix A, n the number of responses and RI is the Random Index which is an experimental value that depends on n .

- Respondents with a $CR < 0.1$ were considered in the analysis,
- Respondents with a $CR \geq 0.1$ are removed for being inconsistent.

A MATLAB function was developed to calculate the consistency ratio and only keep the consistent respondents from the data set for further steps of the analysis. It should be noted that the consistency ratio is calculated for each comparison matrix, and each respondent has different comparison matrices (one for each cluster of criteria, e.g. all level 1 criteria will have one matrix, and level 2 criteria within a specific level 1 criterion will also have their matrix). To avoid losing data, if one respondent only has one consistent matrix, the responses related to the matrix are kept and used in the further steps of the analysis. So as to determine the **representativeness of the sample**, the **confidence level** (α) and the **power of test** ($1 - \beta$), another MATLAB script was developed. If the number of consistent responses is less than 20 then α and β both must be approximated using binomial probabilistic distribution function but if it is more than 20 then normal cumulative probabilistic distribution must be used. For more details about the theoretical calculation of these values, see Section 3.2.3.2.1 in D2.1 Use Case definition.

Figure 176 and Figure 177 show the MATLAB functions to estimate the confidence level and the power of the test.


```

function alfa = significance(FC)
% Variable FC is consistant values coloum. For example FC = c12 will give the significane of c12
coloum.
n = length(FC); % Calculates the Number of consistant respondents(Nt)
% Calculates the Number of respondents Preferred C1 over C2.
if geomean(FC) <= 1
    x = sum(FC < 1);
elseif geomean(FC) > 1
    x = sum(FC > 1);
end

p = 8/17; % Probability of selecting more than 1 or less than 1.
mu = n*p;
sigma = sqrt(n*p*(1 - p)); % Standerd deviation

if n<= 20 % Binomial
    i = 0;
    syms i
    alfa = double(symsum((factorial(n)/(factorial(i)*factorial(n-i))*(p)^i*(1-p)^(n-i)), i, 0,
x));
elseif n>20 % Normal
    alfa = (1 + erf((x - mu)/(sigma*sqrt(2))))/2;
end
end

```

Figure 176. MATLAB function to estimate confidence level

```

function power = betapower(FC)
n = length(FC); % Calculates the Number of consistant respondents(Nt)
if geomean(FC) <= 1
    x = sum(FC < 1); % Calculates the Number of respondents answered mode
elseif geomean(FC) > 1
    x = sum(FC > 1);
end
% Calculates the Number of respondents answered mode
p = 8/17; % Probability(Pi)
mu1 = n*(1-p);
sigma = sqrt(n*p*(1 - p)); % Standerd deviation

if n<= 20 % Binomial
    i = 0;
    syms i
    beta = double(symsum((factorial(n)/(factorial(i)*factorial(n-i))*(1-p)^i*(p)^(n-i)), i, 0,
n-x));
    power = beta;
elseif n>20 % Normal
    beta = (1 + erf((x - mu1)/(sigma*sqrt(2))))/2;
    power = 1-beta;
end
end

```

Figure 177. MATLAB function to estimate power of the test

It is worth saying that for these calculations of the confidence level and the power of the test, as can be seen in the algorithms detailed in Figures 176 and 177, all respondents answering “1”, what means the criterion C_i is equal important that the criterion C_j are not considered in the calculation of the confidence level, which is only focussed on respondents preferring C_i to C_j or vice versa (variable “x”), while they are included in the calculation of the number of expected respondents (variable “mu”) answering that C_i is preferred to C_j or C_j is preferred to C_i .

As there are a lot of respondents answering “1”, this is the reason of the low confidence level in some results.

After these previous calculations and keeping only the consistent responses, the hierarchical analysis can start to calculate the weight of the FCs level 1 and level 2. The following steps are focused on the MATLAB scripts used in the analysis but not in the theoretical framework of the calculation which is already described in Section 3.2.3.2 in D2.1:

1. For fuzzy AHP, Saaty scale (in which each category has only one value), is translated into fuzzy values using the correspondence shown in Table 54 for each consistent response.

Table 54. Fuzzy values to convert Saaty scale

Categories (conventional AHP value)	Triangular FAHP (a_{ij})	Reciprocal numbers FAHP (a_{ij}^{-1})
Equally important (1)	1,1,1,	1,1,1,
Intermediate preference between 1 and 3 (2)	1,2,3	1/3,1/2,1
Moderately more important (3)	2,3,4	1/4,1/3,1/2
Intermediate preference between 3 and 5 (4)	3,4,5	1/5,1/4,1/3
Strongly more important (5)	4,5,6	1/6,1/5,1/4
Intermediate preference between 5 and 7 (6)	5,6,7	1/7,1/6,1/5
Very strong more important (7)	6,7,8	1/8,1/7,1/6
Intermediate preference between 7 and 9 (8)	7,8,9	1/9,1/8,1/7
Extremely more important (9)	8,9,9	1/9,1/9,1/8

2. To transform the matrix coming from all the responses into one collective response two type of normalization have been suggested: (i) by using the mode and (ii) by using the geometric mean. After analysing the results, the geometric mean provided better results

because the calculation with the mode did not give a hierarchy. Figure 178 shows an example of the algorithm developed.

```

A2(1,1) = geomean(TFN55(:,1)); A2(1,2) = geomean(TFN55(:,2)); A2(1,3) = geomean(TFN55(:,3));
A2(1,4) = geomean(TFN56(:,1)); A2(1,5) = geomean(TFN56(:,2)); A2(1,6) = geomean(TFN56(:,3));
A2(1,7) = geomean(TFN57(:,1)); A2(1,8) = geomean(TFN57(:,2)); A2(1,9) = geomean(TFN57(:,3));

A2(2,1) = 1/A2(1,6); A2(2,2) = 1/A2(1,5); A2(2,3) = 1/A2(1,4);
A2(2,4) = geomean(TFN66(:,1)); A2(2,5) = geomean(TFN66(:,2)); A2(2,6) = geomean(TFN66(:,3));
A2(2,7) = geomean(TFN67(:,1)); A2(2,8) = geomean(TFN67(:,2)); A2(2,9) = geomean(TFN67(:,3));

A2(3,1) = 1/A2(1,9); A2(3,2) = 1/A2(1,8); A2(3,3) = 1/A2(1,7);
A2(3,4) = 1/A2(2,9); A2(3,5) = 1/A2(2,8); A2(3,6) = 1/A2(2,7);
A2(3,7) = geomean(TFN77(:,1)); A2(3,8) = geomean(TFN77(:,2)); A2(3,9) = geomean(TFN77(:,3));

3,7) = geomean(TFNA33(:,1)); AA(3,8) = geomean(TFNA33(:,2)); AA(3,9) = geomean(TFNA33(:,3));
    
```

Figure 178. MATLAB algorithm to create pairwise comparison matrix using geometric mean for obtaining collective response

3. Calculate the synthetic extent value (Figure 179).

```

%Calculation of Mg
%Criterias C1 to C4
%Lower value
l1 = A1(1,1) + A1(1,4) + A1(1,7) + A1(1,10);
l2 = A1(2,1) + A1(2,4) + A1(2,7) + A1(2,10);
l3 = A1(3,1) + A1(3,4) + A1(3,7) + A1(3,10);
l4 = A1(4,1) + A1(4,4) + A1(4,7) + A1(4,10);
%Model value
m1 = A1(1,2) + A1(1,5) + A1(1,8) + A1(1,11);
m2 = A1(2,2) + A1(2,5) + A1(2,8) + A1(2,11);
m3 = A1(3,2) + A1(3,5) + A1(3,8) + A1(3,11);
m4 = A1(4,2) + A1(4,5) + A1(4,8) + A1(4,11);
%Upper value
u1 = A1(1,3) + A1(1,6) + A1(1,9) + A1(1,12);
u2 = A1(2,3) + A1(2,6) + A1(2,9) + A1(2,12);
u3 = A1(3,3) + A1(3,6) + A1(3,9) + A1(3,12);
u4 = A1(4,3) + A1(4,6) + A1(4,9) + A1(4,12);

%%Sum(Mg)
% Criterias C1 to C4
sum_l = l1+l2+l3+l4;
sum_m = m1+m2+m3+m4;
sum_u = u1+u2+u3+u4;
%Fuzzy synthetic extent value
S1 = [l1./sum_u m1./sum_m u1./sum_l];
S2 = [l2./sum_u m2./sum_m u2./sum_l];
S3 = [l3./sum_u m3./sum_m u3./sum_l];
S4 = [l4./sum_u m4./sum_m u4./sum_l];
    
```

Figure 179. MATLAB algorithm for estimation of fuzzy synthetic extent value

4. Use the FAHP rules for the identification of the degree of possibility by comparing two fuzzy numbers (Figure 180).


```

% Degree of possibility of C2 greater any other criteria in C1 to C4
V12 = degreeofpossibility(S1,S2);
V13 = degreeofpossibility(S1,S3);
V14 = degreeofpossibility(S1,S4);
% Degree of possibility of C2 greater any other criteria in C1 to C4
V21 = degreeofpossibility(S2,S1);
V23 = degreeofpossibility(S2,S3);
V24 = degreeofpossibility(S2,S4);
% Degree of possibility of C3 greater any other criteria in C1 to C4
V31 = degreeofpossibility(S3,S1);
V32 = degreeofpossibility(S3,S2);
V34 = degreeofpossibility(S3,S4);
% Degree of possibility of C4 greater any other criteria in C1 to C4
V41 = degreeofpossibility(S4,S1);
V42 = degreeofpossibility(S4,S2);
V43 = degreeofpossibility(S4,S3);
% Degre of possibility vector for each criteria.
V_C1 = [V12 V13 V14];
V_C2 = [V21 V23 V24];
V_C3 = [V31 V32 V34];
V_C4 = [V41 V42 V43];

```

Figure 180. MATLAB algorithm to identify degree of possibility

5. Calculate the degree of possibility (Figure 181).

```

%%STEP-5 Weight Vector
W1 = min(V_C1);
W2 = min(V_C2);
W3 = min(V_C3);
W4 = min(V_C4);

W_sum = W1+W2+W3+W4;

W5 = min(V_C5);
W6 = min(V_C6);
W7 = min(V_C7);

W_summ = W5+W6+W7;

W8 = min(V_C8);
W9 = min(V_C9);

W_summm = W8+W9;

WA1 = min(VA_A1);
WA2 = min(VA_A2);
WA3 = min(VA_A3);

WA_sum = WA1+WA2+WA3;

```

Figure 181. MATLAB algorithm to obtain weight of each FC

6. Obtain the normalized weight vector (Figure 182)


```

%%STEP-6 Normalize weight Vector
W_C1 = W1./W_sum;
W_C2 = W2./W_sum;
W_C3 = W3./W_sum;
W_C4 = W4./W_sum;

W_C5 = W5./W_summ;
W_C6 = W6./W_summ;
W_C7 = W7./W_summ;

W_C8 = W8./W_summm;
W_C9 = W9./W_summm;

WA_A1 = WA1./WA_sum;
WA_A2 = WA2./WA_sum;
WA_A3 = WA3./WA_sum;
    
```

Figure 182. MATLAB algorithm to estimation normalized weight of each FC

Fuzzy AHP results allowed to get the most important Fairness Characteristic (FC) for each cluster (level 1 and level 2), but it didn't allowed to get a prioritization list of all the FCs.

To solve this AHP was used to obtain the priority list.

Figure 183 is a screenshot of MATLAB program that includes all the algorithms needed to obtain results:

Figure 183. MATLAB algorithm to estimate the normalized weight of each FC

Results

Once all the scripts needed to analyse the respondents' preferences for each use case were applied, a final Excel sheet is automatically provided with the results containing statistical information and the global weight for each FC level 1 and level 2 described in Section 7.1.2 (Figure 184 and Figure 185).

As it was said before, all calculations can be performed for the intersectional analysis by filtering those particular profiles from the sociodemographic information and for the aggregated analysis by using all the responses provided as output by the Typeform platform.

Figure 184. Excel with results after applying the MATLAB scripts

Figure 185. Weight and rank of the FCs

The global weight of the FCs is calculated by multiplying the local weight of the FCs level 2 and the local weight of its associated FC level 1. FCs level 1 were analysed in the present and the future. For the present scenario, it was determined in several focus groups that the local weight of the FCs level 1 is the same for all of them, while the future scenario was asked in the DAD survey. In the case of FCs level 2, they were only compared in the present scenario.

Use case I

The Use case I analysis was carried out with the 384 DAD surveys filled, being 178 of them answered by women, 106 by men, 1 transsexual men, 2 transsexual women, 9 non-binary people and 88 who prefer not to answer (Figure 186). The high number of respondents that prefer not to say their gender is because this question was not asked in France due to their ethical requirements.

Figure 186. Gender distribution for UCI DAD respondents

Aggregated analysis for the present scenario (Vertex I of the Inclusion Diamond):

Pairwise questions were prepared based on the hierarchical tree (see Annex I in D3.1 Methodology and Requirements for Data Collection). For the aggregated analysis 170 consistent respondents, from a total of 384, were used as data sample to perform AHP calculations and obtain the rank and the weights of the FCs level 2 in the present scenario, Figure 187 shows the hierarchy of fairness characteristics level 2 and their weights.

Railway stations - aggregated

Figure 187. Ranking and weights of the FCs level 2 for an aggregated analysis of UCI

The aggregated analysis was performed with 170 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 33.94%) with a confidence level of 0.50 and a power of the test of 0.45.

Overcrowding and emergency situations result to be the main concern for users of railway stations. So, safety and security issues are the main priority for railways users. The next more important aspects are *harassment and pickpocketing* (Criado-Perez, 2019) which is also linked with safety and security, followed by *Service availability* of the trains and the reliability on the level of service and its frequency. The *Universal design* that allows all kinds of people to move freely all over the space of the stations without any difficulty caused by stairs or any other inaccessible element and the *Cleanliness and maintenance* are also relevant issues. The full description of the FCs defined here can be found in D3.1. Methodology and Requirements for Data Collection.

Intersectional analysis for the present scenario (Vertex 1 of the Inclusion Diamond):

In addition to the aggregated analysis, some intersectional research was performed to determine which are the main factors for the different selected profiles and to determine if the criteria are similar or not than for the aggregated sample gathered. The MATLAB scripts prepared allow performing easily several analyses by filtering the sociodemographic characteristics, and, regarding DIAMOND project is focused on women's preferences, the profiles analysed were:

- Women,
- Women travelling with dependents,
- Women living in a suburban/rural area,
- Women with low wage incomes (less than 21000 €/year) and
- Women who have felt discriminated for their appearance.

Railway stations - Women

Figure 188. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women for UCI.

The analysis carried out to women was performed with 77 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 30.17%) with a confidence level of 0.29 and a power of the test of 0.25.

Women preferences are almost the same as than for all respondents (also including men), with the only difference that women consider more important *harassment and pickpocketing* than *service availability and efficiency* which is in the third position.

Going to a more specific profile such as women traveling with dependents such as children or elderly, it could be said that *Universal design* is the most relevant factor for this specific profile followed by *Overcrowding and emergency situations*.

Railway stations - Women travelling with dependents

Railway stations - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 189. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women travelling with dependents for UCI.

For women with annual incomes lower than 21,000 €/years, Ticketing options and fares is not included as one of the most relevant factors being Overcrowding and emergency situations the most weighted factor (Figure 190).

Railway stations - Women low wage earners

Figure 190. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women with income lower than 21k€ for UCI.

Regarding women living in an urban or suburban environment, they have the same preferences which is, Overcrowding and emergency situations is the most weighted factor. Another important aspect determined is they need to trust in the Service availability and efficiency of the service. (Figure 191).

Railway stations - Women living in rural areas

Figure 191. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women living in an urban or suburban environment for UCI.

Figure 192 analyses the preferences of women that in the sociodemographic questionnaire affirm that they have sometimes felt discriminated for her appearance. *Overcrowding and emergency situations* is, in the same way than all the other profiles regarding women (except for those travelling with dependents), the most relevant factor followed by the *Universal design*, *Service availability and efficiency*, *Harassment and pickpocketing* and finally *Cleanliness and maintenance*.

Railway stations - Discriminated Women

Figure 192. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women who have felt discriminated for her appearance for UCI.

Aggregated analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 4 of the Inclusion Diamond):

FCs level I were compared by putting the respondents in the hypothetical future scenario of hyperloop stations. AHP analysis show that the most important area is *Safety and security*, which can be easily understandable due to a new mode of transport should be reliable for travellers

followed by *Accessibility of the service* and finally the *Design of the infrastructure* (see Figure 193. *Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for UCI.* Figure 193).

Figure 193. *Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for UCI.*

The aggregated analyses were performed with 170 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 33.94%) with a confidence level of 0.50 and a power of the test of 0.45.

Intersectional analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 4 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Since the project is focused on analysing women's preferences, the same intersectional analysis than the one developed for the present scenario was performed in order to compare if there is any particular difference.

As can be seen from Figure 194 to Figure 198, for women *accessibility of the service* is the factor considered the most important.

Hyperloop- Women

Figure 194. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women in UCI.

The analysis carried out to women were performed with 77 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 30.17%) with a confidence level of 0.29 and a power of the test of 0.25.

Hyperloop - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 195. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women travelling with dependents in UCI.

Hyperloop - Women low wage earners

Figure 196. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women with income lower than 21€ in UCI.

Hyperloop - Women living in rural areas

Figure 197. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs in the future scenario identified for women living in an urban or suburban environment in UCI.

Hyperloop - Discriminated Women

Figure 198. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs in the future scenario identified for women who have felt discriminated for her appearance in UCI.

As it can be concluded, for all women profiles, *safety and security* is the main topic concern.

Use case 2

The Use case 2 analysis regarding the Autonomous vehicles was carried out with the 116 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020. The gender distribution was formed by 50 women, 44 men, 1 transsexual women, 1 transsexual men, 3 non-binary people and 17 people who prefer not to answer (being 16 of them French respondents, who, as it has been said in Section 2.3.1 are forbidden to provide this information for ethical issues. This information is shown in Figure 199 with percentages.

Figure 199. Gender distribution for UC2 DAD respondents

Although in this Use case the hierarchical tree is clearly defined (see D3.1), the definition of each FC scenario is determined one by one because some factors affect only to the present situation while others will affect only to future scenarios (see Table 55). Full description of the FCs can be found in D3.1.

Table 55. Scenarios for each FCs regarding if it is applicable up to L3 vehicles or L4+

FC	Present scenario	Future scenario
Safety and security	X	X
Comfort	X	X
Mobility	X	X
Economy	X	X
Environment	X	X
Design option	X	X
Accident rate	X	X
Human error	X	
Training	X	
Traffic management	X	X
Trust in technology	X	X
Simultaneity		X
Traffic efficiency	X	X
Travel time	X	X
Congestion	X	X
Accessibility		X

Monetary cost	X	X
Non-monetary cost	X	X
Vehicle efficiency	X	X
Noise	X	X
Emissions	X	X
Public health	X	X
Infrastructure		X
Vehicle shape	X	X
Vehicle behaviour	X	X
HMI (Human machine interface)	X	X

Aggregated analysis for the present scenario (Vertex 2 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Considering the responses of all the 116 participants, it can be said that 521 of them provided a consistent DAD survey. As explained in Section 7.1.2, the AHP analysis only considers consistent responses and removes the inconsistent ones as they do not provide reliable information about the preferences because those surveys could be done randomly.

Figure 200 determined that, from a total of 20 FCs, the 5 most important were, in order: *trust in technology, public health, non-monetary costs, emissions and vehicle behaviour.*

Autonomous vehicle L3 - aggregated

Figure 200. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for an aggregated analysis in the present scenario for UC2

The aggregated analysis was performed with 52 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 10.31%) with a confidence level of 0.17 and a power of the test of 0.83.

People consider that the main factor to increase the use of the present autonomous vehicles (up to L3 which are commercial types nowadays) is to *trust in technology*, a factor that is linked with being confident in the car that can drive by itself. The second factor in importance is related to *public health* regarding that they feel less stressed with certain advances (such as speed control, park assists, etc) autonomous cars have.

Respondents also give importance (the third position) to the *non-monetary costs* which are indirect costs such as the wear reduction produced by the new technologies due to the smoother driving. In these days when the population is increasingly aware of caring for the environment, *emissions* are also a prominent factor among the top 5 followed by the *vehicle behaviour* that autonomous vehicles have due to their control of accelerations and decelerations making driving smoother and therefore less aggressive.

Intersectional analysis for the present scenario (Vertex 2 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Once all responses were analysed, the intersectional analysis was carried out to know the preferences and their ranking for some interesting specific profiles (from Figure 201 to Figure 205).

The results indicate that:

- *Trust in technology* is the most important factor for women in general which is the same that occurs for the aggregated analysis.
- *Human error*, which usually turns into an accident, is not one of the most weighted factors, it is only relevant for discriminated women. It could be reasonable due to the driverless characteristic of the autonomous vehicles .

- *Public health* is revealed as the most relevant factor, being, for all the profiles analysed, in the Top 5 criteria. In fact, women travelling with dependents, low wage women earners and those who have felt discriminated for their appearance is the most important one.
- *Non-monetary cost* is considered the top criteria for those women that earn less than 21,000 €/year, following *Public health*, which can be comprehensible due to the connections among lack of income and the difficulties they may have in acquiring an autonomous vehicle, which today are high-class cars.
- Although *Monetary cost* might be thought to be one of the most relevant factors, it is only in the top 5 for women living in rural areas and for low wage earners.
- *Emissions* is relevant for all the women profiles analysed except for women living with dependents
- Surprisingly, no particular profile considers the *Accident rate* among the Top 5 criteria.
- *Vehicle behaviour* is only relevant for the aggregated analysis, for women and for women travelling with dependents.
- *Congestion* is only included as the top 5 criteria for discriminated women.

Autonomous vehicle L3 - Women

Figure 201. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women in the present scenario for UC2

The analysis carried out to women were performed with 22 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 8.54%) with a confidence level of 0.12 and a power of the test of 0.88.

Autonomous vehicle L3 - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 202. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women travelling with dependents in the present scenario for UC2

Autonomous vehicle L3 - Women low wage earners

Figure 203. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women with income lower than 21k€ in the present scenario for UC2

Autonomous vehicle L3 - Women living in rural areas

Figure 204. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women living in a rural or suburban environment in the present scenario for UC2

Autonomous vehicle L3 - Discriminated Women

Figure 205. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women who felt sometimes discriminated for their appearance in the present scenario for UC2

Aggregated analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 5 of the Inclusion Diamond):

After analysing the present scenario, it is the turn of the future scenario. As above mentioned, some FCs level 2 were also considered in the future scenario analysis as they can be also relevant for L4+ vehicles in addition to the FCs level 1 as happens in the other use cases (UC1, UC3 and UC4).

Initially analysing the overall ranking of level 2 FCs with influence in Vertex 5 (Figure 206), it can be seen that the top 5 most important FCs are: *public health, emissions, accident rate, , non-monetary costs and simultaneity.*

Autonomous vehicle +L4 - aggregated

Figure 206. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for an aggregated analysis in the future scenario for UC2

The aggregated analysis was performed with 52 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 10.31%) with a confidence level of 0.17 and a power of the test of 0.83.

After studying the FCs level 2 with influence in the future scenario, it was analysed the ranking of the FCs level 1 identified in the literature review and focus groups. For those cars that will not need the “driver” to take control at any time, the main importance is, as expected, for *safety and security* main group, followed by *environment, economy, mobility, comfort and design options* (Figure 207).

Level 1 FC - aggregated

Figure 207. Ranking and weights of the level 1 FC identified for an aggregated analysis in the future scenario for UC2

With the same parameters as in the other aggregated analyses.

Intersectional analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 5 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Following the same order than in the aggregated analysis, the first analysis described is the ranking of the FCs level 2 influencing in the L4+ vehicles (from Figure 208 to Figure 212).

The main results obtained after the analysis are:

- *Simultaneity*, which is the option that driverless vehicles offer to perform more than one task at the same time because the car drives by itself, is the most important factor for women living in rural areas, probably due to the fact that they have to travel long distances to perform their daily tasks such as shopping, going to work or going with their children to school.
- The same than for the present scenario, *non-monetary cost* is the main factor considered by women with low incomes.
- *Public health*, factor linked with driving without stress and being relaxed during the trips, is the main factor for the global population, for women travelling with dependents and for discriminated women.
- Once more, like in the present scenario, the ranking of the factors is different regarding the profile analysed, but *non-monetary cost* is repeated for all except for women travelling with dependents and *Public Health* except for women living in rural areas

Autonomous vehicle +L4 - Women

Figure 208. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women in the future scenario for UC2.

Autonomous vehicle +L4 - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 209. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women travelling with dependents in the future scenario for UC2.

Autonomous vehicle +L4 - Women low wage earners

Figure 210. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women with an income lower than 21k€ in the future scenario for UC2.

Autonomous vehicle +L4 - Women living in rural areas

Figure 211. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women living in rural and suburban environment in the future scenario for UC2.

Autonomous vehicle +L4 - Discriminated Women

Figure 212. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FC identified for women who felt discriminated sometimes in the future scenario for UC2.

Analysing the ranking of FCs level I (from Figure 213 to Figure 217) it can be said that:

- In general, *safety and security* are the most relevant factor (except for discriminated women that selected the *environment*) and the last factor in the top 5 is the *design options*.
- For women travelling with dependents, *mobility* is more preferred than *environment*.
- For discriminated women, the binomial *environment* and *economy* are more preferred than *safety & security*.
- For non-urban women the *economy* is more relevant than the *environment*. Whereas for women with annual incomes lower than 21K€ the *environment* is more weighted than *economy*,

Level 1 FC -Women

Figure 213. Ranking and weights of the level I FC identified for women in the future scenario for UC2

Level 1 FC - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 214. Ranking and weights of the level 1 FC identified for women travelling with dependents in the future scenario for UC2

Level 1 FC - Women low wage earners

Figure 215. Ranking and weights of the level 1 FC identified for women with an income lower than 21k€ in the future scenario for UC2

Level 1 FC - Women living in rural areas

Figure 216. Ranking and weights of the level 1 FC identified for women living in a rural or suburban environment in the future scenario for UC2

Level 1 FC - Discriminated Women

Figure 217. Ranking and weights of the level 1 FC identified for women who felt discriminated for their appearance in the future scenario for UC2

Use case 3

Use case 3 analysis regarding the bicycle sharing services was carried out with the 97 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020. The gender distribution was formed by 46 women, 33 men, 1 transsexual woman, 3 non-binary people and 14 who prefer not to answer (this number belongs to French respondents, who, as it was said in previous Sections, are forbidden to answer this question). This information is shown in Figure 218 with percentages.

Figure 218. Gender distribution for UC3 DAD respondents

According to the hierarchical tree established for UC3, the DAD asks people's preferences regarding the FCs level 2 in the present situation. Below, it can be found the results for the aggregated analysis (considering all the consistent responses regardless participant profile) and intersectional analysis (for several specific profiles selected taking into consideration those that were found relevant when analysing the UESI questionnaires).

Aggregated analysis for the present scenario (Vertex 1 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Having analysed the consistency of the responses collected for the Use case 3 of the DAD survey, 40 respondents were consistent from the 97 registered in Typeform.

After analysing the pairwise comparisons by Fuzzy and traditional AHP, the ranking and weights of the most relevant factors, the top 5, were *topography*, *weather*, *family responsibilities*, *peer influence*, and *negative perceptions* as can be seen in Figure 219.

Bike sharing - aggregated

Figure 219. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for an aggregated analysis of UC3.

The aggregated analysis was performed with 40 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 7.98%) with a confidence level of 0.23 and a power of the test of 0.77.

Taking into account that cyclists move the bicycle by pedalling with their legs, it is not strange to obtain that *topography* is the factor that most influences the use of this service. The second most prominent factor is the *weather*, since many people do not use the bicycle service when the weather conditions are extreme (either because it is snowy, it rains, or it is extremely hot).

Family responsibilities are the third factor. Caring of children and elderly are a handicap for cycling because it is not very common that these sharing services provide bicycles adapted for the companions and makes no option to use them.

Public education and awareness campaign about the recognition of cycling as an acceptable mode of transport (*peer influence*) is another relevant aspect, followed by the *negative perceptions* that are linked with the public awareness campaigns on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods.

Intersectional analysis for the present scenario (Vertex I of the Inclusion Diamond):

Once all consistent individuals were analysed, intersectional analysis were carried out to know the preferences and their ranking for some interesting specific profiles related to women which are the group of people in which this project is centred (from Figure 220 to Figure 224).

The results indicate that:

- *Topography* is the most relevant factor for all the analysis, except for the women living in rural areas that give more importance to *Weather*. This is an expected result due to the

fact that people living far from the urban areas need to travel longer distances and without buildings or other city elements that could protect people from rain, wind or snow.

- All the women profiles reveal *topography*, *weather* and *family responsibilities* as the top 3 (the ranking differs depending on each profile), except discriminate women who include insufficient infrastructure instead of *Weather*
- Women who live in rural or suburban areas, complete the 5 main factors with *peer influence* and *negative perceptions* following the pattern of the aggregated analysis, but women, women travelling with dependents express their concern with *peer influence* and *insufficient infrastructures* as top criteria.

Bike sharing - Women

Figure 220. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women for UC3.

The analysis carried out to women were performed with 21 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 7.86%) with a confidence level of 0.37 and a power of the test of 0.63.

Bike sharing - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 221. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women travelling with dependents for UC3.

Bike sharing - Women low wage earners

Figure 222. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women with income lower than 21k€ for UC3.

Bike sharing - Women living in rural areas

Figure 223. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women living in an urban or suburban environment for UC3.

Bike sharing - Discriminated Women

Figure 224. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women who have felt discriminated for her appearance for UC3.

Aggregated analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 4 of the Inclusion Diamond):

No questions were asked in Use Case 3 about the future scenario regarding the future scenarios analysed in the DIAMOND project are based on the Bohemia report (European Commission, 2017) and there is no information about this topic.

Intersectional analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 4 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Idem as for ‘Aggregated analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 4 of the Inclusion Diamond)’ Section.

Use case 4

The Use case 4 analysis regarding employment was carried out with the 100 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020. The gender distribution was formed by 48 women, 29 men, 3 transsexual women, 2 non-binary people and 18 who prefer not to answer (French participants are forbidden to answer this question). This information is shown in *Figure 225* with percentages.

Figure 225. Gender distribution for UC4 DAD respondents

Below, it can be found the results for the aggregated analysis (considering all the consistent responses regardless participant profile) and intersectional analysis (for several specific profiles selected taking into consideration those that were found relevant when analysing the UESI questionnaires).

Aggregated analysis for the present scenario (Vertex 3 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Pairwise comparison questions were prepared based on the hierarchical tree (see Annex I of D3.1). For the aggregated analysis performed for this UC, the number of consistent respondents were 53 from a total of 100. After performing the analysis with the consistent responses, it was obtained the rank and the weights of the FCs level 2 in the present. *Figure 226* shows those FCs with the highest weights (top 5).

Employment - aggregated

Figure 226. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for an aggregated analysis of UC4.

The aggregated analysis was performed with 53 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 10.56%) with a confidence level of 0.0013 and a power of the test of 0.99.

According to AHP results those fairness characteristics level 2 with higher importance were, *caring and parenting responsibilities*, *demand factors in job recruitment*, *policy and legal issues*, *access to resources* and *job segregation*. As can be seen, the role of people who are in charge of kids or elderly is the most relevant aspect when applying or working in the transport sector, followed by demand factors in job recruitment, in which procedures unfortunately sometimes men and women are not considered as equal, including also aspects of promotion and the design of the jobs.

Intersectional analysis for the present scenario (Vertex 3 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Once all consistent individuals were analysed, intersectional analysis were carried out to know the preferences and their ranking for some interesting specific profiles related to women which are the group of people in which this project is centred (from Figure 227 to Figure 232).

The results indicate that:

- Women in general and in particular those travelling with dependents and with low incomes (in the same way than the aggregated analysis pattern) indicates that *caring and parenting responsibilities* is the most important issue to access to a job in the transport sector. However, women living with dependents feel difficulties in *access to resources* and they consider having problems due to the recruitment process is not gender neutral.
- Women living in rural or suburban areas give more importance to the *job segregation* regarding they do not feel all jobs were available and suitable for both men and women (and there was a more equal balance between genders across all occupations, levels and jobs in transport).

- *Economic deprivation* is in the top 5 criteria for most women specific profiles but not in the general analysis that includes the preferences of all the women participants.
- In general, it could be said that there is quite a diverse ranking of relevant criteria for the different studied profiles, and no one is repeated in all of them.

Employment - Women

Figure 227. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women for UC4.

The analysis carried out for women was performed with 28 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 10.8%) with a confidence level of 0.0097 and a power of the test of 0.99033.

Employment - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 228. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women travelling with dependents for UC4.

Employment - Women living with dependents

Figure 229. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women living with dependents for UC4.

Employment - Women low wage earners

Figure 230. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women with income lower than 21k€ for UC4.

Employment - Women living in rural areas

Figure 231. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women living in an urban or suburban environment for UC4.

Employment - Discriminated Women

Figure 232. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs identified for women who have felt discriminated for her appearance for UC4.

Aggregated analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 6 of the Inclusion Diamond):

FCs level I were compared putting the respondents in a hypothetical future scenario, the use of drones. With 53 consistent respondents, a representativeness of the sample of 10.5% and a 0.0013 confidence level of the results, AHP analysis show that the ranking of these FCs is: *individual characteristics, job characteristics, socio-economic conditions and personal circumstances* (Figure 233).

Employment (future scenario) - aggregated

Figure 233. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for UC4.

Intersectional analysis for the future scenario (Vertex 6 of the Inclusion Diamond):

Regarding the analysis in the future scenario of different women profiles (from Figure 234 to Figure 239), results indicates that:

- The *job characteristics* and the *individual characteristics* are a key factor in the employment in the transport system for all kind of profiles.

Employment (future scenario) - Women

Figure 234. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women in UC4.

The analysis carried out for women was performed with 28 consistent respondents (representativeness of the sample 10.8%) with a confidence level of 0.0097 and a power of the test of .099.

Employment (future scenario) - Women travelling with dependents

Figure 235. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women travelling with dependents in UC4.

Employment (future scenario) - Women living with dependents

Figure 236. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women living with dependents in UC4.

Employment (future scenario) - Women low wage earners

Figure 237. Ranking and weights of the FCs in the future scenario for women with income lower than 21k€ in UC4.

Employment (future scenario) - Women living in rural areas

Figure 238. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs in the future scenario identified for women living in an urban or suburban environment in UC4.

Employment (future scenario) - Discriminated Women

Figure 239. Ranking and weights of the top 5 FCs in the future scenario identified for women who have felt discriminated for her appearance in UC4.

8. Global Service and employers' provision data analysis: Bayesian network analysis and ANOVA analysis on service provisions

Objective of the analysis and alignment with the general DIAMOND's methodology

The objective of this analysis of global service and employers' provision data is:

- on the one hand, Bayesian Network analysis to get a final weighted hierarchy of Fairness characteristics (FCs) level 3 by multiplying the weights obtained in this analysis for the present scenarios described in this section with the AHP weights that were obtained by the analysis detailed in section 2 for the FCs level 1 and 2. Data gathered from Open Structured Data, Proprietary Structured Data, Observations and UESI questionnaires (detailed in D4.1 Datasets description) are analysed all together with the Bayesian Network analysis to rank and weight all the level 3 FCs. A total of 522 responses were analysed for UC-I, 20 for UC-II, 201 for UC-III and 165 for UC-IV;
- on the other hand, by using the same number of responses as in the Bayesian Network analysis, ANOVA test to identify, through a systematic and automatized analysis, those characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual (PI) which exhibit significant differences when assessing satisfaction with the transport system. This ANOVA test will allow a better interdisciplinary analysis and a better generation of Fairness measures for critical profiles obtained as a set of relevant characteristics of the PI.

Figure 1 shows how this analysis fits in the general overall methodology of the DIAMOND's project and it also shows in more detail in the methodological flowchart of the data analysis (Fig. 2).

Methods

Bayesian Networks

The methodology to analyse the Service and employers' provision data and its mathematical development can be seen in the section 3.2.3.1 in D2.1 'Use cases definition'.

Bayesian network analysis was carried out using:

1. Open Markov-0.3.4
2. Julia 1.0. for the automatization of the process to perform the analysis for different polyhedral individual (PI) profiles.

There are two main types of Bayesian network learning methods: parametric learning and structural learning methods. Parametric learning consists in the obtainment of the conditional probabilities given by the structure of the network using the observed frequencies on the database, while structural learning tries to find the graph that best represents the probability distribution of a given database. Within this analysis, since our aim is to obtain the graphical representation and the interdependencies between level 3 FCs, we will use the structural learning methods. At the same time, within the structural learning methods there are two main types, the first one, independence-based or constraint-based methods which consist of detecting the probabilistic conditional independencies present in the database, one of the most famous algorithms pertaining to this type is the PC algorithm (Spirtes and Glymour, 1991). On the other hand, the second type of methods are called search and score methods, although they have also been called methods based on heuristic search. This second type of method consists of performing a heuristic search through the space of possible structures using a metric that measures how well each structure can represent the probability distribution of the variables in the database. Several metrics have been used in the literature: Bayesian (which include, e.g., K2, Bayesian Information criterion (BIC), Bayesian Dirichlet equivalent uniform (BDe)), cross-entropy, Akaike information criterion (AIC), or minimum description length (MDL) (Schwarz 1978, Scutari et al. 2019, Bermejo et al. 2012), between others.

K2 metric (Eq.1) was used for the Bayesian network analysis shown in this study in order to determine the dependencies among the different level 3 FCs for each use case of women (women definition can be seen in D2.1). This algorithm analyses the different combinations of responses among parents and children nodes in order to determine which is the network that provides the better results.

$$L = P(B_S, D) = P(B_S) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^{q_i} \frac{(r_i-1)!}{(N_{ij}+r_i-1)!} \cdot \prod_{k=1}^{r_i} N_{ijk}! \quad (\text{Eq.1})$$

Being:

- $P(B_S)$ the probability to obtain the network B_S (initially all B_S are considered to have the same probability and so $P(B_S)$ is $1/\text{number of possible networks}$),
- n the number of variables,
- r_i the number of possible values per each variable x_i ,
- q_i the number of possible configurations of the parents (given the network B_S) of the variable x_i . Being *configuration of parents* the following: If we consider a network B_S where variable i has 2 parents, a configuration is the adoption of a specific value per each of these parents (for instance: 1,5).
- N_{ij} is the number of times that parents of variable i are adopting a specific configuration j . For example: If we consider a network B_S where the variable i has 2 parents, N_{ij} will be the number of times that these parents have the configuration j or specific values (for instance: 1 and 5).
- N_{ijk} is the number of times that variable i is adopting a specific value (for instance 2) when the parent variables are adopting the configuration j (for instance 1 and 5). For example: When the two parent variables adopt values 1 and 5, variable i is adopting 2 times the value 2. In this case $N_{ijk} = 2$.

Using the logarithmic expression, we obtain what we called the Bayes score or K2 score, and the obtained expression can be seen in equation 2; the use of logarithmic expression, and then only of addition and subtraction operations results in computational run time savings.

$$Bayes\ score = \log[L] = \log(P(B_S)) + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{q_i} \left(\log \left(\frac{(r_i - 1)!}{(N_{ij} + r_i - 1)!} + \sum_{k=1}^{r_i} \log(N_{ijk}!) \right) \right) \quad (Eq. 2)$$

Bayes score or K2 score can be also defined using the logarithmic gamma function (lgamma) (see equation 3), which is easier to use in computation.

$$Bayes\ score = \log(P(B_S)) + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^{q_i} \left(\lgamma(r_i) - \lgamma(N_{ij} + r_i) + \sum_{k=1}^{r_i} \lgamma(N_{ijk} + 1) \right) \quad (Eq. 3)$$

Figure 240. Bayes score of the Bayesian network

To develop the Bayesian network analysis, an open-source program called Open Markov 0.3.4 was used. OpenMarkov allows us to use the PC algorithm (independence-based method) or the hill climbing algorithm (score-based method). Since previous works (Cooper and Herskovits, 1992) have reported that the use of PC algorithm is not appropriate for dense graphs with many variables, we selected to use the Hill climbing algorithm (Friedman et al., 1999; Díez et al. 2018, Bermejo et al., 2012; Gámez et al., 2011) with the K2 metric and an alpha parameter (Laplace-like correction) of 0.5.

Figure 241. Hill climbing algorithm (published in Gámez et al. 2011) shows the hill climbing algorithm. In order to start building the graphical representation the algorithm starts with all the nodes but without any arc or edge between them (G_0), or with a predefined structure. Then, at

each next step the algorithm only considers local changes, i.e. neighbour directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) (G_i) which have been created performing one arc addition, one arc deletion or one arc reversal; and chooses the one resulting in the greatest improvement in the scoring function f . The algorithm stops when there is no local change yielding an improvement in f . Because of this greedy behaviour for the obtainment of the network, the hill climbing algorithm has two main limitations (Ramírez Hereza 2020):

- The solution obtained may be a local optimum rather than a global optimum. This happens when there is not any neighbour with a higher score than that of the current network. However, the structure obtained does not represent the real structure.
- Presence of a plateau. This happens when the neighbour structures are equivalent to the current structure, and then, all of them have the same score.

Some methods to avoid this is the use of greedy search with random restarts, or random perturbations of the structure when getting stuck at a local maximum (Lerner and Malka 2011).

Algorithm 1: Structural learning of BNs by using a hill climbing (HC) algorithm

Input: D : A dataset defined over variables $\mathbf{V} = \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$
Input: \mathcal{G}_0 : A DAG defined over \mathbf{V} used as the starting point for the search
Output: A DAG \mathcal{G} being the graphical part of network \mathcal{B}

```

1  $\mathcal{G} \leftarrow \mathcal{G}_0$ ;
2  $f_{\mathcal{G}} \leftarrow f(\mathcal{G} : D)$  // *
3 [r]  $f$ : decomposable scoring metric improvement  $\leftarrow$  true;
4 while improvement do
5   improvement  $\leftarrow$  false;
6   // *
7   [h] neighbors generated by addition
8   For each node  $X_i$  and each node  $X_j \notin Pa_{\mathcal{G}}(X_i)$  such that  $X_j \rightarrow X_i$  does not
9   introduce a directed cycle in  $\mathcal{G}$ , compute the difference
10   $diff = f(\mathcal{G} + \{X_j \rightarrow X_i\} : D) - f_{\mathcal{G}}$ . Store the change which maximizes  $diff$  in
11   $\langle change_a, diff_a \rangle$ ;
12  // *
13  [h] neighbors generated by deletion
14  For each node  $X_i$  and each node  $X_j \in Pa_{\mathcal{G}}(X_i)$ , compute the difference
15   $diff = f(\mathcal{G} - \{X_j \rightarrow X_i\} : D) - f_{\mathcal{G}}$ . Store the change which maximizes  $diff$  in
16   $\langle change_d, diff_d \rangle$ ;
17  // *
18  [h] neighbors generated by reversal
19  For each node  $X_i$  and each node  $X_j \in Pa_{\mathcal{G}}(X_i)$  such that reversing  $X_j \rightarrow X_i$  does
20  not introduce a directed cycle in  $\mathcal{G}$ , compute the difference  $diff = d_1 + d_2$  where  $d_1$ 
21  corresponds to  $f(\mathcal{G} - \{X_j \rightarrow X_i\} : D) - f_{\mathcal{G}}$  and  $d_2$  corresponds to
22   $f(\mathcal{G} + \{X_j \rightarrow X_i\} : D) - f_{\mathcal{G}}$ . Store the change which maximizes  $diff$  in
23   $\langle change_r, diff_r \rangle$ ;
24  // *
25  [h] Checking if improvement
26  Let  $d^* = \max_{k=a,d,r} diff_k$  and  $move^*$  its corresponding change;
27  if  $d^* > 0$  then
28    improvement  $\leftarrow$  true;
29     $\mathcal{G} \leftarrow$  apply  $move^*$  over  $\mathcal{G}$ ;
30     $f_{\mathcal{G}} \leftarrow f_{\mathcal{G}} + d^*$ ;
31  end
32 end
33 return  $\mathcal{G}$ ;
  
```

Figure 241. Hill climbing algorithm (published in Gámez et al. 2011)

After obtaining the graphical representation of the network, the weights of each FC was determined based on the depth of each node in the network (Awad-Núñez et al. 2016). For that, the minimum number of arcs going from each variable to the main parent was counted (in case there were more than one main parent, the number of arcs considered for each variable is the sum of the minimum number of arcs to each parent). The number of arcs set the importance of each variable within the graphical representation (Awad-Núñez et al. 2016). Those variables or nodes which are not influenced by other ones and influence other nodes are the roots or main parents of the network and are assigned an importance or score of 10, while the importance of the other nodes is assessed by the depth compared with the root of the network. Depth is related

to the number of steps to reach the roots or main partners (Awad-Núñez et al. 2016). If there are 15 layers: layer 1 receives a weight of 10; layer 15, a weight of 1; and intermediate layers, the corresponding linearly interpolated values (see Figure 242. Linear regression to assign Importance for each level based on the depth of each variable in the network). Those nodes that do not have any relation with other nodes are assigned an importance of zero. This does not mean that they are not important, but that they do not show to influence or be influenced, based on bayes probabilities, by any other variable within the data analysed.

Once the importance is obtained, the normalised weight of each variable or node in the network is obtained by dividing the importance of each variable by the sum of the importance of all the variables.

Figure 242. Linear regression to assign Importance for each level based on the depth of each variable in the network

Since the aim is to allow the future analysis for different profiles of the polyhedral individual, the process was automatized using the free Julia programming language ([The Julia Programming Language \(julia.org\)](http://The Julia Programming Language (julia.org))). For this automatization the K2 algorithm was used, instead of the Hill climbing algorithm. The main debility of this K2 algorithm is the sensibility to the initial order of nodes established by the user, that can be reduced if the order is established by an expert (Ramírez Hereza 2020); we introduced a random high number of iterations with different nodes order to overcome this drawback. Then, the selection of the K2 algorithm in the automatization of the calculation of the hierarchy of FCs in the DIAMOND project, which will be included in the Toolbox for further analysis with the updated databases in the future, is justified as follows:

- I. The programming needed to overcome the limitations of the method is easier for the K2 algorithm procedure:
 - a. To avoid the influence of the topological order of the variables in the K2 procedure is enough with programming a random initial ordering in a high number of iterations (until the convergence of the likelihood of the network or the score is obtained).

- b. To avoid the limitation to reach a local maximum when using the Hill climbing algorithm, it should be programmed with random changes in the DAG matrix, which is more complex from a computational point of view.
2. Very complete and already tested packages (building blocks) already exist for the K2 procedure that can be adapted to our analysis in the DIAMOND project, while the building blocks for the hill climbing algorithm are not that much developed and tested, especially when considering arbitrary modifications of the DAG to avoid local maximums.

Algorithms developed to automatize this process are based on the BLN (Bayesian learning of belief networks) method presented by Cooper and Herskovits in 1992 pp. 24, which include the K2 learning algorithm (see Figure 243 below) with the K2 metric, and they are based on the Bellman Ford algorithm to obtain the hierarchy of FCs level 3 through the automatic identification of the shortest path to the main parent per each node (Sulaiman et al 2018, Ekpanyapong et al. 2006). Regarding the computational time needed, it depends on the number of variables, which varies for each use case considered.

1. **procedure** K2;
2. {Input: A set of n nodes, an ordering on the nodes, an upper bound u on the
3. number of parents a node may have, and a database D containing m cases.}
4. {Output: For each node, a printout of the parents of the node.}
5. **for** $i := 1$ to n **do**
6. $\pi_i := \emptyset$;
7. $P_{old} := f(i, \pi_i)$; {This function is computed using Equation 20.}
8. OKToProceed := **true**;
9. **While** OKToProceed and $|\pi_i| < u$ **do**
10. let z be the node in $\text{Pred}(x_i) - \pi_i$ that maximizes $f(i, \pi_i \cup \{z\})$;
11. $P_{new} := f(i, \pi_i \cup \{z\})$;
12. **if** $P_{new} > P_{old}$ **then**
13. $P_{old} := P_{new}$;
14. $\pi_i := \pi_i \cup \{z\}$;
15. **else** OKToProceed := **false**;
16. **end** {while};
17. **write**('Node: ', x_i , ' Parent of x_i : ', π_i);
18. **end** {for};
19. **end** {K2};

Figure 243. K2 algorithm (published in Cooper and Herskovits, 1992)

For each use case, a different number of iterations was developed with five different tests for each of them in order to analyse the convergence of the network. For example, for use case 2 the number of iterations analysed were: 12, 40, 100, 1000, 5000 and 10000 iterations, and five tests were developed for each of this number of iterations. Figure Figure 243. K2 algorithm (published in Cooper and Herskovits, 1992) shows that the score of the network obtained for 5000 and 10000 iterations is very similar and then it has been reached the convergence of the network (pp. 330, 336 Cooper and Herskovits 1992).

Figure 244. Bayes or K2 scores of the networks obtained for each number of iterations and for 5 different tests for use case 2 data. Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

It is important to notice that these scripts will allow to automatically determine the weight of all the Fairness Characteristics Level 3 over the life of the project when more data are gathered in the future.

Since the weights of level 3 FCs are directly related to one or more variables considered in the Bayesian network, for those FCs with only one variable in the network, their weight is the one of this variable, but for those FCs with more than one variable the weight was calculated by using the arithmetic mean. After doing this transformation between variable or node of the Bayesian Network and the level 3 FC, the weights were normalised again so that the sum of all the weights is 1.

Finally, the global weights of level 3 fairness characteristics are obtained by multiplying the local weight obtained by Bayesian networks and their corresponding level 1 and level 2 weights obtained in the AHP analysis, and normalising the results.

ANOVA test to determine the sensitive characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual

In order to determine if some sociodemographic profile are relevant for a specific FC level 3, an ANOVA analysis was performed as a statistical way to compare different groups. The ranking of FCs level 3 was determined with the Bayesian Network analysis (for more details see the previous subsection above) and with the AHP analysis for FCs level 1 and 2 (for more details see Section 7), the top 10 FCs were analysed by this method. It is important to point that the ANOVA analysis includes all the characteristics of the PI for those FCs that were previously ranked as the topmost relevant after the Bayesian network analysis.

As it was explained in D2.2, in this analysis it is used the statistical “F” that follows a Fisher distribution (Eq. 4) with a number of degrees of freedom equal to ($df_{factor}, df_{residual}$), where:

$df_{residual}$ is the total number of data ($N = \sum N_j$) minus 1 minus df_{factor} :

$$df_{residual} = (N - 1) - df_{factor} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

df_{factor} is the total number of groups (j) minus 1:

$$df_{factor} = (j - 1) \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

“F” can be calculated as:

$$F = \frac{MS_{factor}}{MS_{residual}} = \frac{\sum_j N_j (\mu_j - \bar{\mu})^2 / df_{factor}}{\sum_{ij} (x_{ij} - \mu_j)^2 / df_{residual}} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The significance level α is the probability to reject the null hypothesis $H_0 (\mu_1 = \mu_2)$ when it is true: In this case, the F (Fisher)-distribution has got a number of degrees of freedom equal to ($df_{factor}, df_{residual}$): F(1, 38), and the value F_0 for which $\alpha = 0,05$, what means a confidence level of 95%, is 4.

If H_0 is true ($\mu_1 = \mu_2$), there is no statistical difference between samples, the probability that $F_0 > 4$ is 5% or less. Then if after the data collection, and after calculating F according to Eq. 4, the value of F is higher than 4, we can conclude that the means of these 2 groups of study are different with a 95% of significance level (with an error of 5%).

Figure 245. Screenshot of the F distribution calculator.

A VBA was developed to conduct an ANOVA test for all these top 10 Fairness Characteristics per each characteristic of the Polyhedral Individual (PI) in a systematic and automatized way. This VBA has the aim to calculate the value of “F” (statistical with the name F Fisher) per each characteristic of the PI and automatically compare this value with the critical value F_0 belonging to a p-value 0.05. If “F” is higher than F_0 this characteristic has significant differences between ranges, and if “F” is lower than F_0 we can conclude that it has not.

This analysis is complementary to the analysis detailed in section 5.3, here carried out in a systematic and automatized way for all the characteristics of the Polyhedral individual (instead of some of them), and focusing only on the Top 10 Fairness Characteristics level 3 after the AHP and Bayesian Network analysis.

The scripts were prepared to automatically perform the ANOVA for all the characteristics of the PI, using the top 10 FCs obtained in the BN analysis.

The automatization of this process will allow to calculate the significant characteristics of the PI for all the Top 10 FCs after the AHP and the Bayesian Network analysis.

Results

Use Case 1

Bayesian Network analysis

Bayesian network analysis within this use case was performed to data coming from users of different stations of FGC and ZTM network. For this analysis, and since this is a project focused on the preferences of women, we obtained the Bayesian network of women responses. The information that feeds the dataset used for Bayesian networks includes data coming from Proprietary Structured Data, Observations and UESI data collection tools.

With the dataset used as input data, the Bayesian network obtained, showing the relationships between all the variables/nodes included in the dataset, can be seen in Annex 10.1. Using the network obtained and following the methodology explained in section 7.2.1, a hierarchy of level 3 FCs can be obtained, which combines the results obtained from the Bayesian networks (based on quantitative data of current status) with the ones obtained from the AHP analysis (qualitative data focused on women priorities). The Top 10 FCs level 3 and their weights for Use Case 1 are shown in TableTable 56. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case 1 in the analysis performed in December 2020.

Table 56. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case 1 in the analysis performed in December 2020.

FC Level 3	FC Level 2	FC Level 1	Weight Level 3	Normalized Weight Level 3	Weight level 1 x Weight level 2 (AHP)	Global Weight FC Level 3	Normalized Global Weight
Offering adequate personal space	OVERCROWDING AND EMERGENCY SITUATIONS	SAFETY AND SECURITY	0.0096	0.0229	0.1858	0.0043	0.0361
Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating)	OVERCROWDING AND EMERGENCY SITUATIONS	SAFETY AND SECURITY	0.0079	0.0192	0.1858	0.0036	0.0302
Improved ventilation and air-conditioning	OVERCROWDING AND EMERGENCY SITUATIONS	SAFETY AND SECURITY	0.0075	0.0180	0.1858	0.0034	0.0284
Walking time from the points of interest to the	SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY	ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE	0.0089	0.0214	0.1541	0.0033	0.0280

public transport access points							
Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc	SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY	ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE	0.0083	0.0199	0.1541	0.0031	0.0261
Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety	HARASSMENT AND PICKPOCKETING	SAFETY AND SECURITY	0.0085	0.0203	0.1475	0.0029	0.0254
Visibility of the surrounding area of the station	HARASSMENT AND PICKPOCKETING	SAFETY AND SECURITY	0.0084	0.0203	0.1475	0.0029	0.0255
Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY	ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE	0.0079	0.0192	0.1541	0.0029	0.0251
Reliability of the service modes available	SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY	ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE	0.0077	0.0184	0.1542	0.0028	0.0241
Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY	ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE	0.0077	0.0184	0.1542	0.0028	0.0241

It could be seen that *having personal space* is the main factor considered followed by *improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating)* both regarding the overcrowding and emergency situations. Safety and security is the aspect in the AHP analysis with the highest importance from women's opinion when using the rail public service. Measures like having more space so that in the case of an emergency in the stations they can move easily and escape, or lower the interaction with other users through a different design of the seating layout, and then reduce the probability of some undesired or violent behaviours, are considered by women as important aspects to feel more comfortable when using railway stations. The third position is for *improved ventilation and air-conditioning* and *visibility of the surrounding area of the station*. All the 3 top criteria are linked with Safety and Security level I FC that indicates people are very aware of the problems there could happen for using railways. The concerns regarding safety and security also include harassment and pickpocketing issues when considering

necessary complaint and information points in case of violations to personal and point out the visibility of surrounding areas of the station.

In addition to Safety and Security, Accessibility has also been considered as an important aspect, with factors such as walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points, number of service available within the transport infrastructure, reliability of the service modes available and integration with other modes of public transport.

ANOVA analysis

The ANOVA analysis was performed with the data coming from the UESI questionnaires carried out by FGC and ZTM.

Table 57. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case I and their nature in the analysis performed in July 2020 shows the top 10 level 3 FCs for Use Case I, their weights, and the nature of the data. Some level 3 FCs were measured by only one datum coming from structured dataset, observations, or UESI questionnaires, while others can have data coming from different sources. For the ANOVA analysis, only the information coming from UESI was considered. The FCS analysed through ANOVA were:

- Offering adequate personal space
- Improved ventilation and air-conditioning
- Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points
- Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.
- Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety
- Visibility of the surrounding area of the station
- Number of service available within the transport infrastructure
- Reliability of the service modes available

Table 57. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case I and their nature in the analysis performed in July 2020

FC Level 3	Normalized weight	Data collection tool
Offering adequate personal space;	0.0255	UESI
Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	0.0251	Observations
Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;	0.0226	UESI + Observations

Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points	0.0251	UESI
Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.	0.0244	UESI
Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety;	0.0251	UESI + Observations
Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;	0.0209	UESI + Observations
Number of service available within the transport infrastructure	0.0237	UESI + Observations
Reliability of the service modes available	0.0066	UESI + Proprietary data
Integration with alternative shared mobility service for last mile connections, including bike, scooter and car sharing	0.0079	Observations

As an example, Table XX indicates the results of the ANOVA analysis for the age for the FC 'Offering adequate personal space' which is the most weighted Top 10 FC after the Bayesian Network analysis.

Table 58. Example of the ANOVA analysis per age regarding the question “I feel comfortable with the personal space available to me at stations and in carriages.”

Anova: Single factor

SUMMARY

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
18-24	118	545	4,618644	3,639649
25-34	164	735	4,481707	3,932179
35-44	129	616	4,775194	3,89438
45-54	64	340	5,3125	3,297619
55-64	36	204	5,666667	2,685714
65-74	9	53	5,888889	0,361111
>=75	2	11	5,5	4,5

ANOVA

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between groups	76,07148	6	12,67858	3,483491	0,002194	2,116172
Within the group	1874,404	515	3,639619			
Total	1950,475	521				

SIGNIFICANT

The analysis determined that the characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual for women that exhibit significant differences between ranges regarding the 10 topmost level 3 FCs coming from UESIs are:

- For the FC Offering adequate personal space:
 - Age (being people between 25 and 34 years old the most unsatisfied group)
 - Education (being people with *Doctorate* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Income (being people who earn between 31,000 and 40,999 € the most unsatisfied group)
 - Household type (being *Homosexual marriages or stable partner* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Living with a dependent (being those with *preschool age children* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnic group (being *white* people the most unsatisfied group)
 - Discriminated in transport (being those *discriminated* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Improved ventilation and air-conditioning:
 - Education (people with *Master* is the most unsatisfied group)
 - Household type (*Homosexual marriages or stable partner* is the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnic group (being *white* the most unsatisfied group)

- Religion (being those *Christian* the most unsatisfied group)
- Discriminated in transport (being those *discriminated* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Walking time from the points of interest to the public transport access points:
 - Age (being people between *25 and 34 years* old the most unsatisfied group)
 - Education (people with *Primary education* is the most unsatisfied group)
 - Household type (*Single parents* is the most unsatisfied group)
 - Living with a dependent (those with *preschool age children* are the most unsatisfied group)
 - Travelling with dependents (being those *travelling with dependents* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Disability (being those *with disability* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnic group (being *white* people the most unsatisfied group)
 - Religion (being *Christians* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Integration with other modes of public transport including bus, train, etc.:
 - Living environment (being those living in a *suburban area* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Education (being people with *Master* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Religion (being those *white* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Complaint information point in case of violations to personal safety:
 - Living environment (being those living in a *rural area* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Education (being people with *Master* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Income (people who earn between *51,000 and 70,999 €* is the most unsatisfied group)
 - Household type (being *single* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Living with a dependent (being those with *preschool age children* the most unsatisfied groups)
 - Travelling with dependent (being those *travelling with dependents* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnic group (being *white* people the most unsatisfied group)
 - Religion (being *Christians* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Sexual orientation (being *heterosexual* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Visibility of the surrounding area of the station:
 - Living environment (being those living in a *rural area* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Education (being *short-cycle tertiary* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Income (people who earn between *51,000 and 70,999 €* is the most unsatisfied group)
 - Travelling with dependent (being those *travelling with dependents* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnic group (being *white* people the most unsatisfied group)
 - Discriminated in transport (being those *discriminated* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Number of service available within the transport infrastructure:
 - Living environment (being those living in a *rural area* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Education (being people with *Master* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Household type (being *single* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Living with a dependent (*living with preschool age children* being the most unsatisfied group)
 - Travelling with dependent (being those *travelling with dependents* the most unsatisfied group)

- Ethnic group (being *white* people the most unsatisfied group)
- Religion (being *Christian* the most unsatisfied group)
- Sexual orientation (being *heterosexual* the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Reliability of the service modes available:
 - Education (being people with *Doctorate* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Household type (being *single* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Living with a dependent (being those with *preschool age children* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Travelling with dependent (being those *travelling without dependents* the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnic group (being *white* people the most unsatisfied group).

Use case II

Bayesian Network analysis

Bayesian network analysis within this use case is performed with data coming from participants recruited to participate in the simulator developed by IBV and their responses in the UESI questionnaire filled after experiencing the driverless scenarios and situations. So, the information that feeds the dataset used for Bayesian networks includes data coming from Observations and UESI data collection tools. Only data coming from women was considered in the analysis.

With women data used as input data, the graphical representation of the Bayesian network is obtained following the methodology explained in section 7.2.1 (the network can be seen in Annex 10.1). The obtained network shows the relations between the different variables or nodes, which gives an idea of how influential is a variable in the network. With this network, the number of arcs of each node to the roots or main parents of the network, their relation with the level 3 FCS identified and the corresponding level 1 and level 2 FCs weights (obtained through AHP analysis) we can obtain a hierarchy of level 3 FCs. The Top 10 FCs level 3 and their weights for Use Case II are shown in Table Table 59. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case II.

FC Level 3	FC Level 2	FC Level 1	Weight Level 3	Normalized Weight Level 3	Weight level 1 x Weight level 2 (AHP)	Global Weight FC Level 3	Normalised Global Weight
Perception of boredom	SIMULTANEITY	COMFORT	0.0111	0.0146	0.0913	0.0013	0.0260
Perception of joy	SIMULTANEITY	COMFORT	0.0111	0.0146	0.0913	0.0013	0.0260
Perception of the degreee of interaction between passengers	SIMULTANEITY	COMFORT	0.0090	0.0118	0.0913	0.0011	0.0210

Perception of reduction of ecological impact	EMISIONS	ENVIRON MENT	0.0132	0.0174	0.0582	0.0010	0.0197
Importance on controlling speed	VEHICLE BEHAVIOUR	DESIGN OPTION	0.0132	0.0174	0.0569	0.0010	0.0193
Driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment	SIMULTANEITY	COMFORT	0.0079	0.0104	0.0913	0.0009	0.0185
Bad weather	TRUST IN TECHNOLOGY	COMFORT	0.0060	0.0079	0.0753	0.0006	0.0183
Overall preference of sportive driving	VEHICLE BEHAVIOUR	DESIGN OPTION	0.0121	0.0160	0.0569	0.0009	0.0177
Importance of optimising well-being of other road users to determine vehicle behaviour	VEHICLE BEHAVIOUR	DESIGN OPTION	0.0121	0.0160	0.0569	0.0009	0.0177
Perception of driving without steering wheel	PUBLIC HEALTH	ENVIRON MENT	0.0090	0.0118	0.0758	0.0009	0.0174

Table 59. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case II

It could be seen that the feeling of *boredom* and *joy* are the main factors considered for women to accept or not the autonomous vehicles followed by the perception regarding the *interaction with other passengers*, all of them factors linked with the comfort felt by the users and the possibility of simultaneity due to driverless vehicles.

Another group of aspects also considered very important is the one linked with design options such the importance of *controlling the speed*, the *preferences of sportive driving scenarios* and the possibility AVs offers of *optimizing the vehicle behaviour*.

ANOVA analysis

The ANOVA analysis was performed with women data coming from the UESI questionnaires and the simulator carried out by IBV because all the data collected is quantitative.

Analysing the characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual that have got significant differences for the top 10 level 3 FCs, it can be pointed out that no characteristic of the Polyhedral Individual has significant differences. The reason for this result is that the sample considered in this Use Case is not sufficient enough to find differences among groups and for this reason IBV performed a descriptive analysis explored by non-parametric significance tests: Kruskal-Wallis and χ^2 test depending on whether the answer is an ordinal or nominal variable (See Section 4).

Use case III

Bayesian network analysis within this use case is performed to data coming from VELIB and the information that feeds the dataset used for Bayesian networks includes data coming from Proprietary Structured data, UESI and Observations data collection tools. This analysis was developed only using data of women.

With women data used as input data, the graphical representation of the Bayesian network is obtained following the methodology explained in section 7.2.1. (the network can be seen in Annex 10.1.). The obtained network shows the relations between the different variables or nodes, which gives an idea of how influent is a variable in the network. With this network, the number of arcs of each node to the roots or main parents of the network, their relationship with the level 3 FCS identified and the corresponding level 1 and level 2 FCs weights (obtained through AHP analysis) we can obtain a hierarchy of level 3 FCs. The Top 10 level 3 FCs and their weights for Use Case III are shown in Table Table 60. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case III.

FC Level 3	FC Level 2	FC Level 1	Weight Level 3	Normalized Weight Level 3	Weight level 1 x Weight level 2 (AHP)	Global Weight FC Level 3	Normalised Global Weight
Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling	PEER INFLUENCE (SUBJECTIVE NORM)	SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS	0.0316	0.0511	0.0748	0.0038	0.0669
Cycling rain Poncho	WEATHER	WEATHER AND TOPOLOGY	0.0182	0.0294	0.1098	0.0032	0.0566
Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.	TOPOGRAPHY	WEATHER AND TOPOLOGY	0.0132	0.0213	0.1402	0.0029	0.0524
All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure	WEATHER	WEATHER AND TOPOLOGY	0.0149	0.0242	0.1098	0.0027	0.0465

Attractive changing facilities	INSUFFICIENT INFRASTRUCTURE	ACCESSIBILITY AND SPONTANEITY	0.0232	0.0376	0.0676	0.0025	0.0445
Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.	FAMILY RESPONSIBILITIES	SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS	0.0141	0.0228	0.1086	0.0025	0.0434
Safe cycle routes for cycling with children	FAMILY RESPONSIBILITIES	SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS	0.0115	0.0186	0.1086	0.0020	0.0354
Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities	PEER INFLUENCE (SUBJECTIVE NORM)	SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS	0.0165	0.0267	0.0746	0.0020	0.0350
Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling	NEGATIVE PERCEPTIONS (SOCIO-CULTURAL CONSTRAINS)	SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS	0.0165	0.0267	0.0666	0.0018	0.0312
Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes	SAFE ENVIRONMENT AND PERSONAL SAFETY	SAFETY AND SECURITY	0.0199	0.0322	0.0542	0.0017	0.0305

Table 60. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case III

Although bicycles have not always been well considered, nowadays it is considered a healthy and eco-friendly mean of transport and this is, probably, one of the reasons why women point out the increase the *public awareness campaigns on the benefits of cycling*. If people understand the several benefits cycling have, people will increase their use.

Following it, *weather* and *topography* conditions are very relevant factors due to bicycles do not have specific facilities to prevent from those inclement weather and terrain conditions.

Other Top 10 main factors are linked to the importance of having the proper *infrastructure* with specific and *safe lines for cycling with children* and *with lower traffic speeds* that make their use more difficult.

ANOVA analysis

The ANOVA analysis was performed with the data coming from the UESI questionnaires carried out by VELIB. Table 60. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case III shows the top 10 level 3 FCs for Use Case III, their weights, and the nature of the data. Some level 3 FCs were measured by only one datum coming from structured dataset, observations, or UESI questionnaires, while others can have data coming from different sources. For the ANOVA analysis, only the information coming from UESI was considered. The FCs analysed through ANOVA were:

- Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
- Cycling rain Poncho

- Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible
- Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo
- Safe cycle routes for cycling with children
- Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities
- Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
- Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes

The analysis determined that the characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual that have got significant differences between ranges for women regarding the 10 top level 3 FCs coming from UESIs are:

- For the FC Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo:
 - Living environment (being those living in suburban areas those most unsatisfied)
 - Education (being those with master the group most unsatisfied)
 - Travel with dependents (being those who travel with dependents the group most unsatisfied)
 - Disability (being those disabled the group most unsatisfied)
- For the FC Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling:
 - Living environment (being those living in urban areas those most unsatisfied)
- For the FC Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes:
 - Income (being those who earn 51,000-70,999 € the groups most unsatisfied)

Use case 4

Bayesian Network analysis

Bayesian network analysis within this use case is performed with data coming from employees from FGC and ZTM and the information that feeds the dataset used for Bayesian networks includes data coming from Proprietary Structured data and UESI data collection tools. This analysis was performed considering only data from women.

With women data used as input data, the graphical representation of the Bayesian network, is obtained following the methodology explained in section 7.2.1 (the network can be seen in Annex 10.1). The obtained network shows the relations between the different variables or nodes, which gives an idea of how influent is a variable in the network. With this network, the number of arcs of each node to the roots or main parents of the network, their relation with the level 3 FCS identified and the corresponding level 1 and level 2 FCs weights (obtained through AHP analysis) we can obtain a hierarchy of level 3 FCs. The Top 10 level 3 FCs and their weights for Use Case IV are shown in Table 61. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case IV.

Table 61. Weights for the top 10 FCs level 3 for Use Case IV

FC Level 3	FC Level 2	FC Level 1	Weight Level 3	Normalized Weight Level 3	Weight level 1 x Weight level 2 (AHP)	Global Weight FC Level 3	Normalised Global Weight
Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	CARING AND PARENTING RESPONSIBILITIES	PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES	0.0244	0.0564	0.0951	0.0054	0.0821
Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	DEMAND FACTORS (JOB RECRUITMENT)	SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS	0.0249	0.0575	0.0917	0.0053	0.0808
Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	SAFETY AND SECURITY	JOB CHARACTERISTICS	0.0239	0.0553	0.0557	0.0031	0.0472
Diversity training (re ethnicity);	DEMOGRAPHIC	INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS	0.0254	0.0586	0.0515	0.0030	0.0463
Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	SAFETY AND SECURITY	JOB CHARACTERISTICS	0.0234	0.0541	0.0557	0.0030	0.0462
Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities and HR policies;	HR POLICIES	JOB CHARACTERISTICS	0.0249	0.0575	0.0522	0.0030	0.0460

Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	JOB SEGREGATION	SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS	0.0045	0.0103	0.0917	0.0009	0.0423
Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff;	HR POLICIES	JOB CHARACTERISTICS	0.0222	0.0513	0.0522	0.0027	0.0411
Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave;	POLICY/LEGAL	SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS	0.0130	0.0300	0.0885	0.0026	0.0407
Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	POLICY/LEGAL	SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS	0.0123	0.0283	0.0885	0.00251	0.0384

Having the opportunity to change shifts and to reducing the working time to those with small children is the most relevant factor obtained after analysing the employee's perception data; the flexibility of the work is important for them because it allows them to better organize their daily life to carry their kids to school, to go to the doctor or to take care of themselves in case they were ill, etc.

The second factor emerging from the analysis is that *all jobs were widely advertised and all applications were welcomed* which means that no one was excluded by their conditions or personal circumstances

Safety and security are important factors that appear among the Top 10 Fcs level 3: being *security staff available to intervene in case of need* and *applying a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment*. Both issues refer to feeling safe and comfortable in the job position and having the certainty that in case of any disturb, it will be solved immediately.

In general, aspects such as *caring and parenting responsibilities, safety and security and equality among men and women and also among different cultures* emerged as relevant concerns for women.

ANOVA analysis

The analysis determined that the characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual that exhibit significant differences between ranges for women regarding the 10 topmost level 3 FCs coming from UESIs are:

- For the FC Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time:
 - Age (being those between 45 and 54 years the most unsatisfied)
 - Education (being those with degree the most unsatisfied group)
 - Ethnicity (being those mixed the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed:
 - Education (being those with Short-cycle tertiary education the most unsatisfied group)
 - Income (being those earning more than 31,000 € the most unsatisfied)
 - Dependent in the family (being those with dependents the most unsatisfied)
 - Travel with dependents (being those that do not travel with dependents the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Security staff available to intervene in case of need:
 - Education (being those with Short-cycle tertiary education the most unsatisfied group)
 - Dependent in the family (being those with dependents the most unsatisfied)
 - Travel with dependents (being those that do not travel with dependents the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Diversity training (re ethnicity):
 - Education (being those with Short-cycle tertiary education the most unsatisfied group)
 - Income (being those earning more than 51,000 € the most unsatisfied)
 - Dependent in the family (being those with dependents the most unsatisfied)
- For the FC Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment:
 - Education (being those with degree the group most unsatisfied)
 - Income (being those earning between 11,000 and 20,999 € the most unsatisfied group)
 - Dependent in the family (being those without dependents the most unsatisfied)

- Travel with dependents (being those that travel with dependents the most unsatisfied group)
- For the FC Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies):
 - Income (being those earning between 41,000 and 50,999 € the most unsatisfied group)

9. Discussion and general results.

This report (D4.3) presents the findings of our results by methodology across the Use Case (I-IV). In this section, we summarise the key findings for each Use Case to provide an overview for discussion and to better inform the development of the integrated interdisciplinary analysis (D4.4). All the results will feed the interdisciplinary panel and D4.4 analysis report to further propose Fairness measures to achieve a more inclusive transport system for women users and employees. Thus, the conclusions can be summarized as follows:

Use case I – Urban railways

The main aim of Use Case I was to conduct research on stations safety, accessibility and capacity to address basic mobility needs primarily from a gender perspective, but also regarding other demographics (e.g., age, illness) and to examine the findings from intersectional perspective. By collecting data using a variety of methodologies, DIAMOND ensures a comprehensive perspective of issues arising for women, minorities and other vulnerable groups.

Structured Open Data and Observational Data findings

In order to examine the level of accessibility of urban railway infrastructures by women users, a data-driven approach was used. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) were used for the analysis of several geolocated open datasets related to the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland). The analysis focused on assessing the level of accessibility for women commuting by the urban railway infrastructures managed by a Southern European railway provider FGC (82 stations in total) and by an Eastern European railway provider ZTM (96 stations in total), in order to identify and characterize a short list of suitable stations (ten stations characterized by high levels of accessibility and ten stations characterized by low levels of accessibility).

Different composite indicators were defined in order to identify a group of suitable urban railway stations belonging at least two highest or lowest quintiles among the Territorial Data Index, Sociodemographic Data Index and Mobility Data Index. The list was further shortened through the analysis of several open data related to each railway infrastructure: (i) metro and urban railway lines; (ii) transport service tariff zone; (iii) underground or above-ground infrastructure.

Onsite observations were aimed at further characterizing the urban railway infrastructures previously selected through the analysis of structured open data. Observations were based on *ad hoc* developed checklists for the evaluation of infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics related to women's needs as users of public transport infrastructure. The checklist was composed of four main parts: (i) area surrounding the station; (ii) concourse level of the station; (iii) platform level of the station; (iv) carriage.

Social Media findings

With social media data analysis, the aim was to complement the analysis of survey data with larger samples of users, to provide a broader perspective of issues for transport users. Data was retrieved from Twitter API related to relevant topics. Demographic characteristics of Twitter users are not available; however, inference was made about gender using m3Inference tool.

- For the Southern European rail provider (FGC) women were more concerned about the environment and fares. Women also mentioned going to work more often and the issues that arose from this including references to schedule, lines, and journeys. Men were more likely to mention physical factors such as platforms. Both men and women showed concern regarding delays and changes to schedules. During COVID-19 in the transport area, men demonstrated more anger and suspicion while women were more thankful but also concerned by practical issues such as disinfection use.
- For the Eastern European rail provider (ZTM), men were more concerned about other means of transport, like bikes, subway, car, or car as an alternative to the ‘autobus’. Women were more likely to mention their work, and also make references to schedule issues. In both cases (autobus and tramway), women speak more about people, express more frustration and use more swear words.

User satisfaction questionnaire findings

The user satisfaction questionnaire responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs and perception by transport users for fairness characteristics of the service in each case study when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features. Four main groups or factors of the fairness characteristics emerged and was used in the interpretation of the data: Accessibility & Comfort; Safety and Security; Service organisation; and Capability to address service needs. In general, across all use cases from the Northern European case study (Irish Rail), the Southern European case study (FGC) and the Eastern European case study (ZTM) highlighted the following key findings (for more detailed findings on each organisation, please refer to Chapter 6):

- There were some significant gender differences across the questionnaire, with gender showing relevance across many items. In particular across all data sets, women felt less satisfied around safety and security issues than men, and non-binary users even less so.
- Across all data sets, there is one statement that has consistently rated lower than others: “There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them”, showing a lack of specific facilities for parents.
- From the correlation index most questions were not strongly correlated across the 3 data sets, however there were higher correlations (>0.45) around the factors of safety and security, accessibility and comfort and general service satisfaction.
- Results of the stepwise analysis on linear regression show that general satisfaction may be determined by different characteristics in between Northern European Service and Southern and Eastern European samples. However overall, all 3 data sets highlighted operational hours and frequency of service, pricing, information provided, facilities and comfort, as well as safety.
- In all cases there is a high variability in perceived safety across stations; however, while in the FGC data users from urban areas are more satisfied with safety and users from rural areas less satisfied, in Irish Rail we observe the opposite.
- For the Northern and Eastern European data set “travelling with dependents” and “having a chronic illness/disability” were factors that impacted accessibility and comfort. For Eastern European sample, caring responsibility was important for accessibility and comfort and ethnicity was a factor for safety and security, whilst income and travel line were very relevant for Southern European dataset.
- The age group of 35-44 years was most critical of the service provided in Northern European sample than other age groups, while in Southern Europe, depending on the line travelling, older people were more critical. This discrepancy of results may be due to unique services provided

to older citizens in Northern European sample, “free travel scheme”, and accessibility and services provided by certain lines in Southern Europe.

DAD, Bayesian networks and ANOVA analysis findings

The Dynamic Augmented Delphi (DAD) survey was conducted to gather data on transport users to provide a final weighted hierarchy of Fairness Characteristics (FC) using an Analytic Hierarchic Process (AHP) analysis.

- According to DAD surveys, safety and security emerged as the FC of level I considered as the most relevant both for the aggregated analysis and for all groups analysed in the intersectional analysis. In particular, overcrowding and emergency situations emerged as the main FCs of level 2.
- For level 3 FCs, having personal space emerged as the main factor considered, followed by improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating) both regarding the overcrowding and emergency situations. The third position is for improved ventilation and air-conditioning and visibility of the surrounding area of the station.
- All the 3 top criteria are linked with Safety and Security level I FC indicating people are very aware of the problems that could happen for using railways.

The ANOVA analysis carried out after the AHP and the BN analysis conclude that the profiles that have significant differences are mainly education and household type. High level education and singles are the groups that give lower scores and so they are the most unsatisfied groups of people.

Interim summary of findings of Use Case I

Taken together, we can clearly see significant gender differences with women having less access to, lower perception of and lower satisfaction with rail providers. In particular women seem to have greater concern and less satisfaction with safety and security issues. However, it is too simple to generalise for all women across contexts. Results do indicate that issues around mobility, such as disability/chronic illness and caring responsibilities can have a large impact on users’ satisfaction with services. Similarly, we must note that different demographics and fairness characteristics were more meaningful in different countries, showing that consideration of contextual factors are essential.

Use Case II – Autonomous vehicles

The main aim of Use Case II was an experimental analysis with a simulator to assess the emotional reaction of different demographic groups of people to autonomous vehicles’ driving experience followed up by a survey on user’s preferences and characteristics related to their expectations regarding the usage of AV, and how they may influence their likelihood of acceptance.

Observational Data findings related to the experimental assessment:

The sample was reduced due to the restrictions during the pandemic and we were able to have only 40 participants in the actual simulator, drivers between 25-55 years old, divided in two experimental factors. For the sample size to be statistically representative we addressed mainly just two characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual: gender, and travelling with or without

dependent people (mainly in the observed sample they were children under 12 years of age). Two more relevant aspects were considered in the selection of the participants for the experimental design: whether participants enjoy driving, and whether they have affinity with technology. In the selected sample, for the questions related to “driving enjoyment” and “interest in technology” there are not significant differences among genders or groups.

The emotional indicators collected to observe gender-driven stressors related to autonomous driving were based on arousal (the level of intensity) and valence (negativity, neutrality or positivity) obtained from the physiological signals of the passenger measured on board while travelling in a dynamic simulator of an L4 autonomous car.

The higher values of arousal measured are associated with situations of driving faster while slow driving is associated with lower levels of arousal, as can be expected. Regarding gender, there are differences between genders in two scenarios. In the case of the Comfort scenario, men elicited less arousal than women, being for men the scenario with lowest arousal. In the case of Simultaneous task scenario women elicited less arousal than men, being for men the scenario with highest arousal.

For arousal, the values measured and self-assessed by the participants are related to each other, while this did not happen with valence.

The most negative values of valence elicited to the participants occurred during overtaking and the sportive driving, while the more positive corresponds to slow events.

Scenarios with higher impact in emotional state measured with physiological variables are, on one hand, the scenarios related with a smooth and aggressive driving mode (sport and comfort scenario) and, on the other hand, related to performing a simultaneous task (simultaneity scenario). These scenarios are, additionally, the scenarios where gender differences have a higher impact.

Due to driving mode, there are differences in physiological and self-assessed arousal level, being the smooth driving mode more relaxed than the aggressive driving mode. However, in the physiological arousal this difference is higher for men than for women and the subjective assessment also differs.

Men, in the comfort scenario with a smoother driving mode, are significantly less activated (lower arousal) than in the rest of the scenarios, and also compared with women. Thus, we find a clear “relaxing” effect of this scenario for men, while we do not find it for women, for whom the comfort scenario has the same arousal level as the other scenarios.

The sport scenario for men is the most negative (lowest self-declared valence), significantly compared with the rest of scenarios. For men, sport is the second scenario with highest arousal level. For women, the arousal level in the sport scenario is similar to men’s level, and significantly higher than in the comfort scenario, however women do not consider this scenario as negative as men do. For women, comfort and sport scenarios have the same level of self-declared valence.

Therefore, the driving mode impacts the physiological emotional state of both genders in an expected way, however, in men this impact is higher, notably the smooth driving mode has a relaxing effect, and they assess negatively the sport driving mode.

In the simultaneity scenario, where the participant has to perform a simultaneous task, men present the highest activation level compared to the other scenarios and higher than women. This fact could be attributed to a higher cognitive effort of men while performing a simultaneous task.

Additionally, women assess more positively this scenario than men do and exhibit a lower activation level.

User satisfaction questionnaire findings

In UC II UESI questionnaires were collected by two different sources. In the experimental sessions in IBV, participant answered the UESI questionnaires after the experiments in the autonomous driving simulator to gather their opinion. The other source was through an online survey with a Spanish and English version. A total of 96 questionnaires were collected (40 in the experimental session, 47 in the Spanish version of the online survey and 9 in the English version). The user satisfaction questionnaire responses were analysed to identify satisfaction of the end-users related to autonomous vehicles. In the case of UESI questionnaires associated with UC II experiments, the outline was composed by two main parts. The first part is focused on profiling the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users, and was administrated before the execution of the experiments. The second part was focused on evaluating users' satisfaction regarding the autonomous driving performance experienced through the simulation.

The following is a summation of the key findings (for more detailed results, please see Chapter 4):

- The overall perception of autonomous vehicles of the sample is positive. Most of the results were consistent about the assessment of AV's benefits with no differences by gender or by the presence of children in the family composition.
- Some gender differences did emerge, with women indicating less satisfaction with safety, greater need to accessibility and mobility with children in mind, and placing greater importance of energy efficiency.
- Beyond gender, one of the main determinants in this sample results regarding women with/without children. For example, women show greater interest in performing simultaneous activities than men, especially women with children under 12. For men and women with children interest in caring for other passengers in higher and for women, but especially without children, keeping control of driving features is more important.
- Finally, willingness to purchase an AV differed pre-post experiment, with a shift from gender predicting willingness to buy (women less so than men) to with/without children. Women with children, before experiment were less willing to purchase an IV, however after the experiment were the group with highest level of agreement with the statement (excluding cost).

Social Media findings

From the social media analysis and the content base data collected and the estimation of gender based on the user's name, short bio and picture, the tool returns the estimated probability of a user to be man or woman (assigned only when probability above a threshold of 0.9 for one of the two genders).

In this context, for the case study about the use of AV we found that while men tend to focus more on aspects related to technology and business, women are more concerned with social impact, social context and feelings. Looking at words co-occurring with "feel", for men word "confident" has the highest cosine similarity, and then we find other positive words such as "peaceful".

Sentiment in women's language differs from men's language. The analysis was able to distinguish between words that make women have a lower valence than men, and words that give an opposite

contribution. Women tend to have overall a more negative language when speaking about AVs. This is mostly due to a lower use of positive words related to business, such as “money” or “cash”, and of positive words that can be associated with innovation, such as “amazing”, “breakthrough” or “success”; women’s more negative tone also depends on a higher use of negative words like “protest”, “wrong” or “ill”. On the other hand, positive words used more frequently by women include general positive words, and words related to social and daily life, such as “life”, “feel”, “today”, “health”, “family”, “school”. So, both for positive and negative words, women seem less interested than men in business and technological aspects, and more interested in the impact of AVs on the social context and on daily life.

DAD, Bayesian networks and ANOVA analysis findings

The Use case 2 analysis regarding the Autonomous vehicles was carried out with the 116 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020. The gender distribution was formed by 50 women, 44 men, 1 transsexual women, 1 transsexual men, 3 non-binary people and 17 people who prefer not answer. The 5 most important Fairness characteristics identified by the responders were, in order: *trust in technology*, *public health*, *non-monetary costs*, *emissions* and *vehicle behaviour*.

The results indicate that:

Analysing the ranking of high-level fairness characteristics, it can be said that:

- In general, safety and security results to be the most relevant factor (except for women experiencing discrimination, that selected the environment) and the last factor in the top 5 is the design options.
- For women travelling with dependents, mobility is more relevant than environment.
- For women experiencing discrimination, the binomial environment and economy are more relevant than safety & security.
- For non-urban women the economy is more relevant than the environment. Whereas for women with annual incomes lower than 21K€ the environment is more relevant than economy.

When looking at a further level of detail within each of the above categories, the following findings are to be reported:

- Trust in technology results to be the most important factor for women in general, which also occurs for the aggregated analysis.
- Human error, which usually turns into an accident, is not one of the most weighted factors, it is only relevant for women who have felt discriminated on public transport. It could be associated with the driverless nature of autonomous vehicles.
- Public health emerged as the most relevant factor, being, for all the profiles analysed, in the Top 5 criteria. In fact, women travelling with dependents, low wage women earners and those who have felt discriminated for their appearance on public transport rated it as the most important one.
- Non-monetary cost is considered the top criteria for those women that earn less than 21K€ /year, following Public health, which could be explained due to the connections between the

lack of income and the difficulties they may have in acquiring an autonomous vehicle, which today are high-class cars.

- Although Monetary cost might be thought to be one of the most relevant factors, it is only in the top 5 for women living in rural areas and for low wage earners.
- Emissions is relevant for all the women profiles analysed except for women living with dependents
- Surprisingly, no particular profile considers the Accident rate among the Top 5 criteria.
- Vehicle behaviour appears to be relevant for women, especially the ones travelling with dependents.

Congestion is only included among the top 5 criteria for women who experienced discrimination.

When considering key characteristics having an influence on their acceptance of AV for future scenarios, the main characteristics were:

- Simultaneity, which is the option that driverless vehicles offer to perform more than one task at the same time because the car drives by itself, is the most important factor for women living in rural areas; this could be associated with the fact that they have to travel long distances to perform their daily tasks such as going to work, shopping or going with their children to school.
- Non-monetary cost is the main factor considered important by women with low incomes.
- Public health, factor linked with driving without stress and being relaxed during the trips, is the main factor for the global population, for women travelling with dependents and for women who experienced discrimination on public transport.
- The ranking of factors differs by the characteristics of the profiles analysed, but non-monetary cost is repeated for all except for women travelling with dependents, and Public Health for all except women living in rural areas.

Interim summary of findings of Use Case II

Taken together, we can clearly see that the overall perception of autonomous vehicles of the sample is positive. Most of the results were consistent about the assessment of AV's benefits with no differences by gender or by the presence of children in the family composition. In this context women indicated a higher sensitivity towards safety, greater need to accessibility and mobility with children in mind and placing greater importance of energy efficiency.

Furthermore, women show greater interest in performing simultaneous activities than men, especially women with children under 12. For men and women with children interest in caring for other passengers is higher and for women, but especially without children, keeping control of driving features is more important. Finally, the willingness to purchase an AV differed pre-post experiment, women with children, before experiment were less willing to purchase an IV, however after the experiment they were much more including (when costs considerations were not taken into account).

Use Case III - Bikes sharing

Observational Data findings:

Within the objectives of DIAMOND, the results of the proposed analysis allowed to characterize the sample of suitable bike-sharing docking stations for this use case managed by VELIB (Paris Region Petite Couronne), as characterized by high and low levels of accessibility for women; 1297 docking stations in total, in order to identify and characterize a short list of suitable bike-sharing docking stations. Ten stations characterized by high levels of accessibility and ten stations characterized by low levels of accessibility. The index used were: (i) density-based calculation on catchment areas/census section; (ii) normalization of values (z values in a range between 0 and 1); and (iii) weighted formulas of normalized values to calculate the Territorial Data Index (TDI), Socio-demographic Data Index (SDDI) and Mobility Data Index (MDI). Quintile frequency distribution of results made possible the identification of docking stations characterized by high levels of accessibility for the women (belonging to the highest quintile, $\geq 80^{\text{th}}$ percentile) and the stations characterized by low levels of accessibility for women (belonging to the lowest quintile, $\leq 20^{\text{th}}$ percentile).

Furthermore, observations based on *ad hoc* developed checklists were used for the evaluation of infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics related to women's needs as users of bike-sharing services around the following areas: (i) accessibility and spontaneity; (ii) safety and security; (iii) social constraints; (iv) weather and topography; (v) other.

The results highlighted that:

- 60% of the docking stations displayed some negative connotations in relation to spontaneity of accessing the bike service (the index is for reasons related to the maximum number of bikes observed at the docking station/ or the minimum number of bikes recorded during the observation, the percentage of bikes recorded during the observation (considering the capacity of the docking station) and the Number of other public modes of transport near the docking station. Also, no bikes were reported having a child seat for children).
- The characteristics related to public awareness were equally distributed between positive and negative and it was simply measured as an assessment of the observed percentage of female users.
- About 90% of observed docking station displayed some negative features related to separate infrastructure like the Presence of a cycle lane nearby the docking station (approx 200m around), and or the lack of a separate cycle infrastructure.
- And above 40% of docking station had negative features related to safe environment and perceived personal safety related to features such as observation of Safety of the cycle paths and lanes for cycling at night, and or Percentage of users wearing hi-vis cycling gear, and or percentage of worthy bikes among the fleet (e.g., well-functioning brakes, lights, etc.).

Social Media findings

The Social media analysis on users of the Bike sharing service offered by Velib show that the debate on Twitter is quite politicized, both among men and women; however, while men's

conversations related mostly to the electoral campaign, where bike-sharing was a divisive topic, the latter exhibited more interest in strikes and feminism. In terms of gender difference it is worth noting that in tweets involving the major's name, men speak of "fiasco", displaying a more aggressive tone, while women's top co-occurring word is merci ("thanks"), displaying a kinder and more positive type of attitude.

User satisfaction questionnaire findings

The user satisfaction questionnaire responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs and perception by transport users for fairness characteristics of bicycle sharing services and possible challenges when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features. Four main fairness characteristics were assessed: Accessibility and Spontaneity; Safety and Security; Social constraints; and Weather and Topography. The following are the key findings (for more detailed results, please refer to Chapter 6):

- There were some significant gender differences across the questionnaire, with gender showing relevance across many items. In particular women felt less satisfied with accessibility and safety and security issues than men, for example women were more concerned about the availability of safety equipment, transportation with children and safety at docking stations.
- On general issues related to cycling, significant differences emerged only according to gender, with women reporting higher concern.
- From the correlation index most questions were not strongly correlated, however there were higher correlations (>0.45) around the factors of accessibility and spontaneity, and safety and security.
- The user's level of satisfaction was found to be positively related to age, with younger respondents (18-44 years) being less critical of bike-sharing systems than older respondents (45-74 years).
- Perception of safety was linked to traffic speed: lower traffic predicted increased perception of safety and consequently user satisfaction. Similarly, visibility and adequate lighting at docking stations predicted an increased sense of security and user satisfaction.
- The absence of accessories for transporting children and carting goods negatively impacted user satisfaction, with respondents indicating that provision would increase their level of satisfaction.
- Unsurprisingly, weather conditions had a significant impact on cycling and bikes-haring, however the supply of cycling raincoats could help mitigate this and increase user satisfaction.

DAD, Bayesian networks and ANOVA analysis findings

Use case 3 analysis regarding the bicycle sharing services was carried out with the 97 DAD surveys filled up to November 2020. The gender distribution was formed by 46 women, 33 men, 1 transsexual woman, 3 non-binary people and 14 who prefer not answer.

DAD surveys highlighted that, when travelling by bicycle, weather and topography are among the factors that participants were more concerned about. When riding a bicycle, people do not have

any protection to avoid inclement weather, so it is not very comfortable riding in rainy, windy or snowing conditions. Moreover, it is more difficult to use the bicycle in hilly terrains. *Family responsibilities* are also a factor. Caring of children and elderly are a handicap for cycling because it is not very common that these sharing services provide bicycles adapted for the companions and therefore there is no option to use them for people travelling with dependents.

Bike sharing is considered a healthy and eco-friendly means of transport and this is, probably, one of the reasons why women point out the increase the *public awareness campaigns on the benefits of cycling*. Social media also highlighted a strong relation between bike-sharing and social and political issues, in particular for women. If people understand the several benefits cycling have, people will increase their use.

Concerning the bike sharing services, the living environment is the characteristic of the Polyhedral Individual with most significant differences for the top 10 Fairness Characteristics presented in the most granular level (level 3)

The ANOVA analysis was performed with the data coming from the UESI questionnaires carried out by VELIB. The top 10 level 3 Fairness Characteristics (FC) for Use Case III reported the following preferences:

- Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling
- Cycling rain Poncho
- Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible
- Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo
- Safe cycle routes for cycling with children
- Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities
- Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling
- Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes

The analysis determined that the characteristics of the Polyhedral Individual that show significant differences between the preferences expressed in the User satisfaction questionnaire are:

- For the FC regarding the possibility to have Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo:
 - Living environment (those living in suburban areas those most unsatisfied)
 - Education (those with a master's degree or above are the group most unsatisfied)
 - Travel with dependents (those who travel with dependents are the group most unsatisfied)
 - Disability (people with an illness or disability are the group most unsatisfied)
- For the FC related to Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling:
 - Living environment (those living in urban areas those most unsatisfied)
- For the FC regarding Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes:
 - Income (those who earn 51,000-70,999 € the groups most unsatisfied)

Interim summary of findings of Use Case III

Taken together, the overall user's level of satisfaction was found to be positively related to age, with younger respondents (18-44 years) being less critical of bike-sharing systems than older respondents (45-74 years). Perception of safety was also a very relevant factor in bike sharing, and it was linked to traffic speed, and some infrastructural aspects such as the lack of ad hoc cycling lanes. Similarly, visibility and adequate lighting at docking stations predicted increased sense of security and user satisfaction. Absence of accessories for transporting children and carting good negatively impacted user satisfaction, with respondents indicating that provision would increase their level of satisfaction. Last but not least weather conditions had a significant impact on cycling and bike sharing; however, supply of cycling raincoats could help mitigate this and increase user satisfaction.

Use case IV – Employment conditions

The main aim of Use Case IV was to examine gender and employment in the transport sector by examining women's needs in terms of recruitment, retention, and promotion in railways. The primary source of data for Use Case IV was through employee surveys and focus groups and interviews (see D4.2). Analyses that is available for the other Use Cases such as Observational data and social media analysis were not possible with this data set. However, meaningful results have emerged from both the user satisfaction questionnaires and the DAD surveys.

User satisfaction questionnaire findings

The survey results were obtained from employees across 3 data sets of Northern European, Southern European and Eastern European rail providers. The user satisfaction questionnaire responses were analysed to identify possible differences in needs and perception by transport employees for fairness characteristics of the service in each case study when disaggregated in respect to individual and demographic features. The questionnaires tried to cover a number of areas including job segregation/gender balance in their country/community and recruitment and promotion that promotes equality and fairness for women in transport as well as rating overall satisfaction. The following is a summation of the main key findings (for more detailed findings, please refer to Chapter 6):

- In general, gender was found as a relevant predictor of employees' perception related to organization inclusiveness, with women often having a lower level of satisfaction with some of the statements such as balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport related to the context, and satisfaction with how the context employees living in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport.
- In Eastern European data set, the majority of the sample was female limiting examination of gender differences, however income and environment were strongly correlated with organisational inclusive satisfaction. Other issues such as affordable childcare services etc. did not emerge as concerns due to state funded provision of childcare.
- In Northern European data set, women indicated less agreement with statements related to fairness and gender balance in the transport sector of their country and acceptance of women in their organisation. Overall women expressed greater need for affordable childcare services and expenses/support for traveling to work. Women rated less satisfaction with fairness and

inclusivity of women in transport in their country and of women employees in their organisation.

- In Southern European Data set, overall, there were only a few gender differences with women indicating less agreement with women's acceptance by male colleagues in the workplace, however there was significant differences by job level/type and by whether you had children or not in regard to satisfaction with organisational inclusiveness.

DAD, Bayesian networks and ANOVA analysis findings

The DAD surveys provide a complementary view on women's priorities and show that caring and parenting responsibilities are the most highlighted factor even for those profiles that do not necessarily have children or elderly relatives in the household type. People are very aware of the difficulty of accessing a job due to the limitation of taking care of those relatives that need them.

Having the opportunity to change shifts and to reducing the working time to those with small children is the most relevant factor obtained after analysing the employee's perception data; the flexibility of the work is important for them because it allows them to better organize their daily life to carry their kids to school, to go to the doctor or to take care of themselves in case they were ill, etc.

The ANOVA analysis carried out after the AHP and the BN analysis highlighted significant differences according to the education level, and for users living with dependents. Medium level education and those living with dependents are the groups expressing the lowest levels of satisfaction.

Interim summary of findings of Use Case IV

Taken together, women have less favourable view of the railway transport workplace than men. Across all three data sets, there was some indication of less satisfaction with organisational culture such as inclusiveness of the organisation, gender balance in the sector and women's acceptance by male peers. However, context specific issues also were highlighted, for example, in the Northern European sample, there was greater concern around cost of childcare compared to the other samples indicative of country specific policies i.e., state run affordable child care vs. Privatised costly child care. Overall, women showed lower satisfaction with fairness and inclusivity of women in transport which we must properly acknowledge and incorporate into our model and toolkits.

10. References

- Awad-Núñez, N. González-Cancelas, F. Soler-Flores, A. Camarero-Orive, A. (2016) Methodology for Measuring Sustainability of Dry Ports Location Based on Bayesian Networks and Multi-criteria Decision Analysis, *Transp. Res. Procedia*. 13 124–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2016.05.013>.
- Bermejo, I., Oliva, J., Díez, F. J., & Arias, M. (2012). Interactive learning of Bayesian networks using OpenMarkov. *Proceedings of the 6th European Workshop on Probabilistic Graphical Models, PGM 2012*, 27–34.
- Bouyssou, D., Marchant, T., Pirlot, M., Perny, P., Tsoukias, A., & Vincke, P. (2000). *Evaluation Models: A Critical Perspective*. Kluwer, Boston.
- Bruce, Peter, and Andrew Bruce. (2017). *Practical Statistics for Data Scientists*. O'Reilly Media.
- Cheng, C. H., Yang, K. L., & Hwang, C. L. (1999). Evaluating attack helicopters by AHP based on linguistic variable weight. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 116(2), 423–435. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217\(98\)00156-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217(98)00156-8)
- Cooper, G. F., & Herskovits, E. (1992). A Bayesian Method for the Induction of Probabilistic Networks from Data. *Machine Learning*, 9, 309–347.
- Criado-Perez, C. (2019). Invisible women: Exposing data bias in a world designed for men. Great Britain: Vintage Publishing. Retrieved from <https://www.overdrive.com/search?q=91115E7D-9D96-434F-9996-E60D55BDF481>
- Díez, F. J., París, I., Pérez Martín, J., & Arias, M. (2018). Teaching Bayesian networks with OpenMarkov. *PGM 2018*, Praga, Czech Republic, September.
- Ekpanyapong, M., Waterwai, T., & Sung Kyu Lim. (2006). Statistical bellman-ford algorithm with an application to retiming. *Asia and South Pacific Conference on Design Automation, 2006.*, 959–964. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ASPDAC.2006.1594810>
- European Commission. (2017). *New Horizons: Data from a Delphi Survey in Support of European Union Future Policies in Research and Innovation*. Luxemburg: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/654172>
- Friedman N, Nachman I, Pe'er D (1999) Learning bayesian network structure from massive datasets: The "sparse candidate" algorithm. In: *Proceedings of the Fifteenth Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence (UAI'99)*, pp 206–215
- Gallagher, R. J., Frank, M. R., Mitchell, Lewis, Schwartz, A. J., Reagan, A. J., Danforth, C. M., Dodds, P. S. (2021). Generalized Word Shift Graphs: A Method for Visualizing and Explaining Pairwise Comparisons Between Texts. *EPJ Data Science*, 10(4).
- Gámez, J. A., Mateo, J. L., & Puerta, J. M. (2011). Learning Bayesian networks by hill climbing: Efficient methods based on progressive restriction of the neighborhood. *Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery*, 22(1–2), 106–148.

García-Jiménez, E., Poveda-Reyes, S., Molero, G.D., Santarremigia, F.E., Gorrini, A., Hail, Y., Ababio-Donkor, A., Leva, M.C., & Mauriello, F. (2020). Methodology for gender analysis in transport: factors with influence in women's inclusion as professionals and users of transport infrastructures, *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3656. International Transport Forum (2018). Women's Safety and Security: A Public Transport Priority. OECD Publishing.

Geethanjali, B., Adalarasu, K., Hemapraba, A., Kumar, S. P., & Rajasekeran, R. (2017). Emotion analysis using SAM (self-assessment manikin) scale.

Halvey, M. J., & Keane, M. T. (2007). An assessment of tag presentation techniques. In Proceedings of the 16th international conference on World Wide Web (pp. 1313-1314).

Hastie, Trevor (2009). The Elements of Statistical Learning. Springer. p. 203. ISBN 978-0-387-84857-0.

James, Gareth, Daniela Witten, Trevor Hastie, and Robert Tibshirani. (2014). An Introduction to Statistical Learning: With Applications in R. Springer Publishing Company, Incorporated.

Lang, P. J., Bradley, M. M., & Cuthbert, B. N. (1999). International affective picture system (IAPS): Instruction manual and affective ratings. The center for research in psychophysiology, University of Florida.

Laniado, D., Kaltenbrunner, A., Castillo, C., & Morell, M. F. (2012). Emotions and dialogue in a peer-production community: the case of Wikipedia. In Proceedings of the eighth annual international symposium on Wikis and open collaboration (pp. 1-10).

Laparra-Hernández, J., J. M. Belda-Lois, E. Medina, N. Campos, and R. Poveda. 2009. 'EMG and GSR Signals for Evaluating User's Perception of Different Types of Ceramic Flooring'. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* 39 (2): 326–332.

Lerner, B., & Malka, R. (2011). Investigation of the K2 algorithm in learning bayesian network classifiers. *Applied Artificial Intelligence*, 25(1), 74–96.

Mohammad, S. (2018). Obtaining reliable human ratings of valence, arousal, and dominance for 20,000 english words. In Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers) (pp. 174-184).

Molero, G. D., Santarremigia, F. E., Poveda-Reyes, S., Mayrhofer, M., Awad-Núñez, S., Kassabji, A., ... Awad-Núñez, S. Kassabji, A. (2018). Key factors for the implementation and integration of innovative ICT solutions in SMEs and large companies involved in the multimodal transport of dangerous goods. *European Transport Research Review*, 11(28), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12544-019-0362-8>

Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., & Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA), pp. 392–399.

Nardelli, M., Valenza, G., Greco, A., Lanata, A., & Scilingo, E. P. (2015). Recognizing emotions induced by affective sounds through heart rate variability. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, 6(4), 385-394.

Özdağoğlu, A., & Özdağoğlu, G. (2007). Comparison Of AHP and FUZZY AHP For The MCDM Processes With Linguistic Evaluations. *Istambul Ticaret Universitesi Fen Bilimleri Dergisi*, 1, 65–85.

Perez, C. C. (2019). *Invisible women: Exposing data bias in a world designed for men*. Random House.

Ramírez Hereza, P. (2020). *Redes Bayesianas para predicción y descubrimiento de relaciones con señales procedentes de sensores industriales*. Universidad Autónoma de Madrid.

Saaty R.W. (1987), "The analytic hierarchy process: what it is and how it is used", *Mathematical Modelling*, 9, 161-176.

Saaty, T. L. (2016). The Analytic Hierarchy and Analytic Network Processes for the Measurement of Intangible Criteria and for Decision-Making. In S. Greco, M. Ehrgott, & J. Figueira (Eds.), *Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis. International Series in Operations Research & Management Science*. Volume 233 (2nd ed., pp. 363–419). Springer, New York, NY. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4939-3094-4>

Schwarz, G. (1978). Estimating the dimension of a model. *Annals of statistics*, 6(2), 461-464.

Scutari, M., Graafland, C. E., & Gutiérrez, J. M. (2019). Who learns better Bayesian network structures: Accuracy and speed of structure learning algorithms. *International Journal of Approximate Reasoning*, 115, 235–253.

Spirtes, P., & Glymour, C. (1991). An algorithm for fast recovery of sparse causal graphs. *Social science computer review*, 9(1), 62-72.

Sulaiman, O. K., Siregar, A. M., Nasution, K., & Haramaini, T. (2018). Bellman Ford algorithm - in Routing Information Protocol (RIP). *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1007(1), 012009.

Tausczik, Y. R., & Pennebaker, J. W. (2010). The psychological meaning of words: LIWC and computerized text analysis methods. *Journal of language and social psychology*, 29(1), 24-54.

Taylor, B. W. (2004). *Introduction to Management Science*. (P. E. Inc., Ed.). New Jersey.

Vaidya, O. S., & Kumar, S. (2006). Analytic hierarchy process: An overview of applications. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 169(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2004.04.028>

Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In: *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

Zhou, S. H., Oetomo, D., Tan, Y., Burdet, E., & Mareels, I. (2012). Modeling individual human motor behavior through model reference iterative learning control. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 59(7), 1892-1901.

